

**THE DEVELOPMENT, IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION
OF A TEXT-MESSAGING INTERVENTION TARGETING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY
AND SEDENTARY BEHAVIOUR IN ADOLESCENTS**

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Declaration of authenticity and author's rights

I declare that the content presented in this thesis is original work, conducted and written by the author, and has not been submitted previously for another academic degree at any institution.

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Abstract

Despite significant evidence that increased physical activity (PA) and reduced sedentary behaviour (SB) are linked to health benefits, globally only 19% of adolescents are sufficiently active. There is an acute need for novel interventions as current approaches are not consistently effective. Interventions using mobile health (mHealth) technology, for example via text messages (SMS) have shown promise for improving activity behaviours however there is little evidence regarding the effectiveness of SMS. Indeed, there is currently a lack of research exploring the use of SMS in isolation without additional intervention components such as apps and websites. The aim of this thesis was to develop, implement, and evaluate an SMS intervention focusing on adolescent PA and SB. The respective studies focused on exploring the effectiveness, delivery, content, and use of theory within existing interventions (Study 1); using a mixed methods approach to assess feasibility, participant preferences, and initial efficacy of a short-term pilot intervention (Study 2 & 3); and exploring feasibility, fidelity, acceptability, and initial efficacy of an 8-week SMS intervention (Study 4).

Study 1 involved a systematic review of the evidence base of SMS interventions, which target adolescent PA and SB. The results demonstrated that whilst some were effective, high heterogeneity of SMS content, delivery, and outcome measures was evident. Interventions tend to use multiple components, focus mainly on PA, and are most frequently guided by the Transtheoretical Model (TTM) and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). Furthermore, research is needed to determine the most effective intervention content and delivery characteristics for interventions using SMS in isolation.

Study 2 and 3 explored the feasibility, participant preferences, and initial efficacy of a 3-week SMS intervention implemented among secondary school pupils through a qualitative study and cluster randomised trial. Two cohorts from year four and five representing an intervention (N=25, mean age 17 ± 0.2 years) and waitlist control group (N=27; mean age 15 ± 0.3 years) were recruited. Between three and seven SMS were sent each week at varying times, containing information, advice, feedback, and motivational support based on Theory of

Planned Behaviour (TPB), SCT and self-efficacy theory as well as several behaviour change techniques (BCTs). Within Study 2, 24 intervention group participants took part in four focus group discussions to obtain an in-depth account of intervention experiences and perceived behaviour change. Educational and behavioural SMS were perceived useful, with timing of delivery representing a crucial factor for behaviour change. There were varying preferences for theory, content, and frequency, with a specific call for more tailoring of SMS delivery.

In Study 3, 52 participants wore an ActiGraph GT3X+ on the wrist and activPAL4 on the thigh for seven days at baseline and post-intervention to assess PA by measuring moderate to vigorous PA (MVPA), average acceleration (AA) and intensity gradient (IG), and assess SB by measuring sitting and standing time, sit to stand transitions, and sitting bouts of different durations. At baseline, participants in the intervention and control group did not achieve current MVPA guidelines (mean daily MVPA 37.8 and 37.5 minutes, respectively). Univariate Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) revealed no significant differences in post-intervention outcomes between the intervention and waitlist control group. However, the findings indicated that a short-term, SMS intervention was feasible for implementation among adolescents with a recruitment rate of 90%, complete case data for both devices between 60-75%, and 76% of participants replying to at least one SMS.

In Study 4, the feasibility, fidelity, acceptability, and initial efficacy of an 8-week interactive SMS intervention was assessed using mixed methods. Thirty-six participants were recruited from a local secondary school, with 34 (26 female, mean age 13.6 ± 0.5 years) fulfilling the inclusion criteria for the intervention. SMS provided information, advice, feedback, and motivational support guided by the TPB, SCT and TTM, and BCTs linked to these theories. ActiGraph GT3X+ and activPAL4 devices were worn simultaneously for seven days and data showed small improvements for MVPA (mean change 1.8 minutes/day) and AA (1.1mg), with an increase in standing time (0.2 hours/day) and sit to stand transitions (0.1/day). However, there were also small increases in sitting time (0.6 hours/day), fewer sitting bouts of < 30 minutes (-1.1/day), and more bouts lasting between 30 < 60 minutes (1.1/day). Self-report

questionnaires were used for exploring healthy eating and psychological outcomes, with small improvements for healthy eating scores (mean change 0.87), SB self-efficacy (0.02), PA intention (0.08) and PA subjective norm (0.77). There were decreases in PA (-0.03) and SB attitude (-0.14), PA self-efficacy (-0.19), SB intention (-0.62), SB subjective norm (-1.23) and PA (-0.10), and SB perceived behavioural control (-0.25). Following the intervention, all participants categorised within the maintenance stage for PA, with more participants within precontemplation for SB. Recruitment rate was 51%, with an attrition of 39% between week one and eight, with SMS interaction reducing from week one (70%) to seven (30%). A focus group discussion with eight participants revealed varying preferences for SMS content and delivery, with tailoring of advice, information, frequency, and timing required.

Overall, there is a high level of heterogeneity within the current evidence base of mHealth interventions using SMS. Pilot feasibility testing showed some promise for using SMS in isolation, however more research is needed to explore the most effective content, including theories and BCTs to guide this, as well as frequency and timing. Future trials should include tailored content and delivery, as well as primary and clinical care settings to allow young people with acute needs for increasing PA, reducing SB, and enhancing healthy eating to benefit from such efforts.

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"I did then what I knew how to do. Now that I know better, I do better."

Maja Angelou

A version of this quote was stuck to my computer for the most part of my PhD. It rang very true to me on many occasions. My PhD has been, as cliché as it sounds, a journey. I have learned a lot and am grateful for the ride. Sweat and tears, but also a lot of laughter, excitement, and energy has gone into this work over the last 4 years. There are a few people I would like to acknowledge who have supported me in many ways.

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Author publications and presentations

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Abbreviations

AA	Average acceleration
ANCOVA	Univariate Analysis of Covariance
BCT	Behaviour change technique
BMI	Body Mass Index
CI	Confidence interval
CONSORT	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials
COREQ	Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research
CCT	Cybernetic Control Theory
ENMO	Euclidean Norm Minus 1g
GP	General Practitioner
IG	Intensity gradient
LPA	Light physical activity
MET	Metabolic equivalent
mHealth	mobile Health
MPA	Moderate physical activity
MRC	Medical Research Council
MVPA	Moderate to vigorous physical activity
NHS	National Health Service
PA	Physical activity
PE	Physical education

PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
SB	Sedentary behaviour
SCT	Social Cognitive Theory
SD	Standard deviation
SDT	Self-Determination Theory
SE	Standard error
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SMS	Text message(s)
SOC	Stage of Motivational Readiness for Change
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
TTM	Transtheoretical Model
UK	United Kingdom
VPA	Vigorous physical activity
WHO	World Health Organisation

Chapter 1

Introduction

The overall aim of this programme of work was to explore the feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of using SMS to increase PA and reduce SB among adolescents. As part of this, the aim was to systematically review the current evidence base on using SMS for targeting PA and SB in adolescents and designing original research to explore the feasibility, acceptability, including user experiences and preferences, and the effectiveness of using SMS to support health behaviour change with regards to PA and SB.

My research was part-funded by the United Kingdom (UK) National Health Service (NHS) Lanarkshire's Child Healthy Weight Unit in Scotland. It has been estimated that obesity costs the NHS around £6.1 billion every year, with government plans in place since 2016 to outline policies to tackle childhood obesity (Davies, 2020). In addition to providing funding for conducting my PhD programme of work, NHS Lanarkshire and their staff were to support my work by facilitating the use of the NHS's SMS delivery system 'Florence'. Currently, Florence is used primarily for sending General Practitioner (GP) appointment reminders and allowing hypertension patients to send blood pressure readings directly to their GP via SMS. Such SMS services aim to reduce face-to-face contact and find more efficient ways for treating patients and providing advice and signposting to other services. There have been some internal NHS trials to send SMS to patients on weight management pathways. This currently only involves adults and using Florence for sending SMS directly to adolescents for encouraging PA and reducing SB was novel throughout the UK.

It has been postulated that for childhood and adolescent health, structural determinants of health, including political and socioeconomic factors hold particular importance (Pearce *et al.*, 2019). Only recently, an overview of physical activity research has found an increased need for focusing on societal, policy, and macro-economic changes impacting health behaviour change (Ding *et al.*, 2020). For reducing health inequalities, focusing on systemic structures that contribute to unequal socio-economic distributions remains important as this

may impede other efforts that focus on individual-level determinants (Pearce *et al.*, 2019). Despite this evidence, a systematic review of interventions aiming to reduce childhood obesity found a clear lack of studies exploring societal-level programmes for addressing obesity, such as through enhancing diet and PA (Hillier-Brown *et al.*, 2014). For obesity policy specifically, it has been found that in the UK, a strong focus on individual behaviours, rather than high-level, interventionist policies remains, with limited effects on behaviours such as PA and diet (Theis and White, 2021). Particularly during later childhood and early adulthood, individual-level correlates of PA, such as beliefs and motivation, appear to be less impactful compared to environmental and policy factors (Bauman *et al.*, 2012). Thus, there have been calls for research to move away from solely focusing on individual-level determinants, including psychological factors like self-efficacy, attitudes and perceived social support, towards wider determinants with the aim to promote behaviour change (Dahlgren and Whitehead, 1991; Bauman *et al.*, 2012). Despite this, research has acknowledged a need for studies to explore behaviour change mechanisms through analysis of psychological factors to enhance intervention effectiveness (Ding *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the research conducted as part of this thesis focused on providing participant-led, theory-based intervention content with a focus on psychological factors impacting PA and SB change. It was expected that despite the need for policy-level changes within NHS care pathways, the provision of individual-level approaches should be improved, with a particular need for low-burden, low-cost and implementation-ready interventions. In addition, the inclusion of psychological factors associated with PA and SB change was predicted to enhance the present understanding of behaviour change mechanisms as well as improve intervention effectiveness, particularly when system-level support and care provision is unavailable.

The aim of my research was for the findings of my studies to directly influence NHS Lanarkshire's use of SMS to send information and advice to adolescents currently on the weight management and preventing diabetes pathways within the Child Healthy Weight Unit. It was crucial for my studies to be conducted in real-world settings to assess how feasible

and acceptable such SMS are when used with adolescents as well as what type of information or advice is most useful and effective.

To ensure participants from different socio-economic and cultural backgrounds were included in my studies, secondary schools were chosen as the main route for recruitment.

Considering the variety of pupils that were expected to be involved in our research, it was crucial to not only explore feasibility and effectiveness using device-based measures, but also delve into participant experiences and preferences for SMS interventions. Due to the novel nature of the developed intervention, my work was to provide a comprehensive, in-depth account of participant experiences and their perceived usefulness of the SMS in addition to device-based changes in PA and SB.

The below figure provides an overview of the organisation of this thesis, including individual study chapters and their respective aims (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Overview of thesis organisation and respective study aims

In addition to the studies included in this thesis, two attempts were made to conduct a meta-analysis of SMS interventions for adolescent PA and SB. The first attempt was made concurrently with Study 1, however the studies included in the systematic review were too heterogenous to warrant pooling quantitative data. A second attempt was made following the completion of Study 4, with more generous inclusion criteria than Study 1, such as allowing for a broader age range, and using more liberal criteria during the initial citation sifting phase. Whilst many studies have been published around SMS and mobile device-based interventions since the first attempt and the search criteria were broadened, the remaining pool of studies was once again too small and heterogenous to warrant conducting a meta-analysis. Thus, there is a need for future meta-analyses to explore the efficacy of health behaviour change interventions for adolescents using SMS in isolation.

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1 Defining physical activity and sedentary behaviour

PA can be defined as “any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in energy expenditure” (Caspersen, Powell and Christenson, 1985, p. 126), which includes behaviours such as walking, cycling, playground games and doing sports. Recently, more holistic definitions of PA have appeared with the aim to enhance the focus on individuals and behavioural, social, and cultural context they are active in (Piggin, 2020). A recent definition describes PA as involving “people moving, acting and performing within culturally specific spaces and context, and influenced by a unique array of interests, emotions, ideas, instructions and relationships” (Piggin, 2020, p.5).

Considering the complexity of PA as a health behaviour, domains are commonly used as a frame for PA behaviours across different age groups. For adults, the World Health Organisation (WHO) has defined four different domains, including PA at work, PA for transport, domestic PA, and leisure time PA (World Health Organisation, 2003). For adolescents, studies have defined a variety of domains specific to this age group and the contexts in which PA tends to occur (Smith *et al.*, 2016; Dearth-Wesley *et al.*, 2017). These include PA during school hours, out of school PA, including leisure time sporting activities, active travel to and from school and any other walking (Smith *et al.*, 2016; Dearth-Wesley *et al.*, 2017). As a further classification to describe different activity behaviours, intensity is frequently used. PA and SB have been described to exist along a continuum from sleep to vigorous PA (VPA), which is categorised based on intensity, using metabolic equivalents (METs; Figure 2).

Figure 2. Intensity continuum from sleep to MVPA using METs (Carson and Hunter, 2020, p.9) ¹

A common categorisation of PA describes light PA (LPA) between 1.5-4 METs, moderate PA (MPA) and VPA (Pate, O'Neill and Lobelo, 2008). Frequently, a combination of MPA and VPA is being described as MVPA between 4-6 METs. For adolescents, LPAs typically include activities such as walking or housework, with MPA involving activities such as cycling or playing ball games, and VPA encompassing fast running or swimming (Butte *et al.*, 2018). Research has shown that adolescents tend to spend only around 5% of a 24-hour cycle in activities of moderate to vigorous intensity (Chaput *et al.*, 2014). Whilst higher intensity PA shows bigger effects on health outcomes compared to lower intensity PA, it has been demonstrated that even LPA is associated with improvements in cardiometabolic outcomes, such as diastolic blood pressure and Body Mass Index (BMI) (Carson *et al.*, 2013; Tarp *et al.*, 2018; Contardo Ayala *et al.*, 2020). This evidence demonstrates the importance of several different PA intensities, including LPA when focusing on adolescent activity behaviours.

With regards to SB, reaching a comprehensive definition which accounts for behaviours evident across all age groups and allows for chronic conditions and mobility impairments to be considered, has been challenging (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017). An expert consensus was tasked to provide a general definition of SB, which includes emerging behaviours such as screen time (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017). From this, the now widely used definition describes SB

¹ *The Routledge Handbook of Youth Physical Activity (2020). Publisher: Taylor and Francis Group LLC (Books) US. Editors: Brusseau, T. A., Fairclough, S. J., & Lubans, D. R. Reproduced with permission of The Licensor through PLSclear*

as any waking behaviour of ≤ 1.5 metabolic equivalents, while sitting, reclining, or lying (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017). For adolescents, this includes common behaviours such as watching TV, reading, using a computer, phone, or tablet, and doing homework (Dearth-Wesley *et al.*, 2017). Research has shown that adolescents spend around 55% of a 24-hour cycle in SB and LPA (Chaput *et al.*, 2014), which further underlines the importance of SB when targeting activity behaviours.

PA and SB are complex behaviours and research has shown that for youth, there is only a weak negative association between PA and SB (Pearson *et al.*, 2014) and a reduction in SB does not inherently result in an increase in PA (Epstein *et al.*, 2005). These findings therefore do not support the 'displacement hypothesis', which describes that SB displaces PA (Mutz, Roberts and van Vuuren, 1993), but may indicate that those with high levels of PA may simultaneously also present high levels of SB and vice versa (Marshall *et al.*, 2002). This is supported by evidence from multiple studies of adolescent boys and girls, showing that higher levels of PA can be accompanied by high levels of SB, whilst low PA and low SB can also coexist (Marshall *et al.*, 2002; te Velde *et al.*, 2007). These findings emphasise the need to avoid making inferences from one outcome to the other, e.g. presuming low PA due to high SB (Pearson *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, evidence has shown that certain types of SB have independent associations with key health markers such as cardiorespiratory fitness, metabolic risk, and waist circumference, regardless of PA (Healy *et al.*, 2008; Chaput *et al.*, 2013; Santos *et al.*, 2014). These findings underline the importance of considering PA and SB as distinct behaviours that are independently associated with a variety of health outcomes (Pearson *et al.*, 2014; Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Carson and Hunter, 2020).

2.2 Health benefits of physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviour

Increasing PA and reducing SB for promoting health has been widely recognised and incorporated into a variety of government and health agency strategies. In 2010, the Toronto Charter for PA outlined guiding principles for promoting PA and health globally, which included using a life-course approach to encourage children and adolescents as well as

adults and older adults to increase PA (Global Advocacy Council for Physical Activity and International Society for Physical Activity and Health, 2010). In 2014, the WHO set out the 'European child and adolescent health strategy 2015-2020' specifically to promote health and wellbeing among youth (World Health Organisation Regional Office for Europe, 2014). This initiative underlined the importance of developing favourable health behaviours, such as PA, during youth to ensure positive health and wellbeing is maintained into adulthood (World Health Organisation Regional Office for Europe, 2014). Moreover, another governing body, the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, also recommend promoting PA among children and adolescents specifically to achieve benefits related to physical and mental health and avoid the detrimental effects of inactivity, such as an increased risk of developing chronic health conditions (Division of Population Health, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, 2020).

These government and health organisation-led strategies are based on well-established evidence that adolescence is a particularly crucial time for promoting health, as behaviours developed during this time are likely to continue into later life (Telama *et al.*, 2014; Hayes *et al.*, 2019). For example, a longitudinal study found that negative health behaviours such as smoking and alcohol use at age 15 and 21 are moderately to strongly linked to smoking and alcohol use at age 28 (Paavola, Vartiainen and Haukkala, 2004). For PA specifically, evidence shows a moderate tracking effect from adolescence into young adulthood (Hayes *et al.*, 2019), with PA at age 15 and 21 linked with PA at age 28 (Paavola, Vartiainen and Haukkala, 2004). For SB, a moderate tracking effect has been shown from childhood into adolescence (Biddle *et al.*, 2010). Crucially, PA has positive long-term effects on noncommunicable diseases, including obesity, chronic heart disease and type 2 diabetes (Reiner *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, higher after school PA and physical education (PE) participation at school in youth are linked with increased PA, cardiorespiratory fitness, and metabolic health in adulthood (Ekblom-Bak *et al.*, 2018).

The benefits of sufficient PA and a reduction of SB on mental and physical health during adolescence have been well established (Alves *et al.*, 2016; Poitras *et al.*, 2016; Biddle *et al.*, 2019; Pascoe *et al.*, 2020). For mental health, findings from a recent meta-analysis demonstrate a link between increased PA and adolescent mental health, highlighting the importance of promoting PA and reducing SB during youth (Rodriguez-Ayllon *et al.*, 2019). Further, research has shown links between adolescent PA and depression, anxiety, self-esteem, and cognitive functioning (Biddle *et al.*, 2019; Kandola *et al.*, 2020), with causal associations evident between PA, cognitive functioning, and depression (Biddle *et al.*, 2019). A systematic review of the associations between device-measured PA and health in children and adolescents has also demonstrated positive links between PA, quality of life and wellbeing (Poitras *et al.*, 2016). Whilst findings indicate that lower levels of MVPA were linked to reduced academic achievement in adolescents (Haapala *et al.*, 2020), previous research had shown a positive association between PA and academic outcomes only for maths, with inconclusive and limited evidence for overall academic performance (Poitras *et al.*, 2016; Singh *et al.*, 2019).

For physical health, a positive association between MVPA and cardiometabolic health is evident (Skrede *et al.*, 2019), with systematic review findings showing a link between device-measured PA and adiposity as well as cholesterol, blood pressure, triglycerides, insulin resistance, fasting insulin, and fasting glucose in school-aged children (Poitras *et al.*, 2016). In addition, bone health and motor skill development have also been linked to PA within this age group (Poitras *et al.*, 2016). Further, it has been shown that MVPA and SB are independently associated with cardiorespiratory fitness (Santos *et al.*, 2014) and PA is linked with increased aerobic capacity and muscular fitness in adolescents (Poitras *et al.*, 2016; Hui *et al.*, 2020).

Considering the benefits associated with increased PA and reduced SB, research has explored the impact of different PA intensities and replacing SB with PA on adolescent health. A recent meta-analysis explored the health benefits of replacing prolonged SB with

LPA or MVPA in youth (Wijndaele *et al.*, 2019). The findings demonstrate that MVPA provides more beneficial effects for cardio-metabolic risk factors, such as adiposity and blood pressure, compared to LPA (Wijndaele *et al.*, 2019). These findings are in line with those of other research showing that higher intensity PA provides greater reductions for mortality and other health benefits compared to low intensity PA (Poitras *et al.*, 2016; Strain *et al.*, 2020). Reduced SB and increased PA of all intensities is associated with lower mortality, with higher intensities and bigger increases substantially reducing premature mortality (Ekelund *et al.*, 2019). Research has also shown that LPA and MVPA may reduce symptoms related to depression and anxiety among young people (Pascoe *et al.*, 2020). It is evident that even slight increases in LPA can reduce mortality and improve mental health (Ekelund *et al.*, 2020; Pascoe *et al.*, 2020), with higher intensity activities, such as MVPA providing additional benefits (Ekelund *et al.*, 2020).

2.3 Physical activity guidelines and prevalence rates

Considering the wealth of evidence outlining the benefits of achieving increased levels of PA and reducing SB, guidelines have been put into place to inform the public, practitioners, researchers, and policy makers regarding which levels of PA are required to achieve notable health benefits. In 2010, the WHO published an official set of recommendations for children and adolescents, which was updated in 2020 (World Health Organisation, 2010; Bull *et al.*, 2020). The most recent guidelines state that children and adolescents should achieve at least an average of 60 minutes of daily MVPA across the week (Bull *et al.*, 2020). Further, aerobic as well as muscle and bone strengthening activities of vigorous intensity should be done on at least three days per week (Bull *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, SB should be limited, especially with regards to screen time (Bull *et al.*, 2020). Crucially, these new guidelines emphasize the importance of even small increases in LPA and MPA, with a gradual increase to achieve the health benefits associated with performing more PA of higher intensities (Bull *et al.*, 2020). A review of current PA guidelines has shown that globally, 25 countries have national guidelines for PA (Parrish *et al.*, 2020). Nineteen countries have adopted the

existing WHO recommendations for PA with 22 including additional guidelines for SB (Parrish *et al.*, 2020).

The current UK PA guidelines for children aged five to 18 years include that SB should be reduced whenever possible, whilst also breaking up prolonged SB with at least LPA (UK Chief Medical Officers, 2019). In addition, three countries have adopted 24-hour movement guidelines, which include recommendations for PA, SB, and sleep. This includes Canada, Australia, and New Zealand, who recommend that 5-17-year-olds should sleep eight to 11 hours and limit recreational screen time to a maximum of two hours per day (Canadian Society for Exercise Physiology, 2016; New Zealand Government, 2017; Australian Government Department of Health, 2019).

Whilst the benefits of increasing PA and reducing SB have been well established and global recommendations for the required level of PA to achieve these benefits have been in place since 2010, PA levels among adolescents are low (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). In 2016, only 19% of adolescents aged 11-17 years worldwide achieved the recommended amount of 60 minutes of MVPA per day (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). It is also evident that boys are more active than girls, with boys showing a significant increase in PA levels since 2001 (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). This is supported by evidence from a large-scale study with over 340,000 adolescents from 52 countries, which also found evidence of boys being more active than girls (Bann *et al.*, 2019). National survey data from the UK shows that 47% of young people aged five to 16 years in England (Sport England, 2019) and 37% of children aged two to 15 years in Scotland achieve 60 minutes of MVPA per day (Scottish Government National Statistics, 2020).

Within the UK, gender differences are also evident, with boys more likely to achieve the guidelines compared to girls (Sport England, 2019; Scottish Government National Statistics, 2020). Crucially, PA levels are highest at age five to seven years, with adolescents aged 13-16 years showing the lowest levels of PA compared to other school year groups (Sport England, 2019). This evidence is in line with findings from Europe and China, which reported

lower PA among older children compared to younger age groups (Fernandes, 2018; Zhu *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, a large-scale study analysing device-based PA from over 27,000 participants from 10 countries showed that there is reduction in PA starting with children aged five years through to adolescents aged 18 years (Cooper *et al.*, 2015). As PA also tends to decline from adolescence to adulthood (Corder *et al.*, 2019), it is clear that behaviours that will improve health need to be encouraged and established during youth.

With regards to SB, a study using accelerometer data found that adolescents tend to show higher levels of SB, including screen time, compared to younger children (Janssen *et al.*, 2016; Thomas *et al.*, 2020). At age 15, around 70% of waking hours are spent sitting down (Janssen *et al.*, 2016; Arundell *et al.*, 2019), compared to 51% at age seven (Janssen *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, a study using accelerometer data of around 6000 children found that SB tracks moderately over time, with increases of around 21 minutes per day, per year (van Ekris *et al.*, 2020). It has also been demonstrated that adolescents sit more during school compared to after school hours and at home (Arundell *et al.*, 2019; Ortega *et al.*, 2020), with higher SB levels on weekdays compared to weekend days (Arundell *et al.*, 2019). Further, there are some indications that girls tend to show higher levels of SB compared to boys (Wang *et al.*, 2019). Thus, whilst it has been shown that a decline in PA levels is evident from age seven (Farooq *et al.*, 2018) and from primary to secondary school (Remmers *et al.*, 2020), it is crucial to promote PA during adolescence to ensure healthy behaviours can be established before adulthood.

2.4 Measurement of adolescent activity behaviours

To ensure current interventions for adolescent PA and SB can be evaluated and inferences made for future research and practice, accurate measures of those activity behaviours are required. The Behavioral Epidemiology Framework outlines five different types of research including basic research (e.g. physiological mechanisms influencing health), health outcomes research (e.g. associations between behaviours and health outcomes), surveillance research (e.g. trends and patterns of behaviours), theory and correlate research (e.g. causes and

correlates of behaviours) and intervention research (e.g. evaluation of interventions for PA and SB) (Sallis, Owen and Fotheringham, 2000). Each of these types of research require accurate measurement tools to ensure true behaviours are captured. An adapted model of the Behavioral Epidemiology Framework also describes three types of measurements which can be used including report-based (e.g. questionnaires), monitor-based (e.g. accelerometers) and criterion measures (e.g. doubly labelled water technique) (Welk, Morrow and Saint-Maurice, 2017).

The measurement of activity behaviours among children and adolescents in particular is complex, as activities are often intermittent and incidental (Fairclough and Noonan, 2020). Moreover, activities can be unstructured or structured and range across different domains of PA and SB, including during school hours, after school hours and active travel (Fairclough and Noonan, 2020). There are a variety of measurement tools for PA and SB that aim to capture different elements of these behaviours, including intensity, duration, domain, or context (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011; Sylvia *et al.*, 2014). When choosing measurement tools for PA and SB, ease of use and accuracy is considered important (Hardy *et al.*, 2013; Fairclough and Noonan, 2020) as some validated tools may not be feasible for use within the desired contexts due to cost and available expertise. The following provides an overview of self-report and device-based measures for PA and SB.

2.4.1 Self-report measures

Self-report measures for PA and SB in children and adolescents frequently include questionnaires or recall interviews. The popularity of such measures is due to their ease of use and inexpensive nature, as well as their ability to capture contexts and domains of activities for large population groups (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011). However, these measures also come with some limitations, including issues surrounding recall bias and social desirability effects (Sallis and Saelens, 2000). PA and SB are complex, incidental behaviours, which are difficult to recall accurately, with children tending to overestimate their own PA levels (Hussey, Bell and Gormley, 2007). This is in line with findings from

adolescents which found poor agreement between questionnaire and device-based PA data with PA data tending to be overestimated when self-reported (Monyeki *et al.*, 2018).

It has been suggested that self-report data is likely to omit more sporadic bouts of activity, which are easily forgotten when recalling behaviours (Biddle *et al.*, 2011). Whilst there are many different questionnaires for measuring PA and SB in youth, only few demonstrate strong reliability and validity (Biddle *et al.*, 2011). A recent review of PA questionnaires for children and adolescents has found that whilst 89 different questionnaires were identified, only one showed acceptable validity for adolescents, with none demonstrating strong validity and reliability (Hidding *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, whilst there are many questionnaires for SB in children and adolescents, these also tend to show poor validity and reliability (Hidding *et al.*, 2017). Considering these limitations in current self-report measures for adolescent PA and SB, device-based measures have become increasingly popular, particularly for evaluating intervention research.

2.4.2 Device-based measures

For assessing adolescent PA and SB, device-based measures such as accelerometers are increasingly being used (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011). Historically, these have been referred to as 'objective' measures (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011), however in recent years, researchers have promoted and increasingly used the term 'device-based' measures (see for example Prince *et al.*, 2020; Strain *et al.*, 2020). This is due to the analysis of accelerometer data involving subjective decisions with regards to data processing, including for selecting cut points and wear time criteria, and issues of social desirability and intentional non-wear time (Pedišić and Bauman, 2015). These decision-making and device-wear related elements of working with accelerometers underline the importance of understanding the level of subjectivity involved in this process and support the use of terminology that reflects this (Pedišić and Bauman, 2015).

Accelerometers tend to be small, lightweight devices, which measure movement in acceleration (Chen and Bassett, 2005) and have historically been worn on the hip using an

elastic belt (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011). A recent systematic review explored the accuracy of accelerometers for measuring PA and SB compared with energy expenditure measured by indirect calorimetry in children and adolescents (Lynch *et al.*, 2019). Their findings show that accelerometers can accurately measure PA and SB, however devices worn on the hip appear to be more accurate than wrist worn devices (Lynch *et al.*, 2019). Despite this, in recent years, accelerometers have increasingly been worn on the wrist to increase wear time compliance, with research showing higher wear time for devices worn on the wrist, compared to the hip (Fairclough *et al.*, 2016; McLellan, Arthur and Buchan, 2018). To ensure PA and SB outcomes derived from accelerometer data are reflective of typical activities, it is crucial for devices to be worn in line with chosen wear time criteria. It has been recommended that devices should be given to participants for seven days (Migueles *et al.*, 2017), with around three to four days of valid wear needed for results to be sufficiently reliable and representative of usual behaviours (Cain *et al.*, 2013).

Generally, there are several different accelerometer brands and models that are frequently used in current PA research. These include devices such as the GENEActiv (Activinsights, Huntingdon, UK) and Axivity (Axivity, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK), two watch-like, wrist-worn accelerometers. The most widely used brand is ActiGraph (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, US), with several review and validation studies focusing on these devices due to their popularity in current research (Cain *et al.*, 2013; Migueles *et al.*, 2017; Steene-Johannessen *et al.*, 2020). The ActiGraph GT3X+ allows for triaxial assessment of movement behaviours and can be worn on the hip and wrist (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). It has been widely used in PA research with adolescents and validated methods for data collection, processing and analysis are available for different age groups (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). The data output produced from the GT3X+ is converted into arbitrary 'counts', for which cut-points have been derived from research that allow classifying PA levels by intensity (Chen and Bassett, 2005). A review of data collection and processing criteria for this device identified several different cut points currently being used for PA and SB research (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, a study exploring the impact of different data collection specifications, such as device placement, and data processing

decisions, such as cut points, found that depending on the criteria being used, the achievement of current PA guidelines ranges from 8-96% (Migueles, Cadenas- Sanchez, *et al.*, 2019). This research underlines the importance of data processing decisions when using accelerometers and highlights the need for more standardisation within this area of research to ensure data is comparable across studies using different cut points (Migueles, Cadenas- Sanchez, *et al.*, 2019; Rowlands *et al.*, 2019).

Studies assessing PA tend to use cut points to describe different activity intensities and overall activity levels (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). There are numerous different cut points, or thresholds, currently used to distinguish between different intensities, from SB to LPA, MPA and VPA (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). When using cut points for analysing accelerometer data, it is crucial for data collection and processing protocols, including wear position and epoch lengths, to match those from of the cut point validation, as well as for the population to be comparable (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). Importantly, this also involves accelerometer brand and model (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). Further, cut point data is not comparable across studies despite a need for standardisation considering the large body of evidence available involving different population groups and intervention approaches (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018).

It has been recommended that when using accelerometers, raw data should be used to allow more comprehensive analyses, including the reporting of novel metrics such as AA and the IG (Migueles *et al.*, 2017; Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). These metrics allow assessing overall activity (via AA) and the distribution of PA across different intensities (via IG), where higher values signify more time spent across different intensities, with lower values describing less time spent in moderate and higher intensity activities (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). Recent updates of the WHO PA guidelines for adolescents focus on encouraging activities across the intensity spectrum and emphasise the additional health benefits associated with achieving higher intensity activities (Bull *et al.*, 2020). This underlines the importance of being able to portray a comprehensive picture of achieved PA

intensities, illustrated by a single comparable metric of different PA intensities. Crucially, these novel metrics allow comparing data across studies, regardless of data collection and processing protocols, including accelerometer brand or model (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018).

Both AA and IG are suggested to provide a comprehensive account of an individual's PA profile over a 24-hour period and will enable comparisons across different population groups (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). In addition, a study with school-aged children has found that IG is linked with health outcomes such as BMI z scores, waist-to-height ratio, cardiorespiratory fitness, and metabolic syndrome score (Fairclough *et al.*, 2019).

SB also consists of various behaviours and accurately measuring the postural element is particularly important (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017). Accelerometers such as the ActiGraph GT3X+ are, due to their positioning and data properties, unable to provide a valid distinction between different SB modes including sitting, standing, and stepping (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012). In comparison, accelerometers that include inclinometers, such as the activPAL, are able to distinguish postures and have shown to be more accurate in assessing SB when compared to ActiGraph GT3X+ devices (Stålesen *et al.*, 2016; Pfister *et al.*, 2017; Pereira *et al.*, 2020). Thus, accelerometers that allow classifying posture have been recommended for accurately measuring SB (Mitchell *et al.*, 2017; Hurter *et al.*, 2019). The activPAL, worn on the thigh, has demonstrated strong concurrent validity and has been shown to be a valid device-based measurement tool for adolescent SB (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012).

2.5 Current interventions for adolescent physical activity and sedentary behaviour

The need for effective interventions targeting adolescent activity levels has been well established (Global Advocacy Council for Physical Activity and International Society for Physical Activity and Health, 2010). However, evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis of PA interventions for youth has only found small effects, equating to an increase of around four minutes more PA per day (Metcalf, Henley and Wilkin, 2012). In line with these findings, other meta-analyses of PA and SB interventions have shown no significant effects

on MVPA (Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019; Jones *et al.*, 2020), with no clear indication of a positive effect on SB also (Jones *et al.*, 2020). Other meta-analyses have found only small effects on PA (Pearson, Braithwaite and Biddle, 2015; Gal *et al.*, 2018). It has been suggested that these findings may indicate that supporting behaviour change for adolescent PA is complex and barriers need to be identified and overcome in order to achieve bigger effect sizes (Pearson, Braithwaite and Biddle, 2015). For SB, including screen and sitting time, a recent review of systematic reviews demonstrated that some interventions targeting children and adolescents' SB show success, however effect sizes remain small (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). Considering adolescent PA levels continue to be low globally, there is a continued need for successful interventions supporting youth in achieving positive health outcomes associated with sufficient PA and reduced SB (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). In order to ensure the evidence base of effective interventions is robust and reliable, there is a continued call for high quality research evaluating PA and SB interventions to be conducted (van Sluijs and Kriemler, 2016). This will allow PA intervention research to advance in a way that enables lessons to be learned from previous (un)successful trials and interventions showing 'true' effective results can be implemented and disseminated (van Sluijs and Kriemler, 2016).

PA and SB interventions for youth have been implemented within a wide variety of settings (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017; Messing *et al.*, 2019). This includes home-based approaches involving family or caregivers, at childcare and educational settings including schools, leisure settings such as camps as well as technology-led approaches such as those using websites or mobile devices (Messing *et al.*, 2019). A review of PA interventions has found that the evidence of youth interventions is inconclusive with regards to which setting might be most effective (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). There appears to be no clear evidence that interventions implemented in the community or at home are more effective than those implemented in schools (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). However, recent research has demonstrated that particularly; school-based interventions focusing on PE participation and reducing SB, multi-component interventions targeting PA throughout the school day, as well as mobile phone-delivered programs may be effective for improving adolescent activity behaviours (Powell *et al.*, 2018).

In addition, meta-analyses have shown that interventions targeting PA and SB together, tend to be more effective than those targeting only one (Pearson, Braithwaite and Biddle, 2015). As such, the following section provides an overview of current school-based, digital, and mobile phone-led interventions targeting adolescent PA and SB.

2.5.1 School-based interventions

For youth, schools are often used to implement health promotion interventions given the opportunities to access and educate children from a wide range of backgrounds and the possibilities schools provide to reduce health inequalities (Langford *et al.*, 2014).

Nonetheless, recent findings suggest that school-based interventions do not result in significant increases in daily MVPA when captured using device-based measures (Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019). It has been suggested that this may be due to issues surrounding intervention fidelity or ineffectiveness of such interventions to enhance PA across the whole day (Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019). In line with these findings, another study exploring the effect of school-based interventions on PA captured by self-report or device-based measures found only small effects on PA levels (Owen *et al.*, 2017). Further, meta-analyses have also shown mixed results for after-school interventions focusing on adolescent MVPA (Mears and Jago, 2016). Given these findings, it is important to explore other settings for delivering health promotion interventions which have the potential for delivering the most benefits. Although schools may still be an important setting for reaching and recruiting adolescents from different cultural and socio-economic backgrounds, there has been a call for research to target interventions implemented in the community without schools as the main delivery setting (Messing *et al.*, 2019).

2.5.2 Technology-based interventions

Technology-based interventions have emerged as a promising tool for behaviour change (Head *et al.*, 2013). In recent years, research has increasingly explored the use of mHealth interventions which draw upon mobile technology, such as phones and activity trackers, to promote healthy lifestyles and support behaviour change (Free *et al.*, 2013; Müller *et al.*,

2018). There has been an exponential increase in research exploring the efficacy of technologies such as mobile devices and smartphones within health promotion interventions (Taj, Klein and van Halteren, 2019). In a recent review and analysis of the literature on digital health behaviour change interventions, almost 1/3 of studies targeted PA, with mobile apps, wearable sensors and SMS used most frequently to promote PA (Taj, Klein and van Halteren, 2019).

Considering technology such as mobile phones are used widely across different populations, technology-led interventions have the potential to include those harder to reach and less likely to be involved in health promotion interventions. In the UK alone, 83% of adolescents aged 12 to 15 currently own a smartphone (Ofcom, 2019). In comparison, smartphone ownership and access among 13-17-year-olds in the United States stands at 95% (Pew Research Center, 2018) with 95% of 12-19-year-olds in Germany having their own smartphone (Statista, 2020a). Also in emerging economies, smartphone ownership rates have been increasing over recent years, such as in Brazil (2015: 61%, 2018: 85%), India (27%, 37%), the Philippines (31%, 74%) and South Africa (46%, 73%) (Pew Research Center, 2019). It is also evident that in emerging as well as advanced economies, younger age groups are more likely to own smartphones compared to middle aged and older adults (Pew Research Center, 2019). Much lower ownership rates are evident for more specialised mHealth devices such as activity trackers and smart watches (e.g. United States 41%, UK 36%, Germany 25%, Brazil 20%) (Statista, 2020b), underlining the importance of using more widely available devices, like mobile phones, to promote health globally. High access rates to mobile and smartphones suggest that these tools may offer an acceptable means for delivering health behaviour change interventions that can fit within everyday life and have population-wide reach.

Despite a sharp rise in research activity around mHealth (Müller *et al.*, 2018), there is a continued lack of evidence regarding the effectiveness of mHealth interventions on behaviour change and health outcomes (Luxton *et al.*, 2011; Källander *et al.*, 2013; Chib, van Velthoven

and Car, 2015). A review of digital interventions for adolescent PA and SB underlines the importance of more research needing to be conducted to explore tools such as smartphones and SMS for promoting behaviour change among adolescents (Rose *et al.*, 2017). Existing evidence does support the use of technology for health promotion intervention as its use has shown promising results for PA and SB (Free *et al.*, 2013; Müller *et al.*, 2018). Another review and meta-analysis of current evidence on mHealth interventions for adults however, demonstrated improvements for SB, with non-significant effects on MVPA (Direito *et al.*, 2017). For adolescents specifically, the evidence base also shows some equivocal results. Although some reviews have found positive effects of technology-based programmes on health behaviours such as PA and SB (Loescher *et al.*, 2018; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), others have not (Böhm *et al.*, 2019). Another review has found some promising effects of digital interventions on PA, however these do not appear to be maintained longer term (Rose *et al.*, 2017). These equivocal findings may, in part, be due to high levels of heterogeneity with regards to study designs and differences in inclusion criteria concerning the mode of delivery (i.e. mobile technology). It must also be mentioned that reviews have found several existing studies to be of low quality, with inconsistent reporting of intervention components and often without a specific focus on PA.

2.5.3 Text-messaging interventions

SMS have been identified as a promising tool for behaviour change interventions considering their potential for population-wide reach due to the widespread use and ownership of mobile and smartphones. In the UK, 94% of adult internet users alone have used SMS in the last year, with 41% using SMS daily (Ofcom, 2020). Data from the United States shows that 90% of adolescents who own a mobile or smartphone use SMS (Pew Research Center, 2015).

Using text-messaging to promote PA and reduce SB allows all mobile phone users to access such interventions with reduced barriers as no log-in, download or additional device is required. Further, SMS can be sent in real-time, depending on the recipients' schedule or availability, and at low cost (Atun and Sittampalam, 2006; Hall, Cole-Lewis and Bernhardt,

2015). In addition, SMS are a low-burden tool for researchers and practitioners to use and allow adding interactive content by setting up free of charge or paid responses. Moreover, intervention content and delivery can be tailored depending on the recipients, with options for personalised interactive elements (Lau *et al.*, 2011). Considering the burden and long-term resources associated with involving multiple components in a single intervention, SMS may present a straightforward, low-resource intense tool for promoting health population wide. It has also been suggested that SMS may be a much more cost-effective tool compared to other health promotion intervention approaches (Smith *et al.*, 2020). SMS interventions can support behaviour change through providing feedback on goals and progress, motivation, and reminders for being active, as well as information and educational content (Webb *et al.*, 2010; Smith *et al.*, 2020).

SMS have long been seen as a successful tool for health promotion (Webb *et al.*, 2010). A recent meta-analysis has demonstrated that PA interventions incorporating SMS continue to show promising effects, with significant improvements in device-measured PA compared to control groups (Smith *et al.*, 2020). A systematic review of SMS interventions for behaviour change in youth, however, has found only limited evidence supporting the use of this tool for promoting adolescent PA (Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012). In contrast, other evidence does support using SMS as a tool to target PA and SB by demonstrating that some interventions that incorporate SMS are effective in increasing PA and reducing SB (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018).

Despite some positive findings, but due to the scarce evidence base, there is a continued need to establish the feasibility and effectiveness of SMS interventions for improving PA and SB (Smith *et al.*, 2020), particularly among adolescents (Loescher *et al.*, 2018; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Systematic review evidence of PA and SB interventions involving SMS has found that in current interventions, additional components such as activity trackers, websites, educational materials, or environmental changes are frequently used (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018; Smith *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, feasibility studies of SMS interventions also highlight the use of such additional components (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Schoenfelder *et al.*, 2017; Larsen *et*

al., 2018), which does not allow for conclusions to be drawn with regards to the effectiveness or feasibility of using SMS in isolation.

There is a call for research to explore the most effective way for SMS to be used as a tool for health promotion, whether in isolation or as part of a multicomponent intervention (Smith *et al.*, 2020). Evidence examining the effects of SMS-only interventions upon PA and SB in youth is scant (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Whilst it has been shown that multi-component interventions can be effective in changing PA in youth, they require more cost and resources compared to single component interventions such as SMS (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017).

Additionally, more traditional face-to-face interventions tend to come with several barriers for adolescents including cost, lack of opportunities to be active close-by and activities not suitable for or desired by the target group (James *et al.*, 2018). Qualitative research with adolescents has shown that for interventions to be acceptable and effective, they should include PA opportunities that meet their needs and wishes, are suitable to their demographic and provide choice (James *et al.*, 2018). Considering ease of use and adaptability of SMS-based interventions, they offer the opportunity to provide a variety of tailored and population-specific advice and information on health behaviour change, without requiring face-to-face contact. Further, there is some evidence that cost-effective, wide-reaching technology-led interventions such as those using SMS can show significant effects on PA (Webb *et al.*, 2010; Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018).

2.6 Behaviour change theory

Frameworks for developing and evaluating behaviour change interventions, such as the Medical Research Council (MRC) guidelines (Craig *et al.*, 2008), emphasise the importance of using theory within interventions. It is specifically advised to identify suitable theoretical frameworks to guide the intervention and ensure they are applied in a consistent and systematic way (Craig *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, evidence from systematic reviews has often suggested that using theory within PA interventions, including those for adolescents and those using digital tools, such as the internet, may increase their effectiveness (Webb *et al.*,

2010; Pearson, Braithwaite and Biddle, 2015). A review of school-based interventions has demonstrated that whilst such interventions tend to show small effects, those based on theory may be more successful compared to those lacking theoretical foundation (Owen *et al.*, 2017). However, there is contrasting evidence that has found no evidence that PA interventions using theory are more effective than those that do not (Greaves *et al.*, 2011; Mears and Jago, 2016; Rhodes *et al.*, 2017; McEwan *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, evidence from a meta-analysis of PA interventions has found equivocal results with regards to the links between using theory and intervention effectiveness (Prestwich *et al.*, 2014).

Whilst it has been found that using theory does not automatically enhance intervention effectiveness, it has been suggested that theoretical frameworks are important for PA behaviour change in terms of guiding other active intervention components, such as BCTs (McEwan *et al.*, 2019). These BCTs have been universally defined within the hierarchical BCT taxonomy and aid the comparability of intervention components across studies (Michie *et al.*, 2013).

For example, using intervention techniques, or BCTs, associated with specific theoretical frameworks, such as those linked to self-regulation (goal setting, self-monitoring, and feedback) has been shown to increase intervention effectiveness (Greaves *et al.*, 2011). A recent analysis of behaviour change interventions identified five groups, or clusters, of BCTs often used concurrently as well as theories linked to these clusters (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). For example, the BCTs information about other's approval, information about social and environmental consequences and information about health consequences are frequently used as a group and this cluster has been linked to the TPB (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, the BCT cluster of behavioural practice, demonstration of behaviour and instruction on how to perform the behaviour has been linked to Self-efficacy Theory and SCT (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). This link between BCT clusters and underlying theory provides crucial guidance for identifying theory within interventions and allows incorporating appropriate BCTs based on theory and vice versa (McEwan *et al.*, 2019; Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). A meta-

analysis of current PA interventions has demonstrated that interventions guided by theory used more groups of BCTs belonging to the same overarching concept or theory than those not linked to theory (McEwan *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, in contrast to those not guided by theory, interventions incorporating theoretical frameworks have also been found to significantly increase PA through any group of BCTs (McEwan *et al.*, 2019). It has therefore been recommended that when including certain groups of BCTs within an intervention, using an appropriate theoretical framework is crucial for eliciting significant changes in PA (McEwan *et al.*, 2019). Despite the contrasting findings with regards to the effectiveness of using theory, theoretical frameworks have long been suggested to enhance behaviour change by guiding the development of interventions towards components that are likely to positively change behaviours (Michie and Prestwich, 2010). However, there are currently many issues with regards to the insufficient reporting of theory and BCTs within interventions (Michie and Prestwich, 2010). Crucially, this hinders the ability to understand behaviour change mechanisms and impedes inferences with regards to intervention effectiveness and its link to theory (Michie and Prestwich, 2010; Michie *et al.*, 2011). This potentially also contributes to equivocal results of reviews and meta-analyses exploring the success of interventions based on theory compared to those that are not. It has been suggested that by linking theory with frequently used BCTs, this may allow exploring theoretical frameworks and their link to intervention effectiveness even if theory isn't explicitly mentioned (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020).

The lack of a clear link between reported theory and effectiveness has been suggested to be due to how theory is implemented or reported (Naylor *et al.*, 2015; Owen *et al.*, 2017).

Whether a single theory or multiple frameworks are used within interventions, it is essential to report how theory was applied and ensure interventions are based on theory rather than merely superficially guided (Biddle, Mutrie and Gorely, 2015). In addition, it has been found that existing interventions that are reported to use theory are often not applying these frameworks comprehensively or fail to report which theoretical constructs were targeted by BCTs within the intervention (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015). The choice of BCTs

embedded within intervention delivery should be guided by the choice of theory to allow for the link between theory, BCTs and intervention effectiveness to be analysed and enhance the success of behaviour change interventions (Biddle, Mutrie and Gorely, 2015; Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). Applying suitable BCTs within interventions has been suggested to enhance effectiveness as they are an active strategy that targets and supports behaviour change with regards to a specific theoretical construct (Michie *et al.*, 2013). However, it has been found that in some interventions, BCTs not appropriate for the chosen theory are used or the authors fail to target each theoretical construct with suitable BCTs (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015).

In addition to issues surrounding reporting and the inappropriate use of BCTs, it has also been found that using multiple theories within an intervention may reduce effectiveness (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015). Indeed, it has been suggested that ineffectiveness occurs when a combination of theories is used without evidence-based precedent and sufficient theoretical foundation for integrating multiple suitable frameworks (Gourlan *et al.*, 2016). However, choosing theories appropriate for the target behaviour and intervention delivery tool, e.g. SMS, and evaluating their integration thoroughly is expected to optimise the intervention's acceptability and effectiveness. Indeed, if theories are integrated into interventions more effectively, they guide the use of suitable BCTs and facilitate the in-depth evaluation of the intervention process, providing insight into how and why interventions facilitate (or fail to facilitate) behaviour change.

2.6.1 Integration in current interventions

Several systematic review studies have found that theories such as the TTM, the TPB and SCT are used most frequently to inform behaviour change interventions and public health research (Painter *et al.*, 2008; Davis *et al.*, 2015; Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020).

The TTM is a comprehensive theory of behaviour change encompassing stages of change, decisional balance, self-efficacy, and processes of change (Prochaska and DiClemente, 1983; Prochaska, Redding and Evers, 2015). The five stages of change signify that when

changing behaviours, people move through the stages of precontemplation (with no intention to change within the next six months), contemplation (intention to change within six months), preparation (intention to change within 30 days), action (has changed within the last six months), and maintenance (has changed for more than six months) (Prochaska, Redding and Evers, 2015). Indeed, the goal is for most interventions to support people in moving from precontemplation to behaviour change maintenance using processes of change. These processes describe strategies that can be used to advance within the stages of change, such as helping relationships in the form of social support. It has been demonstrated that different processes or change are more suitable for supporting people to move through different stages (Prochaska and DiClemente, 1983). This includes using strategies such as consciousness raising in the earlier stages and focusing on reinforcement and stimulus control during the action stages (Prochaska and DiClemente, 1983). As people move through stages of change, decisional balance is thought to play a key part by signifying the level to which the advantages of changing behaviours outweigh the perceived cost involved with changing. It has been suggested that within the early stages of changing exercise behaviours, the cost tends to outweigh the benefits, with a shift to the contrary during the latter stages of change (Prochaska and Velicer, 1997), in particular also in regards to exercise behaviour among adolescents (Nigg and Courneya, 1998). The TTM also includes self-efficacy from Bandura's self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1977) in the form of the interplay between confidence to change and temptation to fall back into unhealthy behaviours during difficult situations (Prochaska and Velicer, 1997). As with decisional balance, self-efficacy, as the confidence in oneself to change, increases as people progress through stages of change, which has also been shown to be the case specifically for adolescent exercise and PA behaviours (Nigg and Courneya, 1998; Bucksch, Finne and Kolip, 2008; Shaver *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, the predictive capability of the TTM components for PA (Marshall and Biddle, 2001) and specifically among adolescents (Prapavessis, Maddison and Brading, 2004) has been demonstrated. Indeed, the performance of PA as well as self-efficacy have been found to increase from the precontemplation to maintenance stage (Marshall and Biddle, 2001).

Decisional balance has empirically been shown to function as predicted by the TTM, with behavioural benefits increasing across stages (Marshall and Biddle, 2001). It has also been demonstrated that specific processes of change are being used depending on stage of change (Marshall and Biddle, 2001). An important limitation of current TTM research has been insufficient reporting and incomplete implementation within current PA interventions, with some components of this model often not included (Romain *et al.*, 2018a). A recent meta-analysis of TTM-based PA interventions found that 55% incorporated at least three of the five TTM components, with those using more components being more effective compared to those using fewer (Romain *et al.*, 2018b). Decisional balance was used in 52% of TTM interventions and temptation in merely 9%, with no differences between inclusion and exclusion in terms of PA behaviour change (Romain *et al.*, 2018b). On the other hand, self-efficacy (included in 48%) and processes of change (64%) appeared to be important elements for increasing the likelihood of successful PA behaviour change (Romain *et al.*, 2018b). Crucially, this evidence demonstrates the importance of using a comprehensive approach to implementing the TTM within future interventions.

The TPB plays a key role in providing an understanding of determinants of intentions to change behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). The TPB suggests that stronger intentions increase the likelihood of successful behaviour change, with three determinants influencing the level of intention (Ajzen, 1991). These determinants include perceived behavioural control (having volitional control over the performance of a behaviour), subjective norm (perceived social support or pressure to perform the behaviour) and attitude (favourable or unfavourable view towards the behaviour) (Ajzen, 1991). More favourable subjective norms and attitudes, and higher perceived behavioural control are predicted to increase intentions and subsequently positively influence behaviour change (Ajzen, 1991). A meta-analysis exploring the effectiveness of the TPB has demonstrated that its components are effective in predicting intention and behaviour change (Armitage and Conner, 2001). Studies exploring the predictability of these components specifically for adolescents have found that perceived behavioural control, subjective norm, attitude, and intention have moderate to large

associations with PA (Van Der Horst *et al.*, 2007; Murnaghan *et al.*, 2010; McEachan *et al.*, 2011).

Whilst correlations between intention and subsequent performance of health behaviours have been found, research has also shown that at times, even strong intentions do not lead to changes in behaviour (Sheeran and Webb, 2016). This so-called 'intention-behaviour gap' has been illustrated by empirical evidence showing that changes in intentions are not consistently followed by meaningful changes in behaviour (Rhodes and Dickau, 2012). Thus, there is a need for effective intervention components to overcome this discrepancy (Fernández *et al.*, 2015; Isa *et al.*, 2018). Self-efficacy has been demonstrated to be a potentially successful strategy for bridging the gap, with research showing lower levels of self-efficacy among youth who did not follow up their intentions with changes in PA (Isa *et al.*, 2018). In contrast, youth with higher self-efficacy also demonstrated a higher level of intention and subsequent behaviour (Isa *et al.*, 2018). Other studies have explored the influence of action and coping planning on the intention-behaviour process (Fernández *et al.*, 2015; Rhodes and Yao, 2015). Within a sample of young adults it has been shown that action control, linked to self-monitoring, may be an important factor for bridging the intention-behaviour gap and maintaining PA longer term (Fernández *et al.*, 2015). Promising intervention techniques for increasing the likelihood of intentions leading to successful behaviour change include focusing on self-efficacy, self-monitoring, action control and coping planning (Fernández *et al.*, 2015; Rhodes and Yao, 2015).

SCT encompasses a set of theories that generally describe that behaviours occur within an interplay between internal and external processes of a person and their environment (Bandura, 1986). This interaction includes a person's social surroundings and the action of others, the environment, and individual experiences. Within the interaction between the individual and their environment, the belief in one's own abilities (i.e. self-efficacy) and learning from others, including via social support and observation, play a key role in influencing health behaviour change (Bandura, 1977). Research has shown that self-efficacy

and social support are also associated specifically with adolescent PA (Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014). In addition to SCT, self-efficacy theory focuses on this determinant as well as describing that favourable judgements of physiological and affective states, past achievements, persuasion, and vicarious experiences can increase perceived competence to change behaviours (Bandura, 1977). As increased self-efficacy is associated with higher PA (Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014; Rollo, Gaston and Prapavessis, 2016), it represents a key factor for supporting successful behaviour change, across different theoretical frameworks.

For school-based interventions for youth specifically, recent findings show that SCT and TTM remain popular, with some studies incorporating multiple theoretical frameworks (Owen *et al.*, 2017). It is crucial however to select theoretical frameworks based on their suitability for the intervention at hand rather than popularity within the field (Davis *et al.*, 2015). It also has to be mentioned that the choice of theory may also be influenced by the researchers' knowledge, previous experience and awareness of certain theories, which may be in line with those most frequently used (Davis *et al.*, 2015). As a result, there has been a call for more research to be conducted to explore the use and effectiveness of lesser known and used theories, such as the COM-B Model or Control Theory, to ensure appropriate constructs are applied within interventions (Davis *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, novel intervention approaches, such as mHealth tools, may require new, more suitable theoretical frameworks (Riley *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, it has been recommended that researchers should only be encouraged to incorporate theory within intervention development, implementation, and evaluation in contexts where specific evidence exists that justifies its use (Dalgetty, Miller and Dombrowski, 2019) without blindly using theory which is most frequently used across different behaviours and delivery modes.

There is comprehensive evidence that whilst theoretical frameworks tend to target different aspects of behaviour and behaviour change, commonly used theories such as the TTM, SCT, and TPB do indeed show commonalities in terms of their focus (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). For example, it has been demonstrated that certain components within SCT and the

TPB are linked to stages of change within the TTM, with core concepts within the TPB, including perceived behavioural control, being associated with behaviour change across the stages of change within the TTM (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). This indicates that using a combination of these theories, and incorporating them in a comprehensive, well-described manner, is appropriate for PA interventions considering the comprehensive evidence base supporting their use. A more in-depth analysis of theories and BCTs applied within the research presented in this thesis can be found in Chapter 5 and 6.

2.6.2 Use within mobile health interventions

A recent systematic review of mHealth interventions found that SCT is the most frequently used theory within technologies such as mobile apps, activity trackers or SMS (Böhm *et al.*, 2019). Its popularity may, in part, be due to high predictive capabilities for PA and high correlations between its individual components, such as self-efficacy, and PA (Rhodes, McEwan and Rebar, 2019). In addition, most mHealth studies incorporate multiple theoretical frameworks and some also use BCTs such as feedback, self-monitoring, and goal setting (Böhm *et al.*, 2019). There were however, no consistent positive effects of mHealth interventions on MVPA, which is suggested to be due to short intervention durations, potential issues with adherence, bias within subjective assessments of PA and a lack of compliance to the device-based measurement of PA (Böhm *et al.*, 2019).

Recent evidence also demonstrates that as well as in more traditional intervention delivery modes, such as school-based programmes, mHealth interventions frequently fail to provide a comprehensive description of how theory was implemented (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). With regards to SMS interventions, this also includes demonstrating how theory was applied within messages as well as which element of the intervention relates to which theoretical variable (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). Despite the complexity of applying suitable behaviour change theories within mHealth interventions, there has been a call for future research to focus on incorporating theory and applying techniques that have shown to be effective in supporting behaviour change (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). For example, it has

been recommended that techniques such as goal setting, personalisation, social support, feedback, and reminders may be successful tools specifically within mHealth interventions (Salwen-Deremer *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, another recent review of mHealth interventions showed that the most frequently used BCTs in effective interventions included prompts, personalisation, goal setting and action planning, with ineffective interventions frequently using self-monitoring, social support, and feedback (Dugas, Gao and Agarwal, 2020). This underlines the importance of judging the effectiveness of theoretical frameworks and intervention techniques in particular based on the intervention delivery mode and target behaviour (Dugas, Gao and Agarwal, 2020). Crucially, this should occur without generalising across different novel (e.g. mobile apps, SMS, activity trackers) and more traditional approaches (e.g. educational material, practical sessions, environmental changes) (Dugas, Gao and Agarwal, 2020). Furthermore, a review of electronic weight management interventions has demonstrated that interventions may be more successful if one or multiple theories and related techniques are used to guide the intervention itself as well as the chosen outcome measures (Willmott *et al.*, 2019). This underlines the importance of using theoretical frameworks not just to inform the development of interventions, but also ensure the targeted constructs are also subsequently assessed.

2.7 Intervention design and evaluation

Frameworks are often used to guide the evaluation of interventions and the theory applied, by exploring processes and outcomes related to implementation and effectiveness (Fynn, Hardeman, Milton, Murphy, *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, many different frameworks are currently being applied for developing and evaluating interventions, with a recent scoping review identifying 68 frameworks for PA interventions alone (Fynn, Hardeman, Milton and Jones, 2020).

Within this thesis, the MRC framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions was used due to the complex nature of the target behaviours, designed intervention and outcomes that are being addressed (Craig *et al.*, 2008). For developing and evaluating novel

approaches, such as mobile device-based interventions, the MRC guidance is particularly relevant as it recommends for appropriate theory to be identified and ensures more effective and 'implementation ready' interventions can be developed (Craig *et al.*, 2008; Bowen *et al.*, 2009). It describes that intervention development should be rooted in evidence-informed and theory-based foundations before moving on to pilot and feasibility evaluations (Craig *et al.*, 2008). Due to a lack of comparable research and gaps in the evidence base for using SMS in isolation, the MRC guidelines were crucial for informing the process of developing, implementing, and evaluating the present intervention. This included a comprehensive description of intervention context and theory, for which the MRC framework provided detailed guidance (Craig *et al.*, 2008).

Following comprehensive development of theory- and evidence-based foundations, pilot and feasibility studies were conducted in line with the MRC guidance (Craig *et al.*, 2008). This was vital for exploring key elements of intervention implementation and outcome evaluation, including recruitment and retention, data collection and analysis processes, intervention delivery and initial effectiveness, prior to full scale implementation and evaluation (El-Kotob and Giangregorio, 2018).

In addition to providing comprehensive quantitative pilot and feasibility testing, qualitative data is also presented throughout this thesis, which has been recommended by the MRC guidelines as part of intervention evaluations (Craig *et al.*, 2008; O'Cathain *et al.*, 2015). Collecting qualitative and quantitative data concurrently provides in-depth insights into participant experiences and preferences of interventions in addition to quantitative device- and questionnaire-based data (Shorten and Smith, 2017). Particularly for assessing acceptability, qualitative data as well as quantitative behavioural outcomes will enable researchers to assess how likely participants are to engage with the intervention and benefit from its effects before designing and evaluating a full-scale trial with increased resources (Sekhon, Cartwright and Francis, 2017). The MRC framework provides guidance on the importance of understanding the mechanisms of an intervention, which allows for the most

effective components to be identified (Craig *et al.*, 2008). This allows focusing on successful strategies and efficiently work towards intervention implementation and behaviour change maintenance. Conducting pilot and feasibility studies that use mixed methods also allow assessing any unintended intervention effects, crucial for the subsequent stages of large-scale implementation and evaluation (Craig *et al.*, 2008).

There has been growing critique over recent years with regards to the lack of transparency and sufficient, comprehensive reporting of intervention components. This also includes how theory is being used to inform intervention development and design (Corder, Klingberg and van Sluijs, 2020). It has frequently been suggested that a lack of consistent intervention effectiveness of current approaches for promoting PA could be due to poorly designed and executed research, with insufficient reporting of important study elements such as data collection procedures and intervention implementation (Corder, Klingberg and van Sluijs, 2020). Frameworks such as the MRC guidelines ensure that important study elements are reported and, more importantly, interventions are developed in a transparent, structured way. In addition, to ensure comprehensive reporting, widely used guidelines, including the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA; Study 1) (Moher *et al.*, 2009), the Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research (COREQ) checklist (Study 2) (Tong, Sainsbury and Craig, 2007) and the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) checklist with extension for pilot and feasibility trials (Study 3 & 4) (Eldridge *et al.*, 2016) will be used for reporting research presented throughout this thesis.

2.8 Summary

Global PA levels are low amongst adolescents which represents a crucial time for targeting health behaviours such as PA and SB due to their demonstrated tracking into adulthood. Considering the comprehensive health benefits of sufficient PA and reduced SB, there are several different settings and intervention approaches currently used for targeting adolescent activity behaviours. However, despite a large body of evidence, current interventions do not show consistent positive effects. As a result, there have been calls for the development of

novel, more effective intervention approaches, such as those using mobile technology.

Considering ease of use, low financial burden, interactivity, and options for tailored content and delivery, SMS have transpired as a potentially successful tool for delivering PA and SB interventions. High use of mobile phones and SMS among adolescents make SMS interventions a promising approach, however there is a lack of research focusing on SMS alone without the addition of websites, apps, or other components.

There is also an acute need for studies to involve device-based measures of PA and SB and to employ qualitative as well as quantitative measures for evaluation. The MRC guidelines for developing and evaluating complex interventions, emphasizes the importance of developing a thorough understanding of effective intervention components, including theory. Theoretical frameworks such as SCT, TTM and TPB as well as clusters of BCTs including goal setting and feedback have demonstrated to be appropriate for use within SMS targeting PA and SB. Moreover, there is a lack of research using appropriate qualitative and quantitative data for assessing outcomes related to the intervention development and delivery process as well as participant experiences, preferences, and behaviour change. Such mixed methods evaluations are vital for understanding which intervention components are most effective and how adherence and behaviour change maintenance can be improved. Thus, the research presented in the following chapters aims to address the lack of research of low-burden, theory-led SMS interventions targeting PA and SB in adolescents by providing comprehensive qualitative and quantitative data to develop and evaluate such interventions.

Chapter 3

General methods

In this chapter, the methodology applied within the intervention studies presented in this thesis will be outlined. Information with regards to ethics approval, participant recruitment, data collection and analysis is provided, with additional, more specific information and variations to these methods presented in the respective subsequent study chapters.

3.1 Ethical approval

All studies received ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee prior to any data collection. In addition, for Study 4, ethical approval was also obtained from the respective local authority (South Lanarkshire Council).

3.2 Participant recruitment

For Study 2 and 3, an existing contact to a local secondary school was used. The PE department head identified two classes potentially suitable for participation as they were unaffected by exam periods and other school-related activities at the time of data collection and intervention implementation. The PE department head facilitated the distribution of study information. At the start of a regular PE lesson the research team gave pupils within the respective year four (N=30) and year five (N=28) class an overview of the research project, their potential involvement and all intervention and data collection procedures. Pupils had the opportunity to ask any questions and raise concerns during and after this information session. To be eligible, pupils had to be between 10 and 19 years old, be able to take part in general PA and be proficient in the English language. Subsequently, six pupils declined to participate and a convenience sample of 52 participants from the two classes was recruited. The principal investigator used coin tossing to cluster randomise the two classes to the intervention or waitlist control group, a recognised method for reducing risk of random sequence generation bias (Higgins *et al.*, 2019). This resulted in the year four cohort (N=27)

to be allocated to the waitlist control group, with the year five class (N=25) representing the intervention group.

For Study 4, new links to a local secondary school were established through the process of two rounds of recruitment. The first round involved a collaborating member of staff within the NHS Lanarkshire Child Healthy Weight Unit to contact 18 local secondary schools via email to the school office or head teacher to enquire about their interest for taking part in this study. As no responses were received within the predetermined timeframe, a second round of recruitment was initiated. This involved emailing the PE department head and Active Schools coordinators of 28 secondary schools from two local authorities, South and North Lanarkshire. Fourteen schools responded (six teachers, eight Active Schools coordinators), with nine meetings subsequently held. All nine schools were interested in taking part in the study, however four ceased contact and were excluded. Due to the ever-changing schedule for this study because of the re-distribution of the collaborator's staff and resources (see chapter 9), two schools were recruited for participation, with one approved by the respective local council.

3.3 Consent

For Study 2 and 3, the PE department head distributed information sheets and consent forms (Appendices 1-4) among the two recruited classes (N=58). This included detailed information regarding study procedures, such as data collection, intervention duration and content, as well as a separate information sheet outlining basic information containing links to additional detail surrounding the SMS delivery system, Florence, used for this study. This information focused on current data protection procedures and which details, such as phone numbers, will be collected and stored. Participants who agreed to take part were given an additional information sheet outlining the use of Florence and providing information on how to reply when prompted (Appendix 5). Considering the pupils' age, two informed consent forms were used, one for parents or caregivers and another for participants to complete themselves. Participants and their parents or caregivers were given sufficient time to consider the

provided study information and were encouraged to contact the research team with any questions or concerns. They were informed that participation was voluntary, there were no consequences for opting out of the study at any stage, their data would be held securely and anonymous and would be retained for possible publication or presentation of this work and that focus groups would be audio recorded.

For Study 4, information sheets and informed consent forms (Appendices 6-9) were distributed to two classes (N=60) identified as suitable by the PE department head as well as additional pupils from another class (N=10) interested in taking part. Information was provided with regards to data collection, intervention, and analysis procedures as well as data protection and storage, with ample time being given for asking questions and raising any concerns. Once again, both parents or caregivers and pupils themselves were asked to provide consent should they wish to participate. In addition, participants who agreed to take part were given an information sheet outlining the use of Esendex, the SMS delivery system for this study. This included a step-by-step guide on how to reply to SMS when prompted (Appendix 10).

3.4 Mixed methods approach

Throughout the studies conducted as part of this thesis, a parallel mixed methods approach was taken. Particularly when conducting feasibility research of novel interventions, using a combination of qualitative and quantitative data has been recommended (O’Cathain *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, there has been a specific call for qualitative data to be used to develop and implement effective SMS interventions as it allows obtaining participant views and preferences for SMS delivery (Lau *et al.*, 2019). In this thesis, qualitative and quantitative data were collected concurrently, which allowed obtaining a more in-depth insight into participant experiences, preferences, and perceived behaviour change (Shorten and Smith, 2017). When assessing acceptability, incorporating qualitative data in addition to device- and questionnaire-derived data enabled assessing how likely participants are to engage with the intervention and benefit from its effects (Sekhon, Cartwright and Francis, 2017).

Overall, a pragmatic approach was used whereby the specific research questions guided the choice of methods used within the respective study (Feilzer, 2010). This also allowed for a combination of inductive and deductive analyses as well as focusing on data collection tools most appropriate for the specific context of the respective study (Feilzer, 2010). Whilst the quantitative data collected throughout this thesis followed rigorous protocols and focused on using validated (e.g. for assessing psychological outcomes) and device-based (e.g. for assessing PA and SB) measures, qualitative data in the form of focus group discussions was collected to better understand participant experiences and preferences as well as understand how SMS interventions can be developed, implemented, and evaluated more effectively. Despite the research presented in this thesis being led by theory in terms of intervention development and the choice of psychological outcome measures, the pragmatic approach allowed for the methodology to also be guided by practical considerations and aims of the respective study (Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2009). Thus, by using qualitative methods in addition to device-based validated measures, their respective benefits generated a greatly enhanced richness and understanding of data (Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2009, 2016). Due to the complexity of research questions addressed throughout this thesis as well as the novel nature of the designed intervention, the pragmatic mixed methods approach was expected to yield the most comprehensive and in-depth but also most robust and theory-led findings.

3.5 Philosophical grounding of the research

Research paradigms are described as a way to guide and frame the approach and methods utilised when conducting research studies (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Particularly for mixed methods research, there has been debate about the appropriateness and relevance of paradigms such as critical realism, pragmatism, and post-positivism (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Generally, realism is an ontological position that acknowledges that there are no objective or absolute findings, with alternative accounts needing to be considered. Realism has often been stated to lend itself to mixed methods research (Maxwell and Mittapalli, 2010). In contrast, post-positivism is a paradigm often referred to within quantitative research (Maxwell

and Mittapalli, 2010). This paradigm encompasses the belief that 'true' evidence or experiences are accessible when appropriate research methodologies are implemented (Maxwell and Mittapalli, 2010). On the other hand, fallibilism postulates that no evidence or data is able to account something as 'true' without any level of doubt (Maxwell and Mittapalli, 2010). Fallibilism as an epistemology is often linked to qualitative research methodologies that place emphasis on context, beliefs and prior experiences influencing upon research enquiries. It is important to view the evidence presented in this thesis as a result of rigorous enquiry employing appropriate methods for the respective aims and context. However, the findings are in no way considered as absolute statements as to the research aims and the researcher appreciates that alternative accounts may exist.

For guiding the research conducted as part of this thesis, a pragmatic paradigmatic framework was adopted (Morgan, 2007; Shannon-Baker, 2016). Pragmatism involves the understanding that specific research methods are not inherently linked to any one specific philosophical paradigm (Maxwell and Mittapalli, 2010). It also has often been used as a methodological approach that focuses on practicalities, such as using methods that are deemed feasible (Morgan, 2014). Moreover, a pragmatic research paradigm involves harnessing the strengths of combining qualitative and quantitative methods (Morgan, 2014). Thus, whilst in other worldviews, different ontological and epistemological views are linked to specific qualitative and quantitative methods, pragmatists combine these acknowledging that their simultaneous use achieves findings that address the research aims (Morgan, 2007). There has been a call to recognise that, even within a pragmatic paradigm, there are indeed philosophical beliefs and prior experiences that will influence the researchers' decisions and actions with regards to research methodologies (Morgan, 2014).

Using a pragmatic approach in the present context prevented frequent limitations of using dialectical approaches, for example those encompassing realist and positivist assumptions, to occur. A dialectical approach using two paradigms for the respective qualitative and quantitative measures often results in over-dominance of one over the other or

incompatibility of findings between the individual methods. As the main aim of this research was to use mixed methods for complementarity and expansion of findings (Schoonenboom and Johnson, 2017), it was deemed important to work along the strengths of using a pragmatic approach, which would allow for an overarching paradigm to guide the research.

Throughout the thesis process, the researcher acknowledged that their own experiences and expertise would inherently affect the implementation and execution of the individual studies, with specific emphasis on this as part of the qualitative data analysis. Moreover, pragmatism involves acknowledging that data is contextual, however a degree of possible transferability remains (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Thus, it was important for the data presented in this thesis to include contextual information, which would allow the reader to consider the appropriateness of the study design, implementation and results to be applicable to other contexts, for example those involving clinical populations or other digital health tools.

Further, pragmatism encapsulates that the research aims inform methodology, which lends itself particularly appropriately for mixed methods research (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Whilst the qualitative elements in particular involve an appreciation of how the researcher's expertise, beliefs and previous experiences affected the research, there was no specific focus on realist or idealist grounding of the work. Moreover, no purely subjective or objective epistemology guided the work, but rather, research was conducted to answer specific research questions (Morgan, 2007). Further, the quantitative elements conducted as part of this mixed methods research placed emphasis on using valid and reliable measures, however it was also recognised that subconscious beliefs and presumptions may have affected data collection and analysis. Pragmatism recognises that the respective qualitative and quantitative methods applied within mixed methods research are appropriate in combination and are able to compensate for each other's strengths and limitations (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Thus, the present research was able to focus on using a parallel mixed methods design, with individual qualitative and quantitative methods complementing

each other to comprehensively, and most appropriately achieve the pre-determined study aims.

Generally, it is acknowledged that the practitioner and research experience of the research team impacted and led the study execution, with a focus on implementation-ready and evidence-based work. Throughout, an important focus was placed on a level of reflexivity and consciousness of inherent influences due to the researchers' own expertise and previous experiences.

3.6 Feasibility assessment

The intervention studies conducted as part of this thesis contained a particular focus on assessing the feasibility of SMS interventions implemented within secondary schools. It has been recommended that within pilot studies, a priori feasibility thresholds and criteria for progression to full trial should be set (Thabane *et al.*, 2010; Mbuagbaw *et al.*, 2019).

However, considering the novelty of the intervention and lack of previous research providing feasibility data to guide the development, implementation and analysis of the present interventions, no a priori thresholds were set. The assessment of feasibility and acceptability of the conducted interventions therefore focused on the degree of acceptance during recruitment, engagement of participants throughout the intervention duration, and perceived suitability and effectiveness of the SMS intervention as described in the qualitative data presented throughout this thesis (Bowen *et al.*, 2009). In addition, emphasis was also placed on any technical issues during the process of sending and receiving SMS as well as throughout data collection, particularly when using device-based measures (Bowen *et al.*, 2009). We acknowledge the limitations of this approach as a priori criteria can be crucial in ensuring only trials achieving pre-determined thresholds are scaled up into full RCTs (Mbuagbaw *et al.*, 2019).

3.7 Anthropometric and demographic data

As part of Study 2, 3, and 4, several demographic and anthropometric measures were taken. At baseline (Study 2, 3 & 4) and post intervention (Study 4), height and weight were measured barefoot and to the nearest 0.1cm/kg using a portable stadiometer (Seca Stadiometre, Seca Ltd, Birmingham, UK) and electronic scales (Seca Digital Scales, Seca Ltd., Birmingham, UK). From these, BMI was calculated using the formula kg/m^2 and BMI-for-age weight categories were determined using the WHO growth reference for youth aged five to 19 years, with boys and girls assessed using the respective reference values (Butte, Garza and de Onis, 2007).

At baseline, participants also provided their home postcode to assess socio-economic status via the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) (The Scottish Government, 2015). The SIMD uses relative decile scores between one (most deprived areas) and 10 (least deprived areas). Participants whose postcode classes them on a decile score of two or below were determined to be among the most deprived 20%. Additionally, participants were asked to provide their age, gender, and year group.

3.8 Physical activity measurement

To explore changes in PA and SB as a result of the respective intervention, PA and SB data was collected in Study 2, 3, and 4. In all studies, two accelerometer devices were used simultaneously.

3.8.1 Data collection

For measuring PA, ActiGraph GT3X+ (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) devices were worn on the non-dominant wrist. Device placement was demonstrated, and participants verbally confirmed which was their non-dominant wrist, that is, the hand they do not normally write with. ActiGraph GT3X+ devices are widely used to measure PA levels in both adults and children (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). Devices were initialised to record at 90Hz starting shortly after being distributed. In addition, participants were provided with a document outlining the

wear time instructions for ActiGraph devices, which included wearing the device every day and night for seven days and only taking it off for showering, bathing, and swimming (Appendix 11).

3.8.2 Data processing and analysis

Raw acceleration data was downloaded using ActiLife software (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) and saved as raw csv files for processing in R (<http://cran.r-project.org>) using the GGIR package version 1.8-1 (Migueles, Rowlands, *et al.*, 2019). This included autocalibration, detection of sustained abnormally high values, detection of non-wear and calculation of the average magnitude of dynamic acceleration corrected for gravity (Euclidean Norm minus 1g, ENMO) averaged over 5-second epochs and expressed in milligravitational units (mg) (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018; Migueles, Rowlands, *et al.*, 2019). For inclusion in data analysis, participants had to meet the following wear-time criteria: minimum of three days of valid wear (study 4) or a minimum of three weekdays and one weekend day of valid wear (studies 2 and 3), with ≥ 16 hours of wear time per day, post calibration error $< 0.01g$ and wear data for each 15-minute period of the 24 hour cycle (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). PA was assessed using AA (ENMO, mg), IG and time spent in MVPA. AA provides an indication of PA volume whereas the IG represents the PA intensity profile over the recorded time period (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). MVPA was defined as time accumulated above 201mg using the recommended threshold for children and adolescents (Hildebrand *et al.*, 2014). Data was subsequently input into SPSS statistical software for Windows version 25 (IBM, Armonk, NY) for further analysis.

3.9 Sedentary behaviour measurement

3.9.1 Data collection

For measuring SB, activPAL4 (PAL Technologies, Glasgow, UK) devices, valid for use in adolescents (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012), were attached to the participants' right thigh using waterproofing sleeves and Tegaderm medical adhesive (3M, Bracknell, UK) as

per the manufacturer's recommendations. Participants who preferred to attach the device themselves were able to do so in the PE changing rooms without supervision. Once attached, the research team performed a visual check to ensure this was done correctly. activPALs were initialised and recorded at 20 Hz, starting shortly after being distributed. Participants were instructed to wear the accelerometers for 24 hours per day over the course of seven days. They also received an envelope containing an information sheet outlining wear instruction, including when and how to change the adhesive tape (Appendix 11).

3.9.2 Data processing and analysis

For analysis of SB outcomes, activPAL4 data was downloaded using PALconnect software (PAL Technologies, Version 8.10. Glasgow, UK). Using PALbatch (PAL Technologies, Version 8.11. Glasgow, UK), PAL datx files were exported as csv events files, which were subsequently imported into Processing PAL (Version 1.2, Leicester, UK). For processing of files in Processing PAL, the validated algorithm for sleep and non-wear was used: longest bout per 24-hour period that lasts > two hours or any very long bouts lasting > five hours. Surrounding bouts were all bouts where any portion was within a 15-minute window before or after a sleep/non-wear bout (Winkler *et al.*, 2016). All surrounding bouts were classed as sleep/non-wear if the sleep window contained a sitting, lying, or standing bout of > two hours, or a > 30-minute sitting, lying or standing bout with < 20 steps; a sleep/non-wear bout; or only posture changes without intervening steps (Winkler *et al.*, 2016). Days were considered invalid if > 95% of waking wear consisted of the same activity, or if < 500 steps or < 10 hours of waking wear was found (Winkler *et al.*, 2016). Participant files were included in subsequent analysis if devices were worn on at least three days (Study 4) (Troost *et al.*, 2000) or at least three weekdays and one weekend day (Study 2 & 3) (Troost *et al.*, 2000; Shi *et al.*, 2019). Finally, using Processing PAL, a random selection of heatmaps of available data were visually inspected to check for irregularities in sleep/non-wear times. The following outputs were generated using the same software: main output for average waking wear time, wear time days, average sitting time, standing time, sit to stand transitions and number of sitting

bouts (<30 mins, 30<60 mins, ≥60 minutes). As with PA data, eligible data was subsequently analysed using SPSS statistical software for Windows version 25 (IBM, Armonk, NY).

Chapter 4

Study 1

Text-messaging interventions for improvement in physical activity and sedentary behaviour in youth: systematic review

The study presented in this chapter has been published in the *Journal of Medical Internet Research mHealth and uHealth* (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018).

4.1 Introduction

Participating in sufficient levels of PA is essential to reduce the risk of all-cause mortality and cardiovascular disease (Warburton, Nicol and Bredin, 2006; Alves *et al.*, 2016). For adolescents, it is recommended that they undertake at least 60 minutes of MVPA per day (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). Unfortunately, few adhere to these current activity recommendations with adolescence characterized by declining PA levels in conjunction with increased sedentary time, despite calls for sedentary time to be minimized (Department of Health, Physical Activity, Health Improvement and Protection, 2011). For instance, findings from Europe suggest that 83.2% of adolescents aged 11 to 17 don't achieve a minimum of 60 minutes of MVPA per day whilst globally, it has been estimated that 80.3% of adolescents are insufficiently active (Hallal *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, global data suggests that adolescents spend 57% of their time in sedentary activities with 40% of adolescents spending three or more hours watching TV on weekdays increasing up to 50% on weekends (2010; Arundell *et al.*, 2016). These findings are particularly concerning as SB is associated with various aspects of poor psychological and physiological health as well as all-cause and cardiovascular disease-related mortality (Thorp *et al.*, 2011; Tremblay *et al.*, 2011; de Rezende *et al.*, 2014; Hoare *et al.*, 2016). Conversely, increased PA improves adiposity, blood lipid profile, blood pressure, insulin resistance, aerobic fitness, and bone health (Poitras *et al.*, 2016) while also reducing premature all-cause mortality (Warburton *et al.*, 2010). Given these relationships both SB and PA are important therapeutic targets to reduce

lifestyle induced non-communicable diseases and especially during adolescence, where behaviours developed in younger ages are likely to continue into later life (Craigie *et al.*, 2011; Telama *et al.*, 2014). Given the inconsistent success of traditional intervention approaches, there is a need for research to generate new strategies to modify physical inactivity and SB (Cobiac, Vos and Barendregt, 2009).

mHealth, which draws upon mobile devices for health-related applications has emerged as a promising tool for health-related behavioural interventions (Free *et al.*, 2013). Mobile phones are used by all age groups with more than 90% of UK children aged 12 to 15 currently using them (Ofcom, 2016). Such high usage suggests that these mobile devices may offer a cost-effective and acceptable means for delivering health behaviour change interventions that can fit within people's everyday lives and have population wide reach. Unsurprisingly mHealth approaches are also being used to provide health care services worldwide, including in Africa, Asia, and South America (Chib, van Velthoven and Car, 2015). In the UK, the NHS is employing the text-messaging system 'Florence' to support patients in monitoring, managing, and improving their health (Clark and Birch-Jones, 2014). mHealth systems can also be used to send appointment or medication reminders to support health care workers by providing training, decision making and communication tools as well as to implement health promotion and education interventions (Chib, van Velthoven and Car, 2015; Silva *et al.*, 2015).

However, there is a lack of evidence regarding the effectiveness of mHealth interventions on behaviour change and health outcomes (Luxton *et al.*, 2011; Källander *et al.*, 2013; Chib, van Velthoven and Car, 2015). Unfortunately, research which has examined the effects of SMS interventions upon PA and SB in youth is also scant.

Previous systematic reviews and meta-analyses involving adolescents have included a variety of technologies, such as apps, e-mail, video games and websites when reviewing the evidence on the most effective means of improving PA and SB (Norman *et al.*, 2007; Cushing and Steele, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2011; Hieftje *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013; Chaplais *et al.*, 2015; Turner *et al.*, 2015; Weihrauch-Blueher *et al.*, 2016; Direito, Carraca, *et al.*,

2017). However, none of these reviews have assessed the effectiveness of SMS in isolation. Moreover, reviews have included a number of outcomes such as disease state or medication adherence (Cushing and Steele, 2010; Wei, Hollin and Kachnowski, 2011; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Head *et al.*, 2013; Loescher *et al.*, 2018) and have focused on several different health behaviours such as smoking and diet (Norman *et al.*, 2007; Cushing and Steele, 2010; Hieftje *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013; Turner *et al.*, 2015; Weihrauch-Blueher *et al.*, 2016; Loescher *et al.*, 2018). As such, evidence is lacking which has examined the efficacy of mobile devices to influence PA and SB. Furthermore, and to the best of our knowledge, existing systematic reviews and meta-analyses involving adolescents and SMS as a means for improving PA and SB have not explored the use of theoretical frameworks (Wei, Hollin and Kachnowski, 2011; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2013; Chaplais *et al.*, 2015; Siopis, Chey and Allman-Farinelli, 2015; Turner *et al.*, 2015; Weihrauch-Blueher *et al.*, 2016; Loescher *et al.*, 2018).

As evidence has shown increased effectiveness of health interventions using a behavioural theory framework (Glanz and Bishop, 2010; Webb *et al.*, 2010), it is surprising that many interventions have been developed without proper underpinning theory. Even in those studies that suggest their intervention was informed by appropriate theory, the specific application of theory often remains unclear (Taylor, Conner and Lawton, 2012; Bluethmann *et al.*, 2017). As well as evaluating the evidence of effectiveness of interventions using mobile phones for improving PA and SB, it is important to evaluate the theory and BCTs which have been used to develop these interventions. Providing this information is essential for health care practitioners to ensure that future mHealth interventions are effectively implemented. To provide this evidence, this review aimed to systematically identify mHealth studies that have been developed to increase PA levels and to reduce SB in adolescents. A subsequent aim was to identify the theory and BCTs used in these studies. Findings from this review are expected to provide insight into the development of future m-health interventions in order to maximize their effectiveness.

4.2 Methods

All data is reported in accordance with the PRISMA statement guidelines (Moher *et al.*, 2009).

4.2.1 Eligibility criteria

Experimental (randomized controlled trial or quasi-experimental design) studies were included if they involved or reported data separately for participants between the ages of 10 and 19 with or without known morbidities, used text-messaging via a mobile or smartphone within the intervention, both in addition to other intervention components or on its own, employed usual care, another intervention or no intervention as comparator and assessed at least one outcome related to PA and/or SB. All outcomes related to PA and SB, such as step count, MPA, and screen time, as well as all subjective and device-based outcome measures were eligible for inclusion. Further, only studies that were written in the English language and where full text was available were included. Studies were excluded if they solely used other technologies such as apps, websites, or email.

4.2.2 Information sources

A systematic search of the following electronic databases was conducted in March 2017 and updated in November 2017: Web of Science (coverage 1864-2017), PubMed (1809-2017), Medline (1946-2017), CINAHL Complete (1937-2017), PsycINFO (1800s-2017; not available for search update and replaced by PsycARTICLES 1894-2017) and SPORTDiscus (1930-2017). All databases except PubMed (7th November 2017) were last searched on the 8th November 2017. During the initial search, KL searched bibliographies and contacted corresponding authors of eligible studies. Bibliographies of existing systematic reviews and meta-analyses identified during the initial search process were also screened for eligible studies (Norman *et al.*, 2007; Fjeldsoe, Marshall and Miller, 2009; Cushing and Steele, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2011; Wei, Hollin and Kachnowski, 2011; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Head *et al.*, 2013; Hieftje *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013; Chaplais *et al.*, 2015; Orr and King, 2015;

Siopis, Chey and Allman-Farinelli, 2015; Turner *et al.*, 2015; Weihrauch-Blueher *et al.*, 2016; Direito, Carraca, *et al.*, 2017; Loescher *et al.*, 2018).

4.2.3 Search

Search terms and combinations of the electronic database search are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Electronic database search terms and combinations

Category		Search term		Search term
Intervention mode	1	„mobile phone“	9	mHealth
	2	smartphone	10	telehealth
	3	„cell phone“	11	“online health”
	4	„handheld device“	12	e-Health
	5	text-messag*	13	eHealth
	6	SMS	14	“mobile health”
	7	“messag* service“	15	“digital media”
	8	“messaging system”	16	ICT
	17	[1 - 16] combined with OR		
Study design	18	„randomised controlled“	21	„controlled trial“
	19	„randomized controlled“	22	quasi-experimental
	20	RCT		
	23	[18 - 22] combined with OR		
Participants	24	adolescen*	30	pediatric
	25	youth	31	teen*
	26	“young people”	32	„school age“
	27	“young adult*”	33	„school-aged“
	28	child*	34	highschool
	39	paediatric	35	„secondary school“
	36	[24 - 35] combined with OR		
Behaviour	37	activity	41	“behaviour change”
	38	sport	42	lifestyle
	39	exercise	43	sedentary
	40	health*	44	sitting
	45	[37 - 44] combined with OR		
	46	[17, 23, 36, 45] combined with AND		

* Asterisk used to search for words beginning with these letters

4.2.4 Study selection

Study citations from the electronic search were imported into the reference manager software Zotero (Version 5.0, online and standalone). KL manually removed duplicates. For the initial search, KL and HF independently screened titles and abstracts of all remaining studies. Following the search update, KL and DB independently reviewed new titles and

abstracts with the full texts of relevant titles obtained to confirm eligibility. KL and HF (DB for search update) discussed discrepancies until consensus was reached. KL hand searched bibliographies of eligible studies and contacted corresponding authors for additional manuscripts. All eligible studies were then included in qualitative synthesis.

4.2.5 Data collection process

Data extraction was conducted based on the Cochrane Collaboration's Data Extraction Template for Included Studies (Version 1.8) (Cochrane Consumers & Communication Review Group, 2016). Items of interest for this review such as the content of SMS and interactivity were added to the Cochrane Data Extraction Template. KL piloted the updated template on two randomly chosen studies eligible for this review. Subsequently, the piloted form was revised where necessary. Thereafter, KL and HF (DB after search update) independently extracted required data using the revised form. Extractions were compared and discussed until consensus was reached for all items. Content was then synthesised for analysis.

4.2.6 Data items

Data extracted included (a) general study information (such as country, aims, target health behaviour); (b) methods (such as study design, duration of intervention); (c) participants (such as population description, number recruited, age, sex, health status); (d) intervention and control group(s) (such as name of group, number of participants randomized, intervention mode, content, use of theory, message content, frequency, device, interaction, adherence); (e) outcomes (assessed PA/SB outcomes, method of PA/SB outcome assessment, timing of PA/SB outcome assessment); (f) results and conclusion (including additional results information and relevant conclusions); (g) other information (including funding source and conflicts of interest). Where data was missing or clarification was sought, study authors were contacted. Where multiple studies reported on multiple follow-up periods or outcomes of the same intervention, outcomes from the longest follow-up time point available for each outcome were extracted.

4.2.7 Risk of bias in individual studies

Assessment of risk of bias was conducted at study level. KL and HF (DB after search update) reviewed all included manuscripts using the Cochrane Collaboration's risk of bias assessment tool (Higgins *et al.*, 2019). KL employed this assessment tool using RevMan (software, version 5.3). Due to the nature of behavioural interventions, blinding of participants and personnel is challenging and rarely incorporated (Boutron *et al.*, 2004). This item was therefore not included in the assessment. The following remaining domains were judged: selection bias (random sequence allocation, allocation concealment), detection bias (blinding of outcome assessment), attrition bias (incomplete outcome data), reporting bias (selective reporting) and other bias. KL and HF (DB after search update) ranked each item as high, low, or unclear risk for each study and discussed discrepancies until consensus was reached.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Study selection

The electronic database and hand search produced 5,565 and 266 studies, respectively. After removal of duplicates, 2,365 studies were screened. 2,295 records were excluded, and 70 full-text articles assessed. Thirteen eligible full text articles assessing 11 different interventions remained and were included in qualitative synthesis. A flowchart of the systematic literature search is displayed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Flowchart of systematic literature search

4.3.2 Study characteristics

Study characteristics of included studies are shown in Table 2 and 3. Twelve studies targeted PA (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and seven SB (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, most studies also focused on dietary behaviours (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*,

2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017).

Some studies focused on participants with specific characteristics, including those not meeting current PA guidelines (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018), not participating in PE lessons or organised sports (Lubans *et al.*, 2012), having type 1 diabetes (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009), being at high risk for diabetes (Patrick *et al.*, 2013), having a BMI \geq the 85th percentile (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017) and being \geq 1-year post cancer therapy (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). When including overweight or obese participants, rates ranged between 23.7% (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) and 55% (Chen *et al.*, 2017) for overweight and between 6.7% (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) and 45% (Chen *et al.*, 2017) for obesity. Mean age of participants ranged between 12.5 (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) and 17.3 (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). One intervention only included female participants (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Twelve studies consisted of \geq 50% female participants (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018).

Table 2. Study characteristics of included studies

Author, year, country	N	Design	Age	PA/SB outcomes	Assessment	Intervention duration	SMS intervention	Comparator(s)
Brannon et al., 2018, U.S.	10	N-of-1 RCT	16.7 ± 0.95	MVPA min/day, SB min/day	Device-based	24 days	SMS + mobile app	Mobile app only
Chen et al., 2017, U.S.	40	RCT	14.9 ± 1.7	PA days/week, TV/computer hours/day	Self-report	6 months	SMS + FitBit and app + online program	Online program + pedometer + diary
Dewar et al., 2013, Australia	357	Group RCT	13.2 ± 0.5	Accelerometer counts/min, % MVPA, screen time min/day	PA: device-based SB: self-report	12 months	SMS + school program	Waitlist condensed intervention
Dewar et al., 2014, Australia	357	Group RCT	13.2 ± 0.5	% MPA, VPA, MVPA; SB min/day	PA: device-based SB: device-based + self-report	12 months	SMS + school program	Waitlist condensed intervention
Ermetici et al., 2016, Italy	487	Non-randomised CT	12.5 ± 0.4	MVPA hours/week, screen time hours/day	PA: device-based + self-report SB: self-report	24 months	SMS + school program	No information
Lana et al., 2014, Spain & Mexico	2001	RCT	Pre 13.26 ± 1.03 Post 12.91 ± 0.77	SB (less than 360 min PA/week)	Self-report	9 months	SMS + online program	Online intervention, limited access online intervention
Lau et al., 2012, Hong-Kong	78	Non-randomised CT	CG 13.26 ± 1.14 IG 12.29 ± 0.87	PA level last 7 days	Self-report	8 weeks	SMS + online program	No intervention

Lubans et al., 2012, Australia	357	Group RCT	13.18 ± 0.45	Accelerometer counts/min, MVPA min/day, SB min/day	PA: device-based SB: self-report	12 months	SMS + school program	Waitlist condensed intervention
Mendoza et al., 2017, U.S.	60	RCT	16.6 ± 1.5	MVPA min/day, SB min/day	Device-based	10 weeks	SMS + FitBit and app + Facebook group	Standard care
Newton et al., 2009, New Zealand	78	RCT	14.4 ± 2.37	Step count, MVPA min/week	Device-based + self-report	12 weeks	SMS + pedometer	Standard care
Patrick et al., 2013, U.S.	101	RCT	14.3 ± 1.5	MVPA min/week, SB hours/day	Self-report	12 months	SMS + online program	Online program, online program + group sessions + phone calls, usual care
Sirriyeh et al., 2010, UK	120	RCT	17.3 ± 0.68	MVPA MET minutes/week	Self-report	2 weeks	SMS only	Neutral SMS
Straker et al., 2014, Australia	44	Within-subject CT	14.1 ± 1.6	SB, light, moderate, vigorous PA min/day	Device-based	12 months	SMS + group sessions + phone calls	No intervention

N = number of participants randomised. Age in mean ± standard deviation. RCT = randomised controlled trial

4.3.3 Intervention design and content

Two interventions included SMS in addition to a school program (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). Five with an online intervention (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017) and others in addition to pedometers (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009), group sessions and telephone calls (Straker *et al.*, 2014), apps (Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and FitBits (Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Only one intervention consisted solely of SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Two interventions consisted of different types of SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Depending on group allocation, one employed SMS focusing on affective and/or instrumental beliefs (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010), whereas the other involved SMS from different senders including a parent, peer, or behavioural health specialist (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). School-based interventions using SMS included elements such as sport and PA opportunities, educational (group) seminars, provision of healthy foods, self-monitoring tools and printed or email materials promoting healthy lifestyles (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). One also used a Facebook group to promote healthy lifestyles and keep participants informed about the intervention (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). Interventions that included an online component also consisted of a variety of elements: forums, diet analysis, videos, educational games, challenges, educational materials, expert advice, behavioural skill training, goal setting, monitoring, feedback, and tutorials on behaviour change strategies (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017). One study included access to a private Facebook group, which provided rewards for achievements, encouragement, and a discussion board, as well as using FitBits and an app to monitor progress towards individualised goals (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). In another study, participants wore pedometers that were used to encourage PA and facilitate recording progress (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009). Another study included group sessions that provided education on health behaviours and achieving successful behaviour change. In this study, participants also received phone coaching during the 12-

month maintenance period post intervention (Straker *et al.*, 2014). One study using an app for monitoring and reporting of PA also included autonomous and external goal setting as well as daily feedback (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Depending on which condition participants were assigned for that day, SMS were sent by a behavioural health specialist, parents, or a peer (Brannon *et al.*, 2018).

4.3.4 Content of SMS

SMS were used to encourage, motivate, reinforce, and prompt participants to be physically active or maintain their current positive behaviour changes (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Some studies provided participants with suggestions for healthy lifestyle behaviours (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018).

In addition to promoting PA, one study also employed SMS to provide participants with health behaviour information, behavioural skills, solutions for PA barriers, to reinforce the benefits of PA and to build rapport with a virtual friend (Lau *et al.*, 2012). SMS were also used for feedback (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018), which in one study depended on the participant's goal attainment (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). SMS also included statements from testimonials as well as messages targeting intrinsic motivation and reflective questioning (Straker *et al.*, 2014). SMS were also used to reduce risk behaviours (Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014). Two interventions employed SMS aiming to increase participant self-efficacy (Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014). Three interventions sent SMS related to goal setting, such as the participants' specific weekly challenges (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). In addition to this, one intervention included affective SMS for encouragement and as a reminder of PA goals. In this intervention, SMS sent in intervention week two were based on the participants' step counts from week one (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Another study sent SMS regarding affective and/or, depending on the intervention group, instrumental gains associated with regular PA. These

included messages regarding the benefits of being active, such as physical and psychological improvements (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Three studies used SMS to remind participants to follow the intervention protocol, such as logging on to the intervention website or wearing an activity tracker (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2017).

4.3.5 Theory derivation

Three studies based their interventions on the TTM of behaviour change or Stage of Motivational Readiness for Change (SOC) model (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014). One study used the SOC model to tailor intervention content and presentation, such as by adapting SMS and website content according to the participant's stage of motivational readiness (Lau *et al.*, 2012). Participants in pre-contemplation, contemplation and preparation stage were given information on benefits and barriers of PA, opportunities for PA, goal setting as well as PA planning. Participants classed in the action stage were provided with monitoring tools and information to prevent relapse (Lau *et al.*, 2012). In addition to the TTM, one study also used the I-Change, Attitude - Social influence - Self-efficacy, Model and addressed attitude, social influence, and self-efficacy. They emphasised advantages of following the recommendations and disadvantages of risk behaviours, created a healthy online social environment and strengthened skills to avoid risk behaviours (Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014).

Moreover, one study used both behavioural determinants models and TTM to guide intervention design (Patrick *et al.*, 2013). One study employed affective and instrumental beliefs as well as the TPB (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Two interventions were informed by SCT (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017). One focused on self-efficacy, outcome expectation, self-monitoring, skill mastery and self-regulation capabilities (Chen *et al.*, 2017). Another employed SCT by planning social support or change, providing general encouragement and information about the behaviour health link as well as identifying barriers and strategies to overcome these. Specifically, outcome

expectations, social support and self-efficacy were targeted (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Self-determination theory (SDT) formed the basis for two interventions (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017), with one also using goal-setting theory (Straker *et al.*, 2014). This intervention focused on the provision of a need-supportive environment to achieve greater self-determination, autonomous motivation, and consequently greater engagement with the desired behaviour(s). Goal-setting theory was employed to increase autonomous and intrinsic goal setting in order to predict greater goal attainment and engagement with desired behaviours (Straker *et al.*, 2014). The other focused on psychological needs that influence motivation: competence, autonomy, and relatedness. The FitBit and app aimed to increase competence and autonomy by providing opportunities to set personalised goals and monitor progress. The Facebook group aimed to enhance relatedness by providing support (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Cybernetic Control Theory (CCT) was used by one study, which included self-regulation strategies defined by goal setting, self-monitoring, goal review and feedback (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Two studies did not provide any information regarding theory derivation. Authors were contacted and lack of a specific theory base informing SMS was confirmed (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016).

4.3.6 SMS delivery and interactivity

In three studies, SMS were sent weekly (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Two sent daily SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Another sent SMS only on weekdays (Lau *et al.*, 2012). Two sent three or more each week (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). Two studies only sent SMS during the maintenance period following the intervention (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017). In one, the number of SMS was reduced from three to one per week and finally to one per month (Straker *et al.*, 2014). In the other, SMS were sent bi-weekly during a 3-month maintenance phase (Chen *et al.*, 2017). Another intervention increased the frequency of SMS from weekly up to twice per week (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013,

2014). Five studies specified the time of SMS delivery (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). SMS were sent at 4pm at the end of the school day to minimise the risk of cross-contamination (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010), close to mealtimes (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016), between 7 and 8pm (Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and depending on the SMS content, such as immediately after school when encouraging PA (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Another study sent SMS on weekday evenings at 6pm and at 12pm on weekends. Here, participants were able to choose on which days they wished to receive SMS (Straker *et al.*, 2014).

Three studies gave participants the possibility to interact with the research team and reply to SMS (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014). Responding was optional, however one study provided a monetary incentive to do so (Lau *et al.*, 2012). Another study also allowed interactivity, however participants would only receive one reply (Straker *et al.*, 2014).

4.3.7 Risk of bias within studies

Five studies referred to previously published study protocols (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014). These were used to obtain missing information needed for the risk of bias assessment. The judgement of each risk of bias item across studies can be found in Figure 4. Table 3 shows the support for judgement of each item and study.

Figure 4. Judgement of risk of bias across studies

Table 3. Support for judgement of risk of bias per item and study

Author, year	Random sequence generation	Allocation concealment	Blinding of outcome assessment	Incomplete outcome data	Reporting bias	Other bias
Brannon et al., 2018	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	High High amount of missing data	Low All outcomes reported	High Compliance bias (use of incentives)
Chen et al., 2017	Low Randomisation using computer program	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Insufficient reporting of reasons for missing data	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report), compliance bias (use of rewards)
Dewar et al., 2013	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	High At baseline only. Outcomes likely to be influenced by lack of blinding	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Dewar et al., 2014	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Ermetici et al., 2016	High No randomisation	High No randomisation	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Insufficient reporting of reasons for missing data	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Lana et al., 2014	Low Randomisation using computer program	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Insufficient reporting of attrition, exclusions and reasons	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)

Lau et al., 2012	High No randomisation	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report), compliance bias (use of incentives)
Lubans et al., 2012	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	High At baseline only. Outcomes likely to be influenced by lack of blinding	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Mendoza et al., 2017	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	High Un-blinded RCT	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	Low Appears free of other sources of bias
Newton et al., 2009	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Low Assessors blinded at follow-up	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Patrick et al., 2013	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Not enough information	Unclear Insufficient reporting of reasons for exclusions and drop-outs	Low All outcomes reported	High Response bias (use of self-report)
Sirriyeh et al., 2010	Low Randomisation using random number generator	Unclear Not enough information	Low Assessors blinded at follow-up	Unclear Insufficient reporting of reasons for exclusions and drop-outs	High Missing mean and SD of MET minutes at time point 1	High Response bias (use of self-report), analytical bias (removal of outliers)
Straker et al., 2014	High Within-subject waitlist study design	High Within-subject waitlist study design	High Outcomes likely to be influenced by lack of blinding	Low Missing outcome data balanced and similar reasons across groups	Low All outcomes reported	Low Appears free of other sources of bias

Several studies were rated as unclear selection bias with regards to random sequence allocation (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Three were rated high risk (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) and three low risk (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017). Most studies also tended to be of unclear risk of selection bias with regards to allocation concealment (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Two studies were rated as high risk for this item (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016).

Seven studies were ranked to be of unclear risk of detection bias (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Dewar *et al.*, 2014; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018), with four judged as high risk (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017) and two as low risk (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). With regards to attrition bias, seven studies were judged to be of low risk (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017), whereas five were ranked as unclear (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017) and one as high risk (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Twelve studies were of low risk of reporting bias (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Only one study was classed as high risk of bias for this item (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Ten studies were ranked as high risk of response and recall bias (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017). Risk of compliance bias was evident in three studies (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*,

2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Another study was judged to be of high risk of analytical bias (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Two studies appeared free of other sources of bias (Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017).

4.3.8 Synthesis of results

PA and SB assessed in hours per week or hours per day were converted into minutes per week and minutes per day (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). For the following, intervention group refers to the condition incorporating SMS. An overview of findings including PA and SB outcomes and outcome measures can be found in Table 4. Table 5 shows theoretical frameworks used and effectiveness of intervention groups in each study.

Table 4. Overview of PA and SB outcomes and outcome measures in intervention groups at longest follow-up

	Accelerometer	Pedometer	Questionnaire	Interview
PA outcomes				
Accelerometer counts/min	↓ [3]			
Light PA min/day	↓ [13]			
MVPA %	↓ [3]			
MVPA min/week			↑ [5] ↑ [10]	↓ [11]
MVPA min/day	↑ [1,9] ↓ [8]			
MPA %	↓ [4]			
MPA min/day	↑ [13]			
VPA %	↓ [4]			
VPA min/day	↑ [13]			
MVPA score			↑ [7]	
4-day step count		↓ [10]		
MVPA MET min/week			↑ [12]	
PA days/week			↑ [2]	
SB outcomes				
Screen time min/day			↓ [3,5] ↑↓ [8]	
TV/computer hours/day			↓ [2]	
Total SB	↑ [4,13] ↑↓ [1] ↓ [9]		↓ [4] ↓ [11]	
PA less than 360 min/week			↑ [6]	

↑ Increase; ↓ Decrease; ↓ ↑ = Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) between baseline and

longest follow-up. ↓ ↑ = Statistically significant ($p \leq 0.01$) between baseline and longest

follow-up. [1] Brannon et al., 2018, [2] Chen et al., 2017, [3] Dewar et al., 2013, [4] Dewar et

al., 2014, [5] Ermetici et al., 2016, [6] Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014, [7] Lau et al.,

2012, [8] Lubans et al., 2012, [9] Mendoza et al., 2017, [10] Newton, Wiltshire and Elley,

2009, [11] Patrick et al., 2013, [12] Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010, [13] Straker et al., 2014

Table 5. Theoretical framework and intervention effectiveness for intervention group at longest follow-up for individual studies

	TTM	TPB	SCT	SDT	CCT	N/A
Physical activity						
Brannon et al., 2018					●	
Chen et al., 2017			●			
Dewar et al., 2013			○			
Dewar et al., 2014			○			
Ermetici et al., 2016						●
Lau et al., 2012	●					
Lubans et al., 2012			○			
Mendoza et al., 2017				●		
Newton et al., 2009						○
Patrick et al., 2013	○					
Sirriyeh et al., 2010		●				
Straker et al., 2014				●		
Sedentary behaviour						
Brannon et al., 2018					○●	
Chen et al., 2017			●			
Dewar et al., 2013			●			
Dewar et al., 2014			○●			
Ermetici et al., 2016						●
Lana et al., 2014	○					
Lubans et al., 2012			●			
Mendoza et al., 2017				●		
Patrick et al., 2013	●					
Straker et al., 2014				○		

N/A – No theory framework; ○ Negative effect (PA decrease, SB increase); ● Positive effect (PA increase, SB decrease); ●○ = Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) between baseline and longest follow-up. ●● = Statistically significant ($p \leq 0.01$) between baseline and longest follow-up.

4.3.9 Physical activity

Included studies assessed accelerometer counts (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013), LPA (Straker *et al.*, 2014), moderate and/or vigorous PA (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017;

Brannon *et al.*, 2018), step count (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009) or the number of days on which a minimum of 60 minutes of PA was achieved (Chen *et al.*, 2017). Nine studies assessed MVPA (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Three studies resulted in a decrease between baseline and longest follow-up for the intervention group (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Patrick *et al.*, 2013). One study however found an increase in MVPA between 6- and 12-month assessment (Patrick *et al.*, 2013). In another study, MVPA of normal weight participants increased between baseline and 2-school-year follow-up for the intervention group, however decreased for the control. For overweight or obese participants, MVPA increased in both groups (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). Four interventions resulted in increases in MVPA for all intervention and control groups between baseline and follow-up (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Two studies assessing MVPA used different types of SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). SMS sent by parents were effective in increasing MVPA for 70% of participants. SMS sent by a peer for 50% and those sent from a behavioural health specialist for 90% of participants. Overall, the intervention resulted in higher levels of PA than during the control condition (Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Another study employed neutral, affective, instrumental or a combination of affective and instrumental SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). Across all participants, MVPA increased during the 2-week intervention with affective SMS resulting in the highest levels of PA undertaken (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). In two studies, MPA and VPA were assessed (Dewar *et al.*, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014). Total, during school, after school and weekday MPA and VPA decreased from baseline to 12-week follow-up for both intervention and control group (Dewar *et al.*, 2014). The other study showed increases in MPA and VPA between baseline and 12 months (Straker *et al.*, 2014). For the intervention group, one study found an increase in PA levels between baseline and three months and between baseline and six months. PA levels decreased in the control condition (Chen *et al.*,

2017). Assessments of accelerometer counts, LPA and daily step count showed decreases between baseline and follow-up (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014).

4.3.10 Sedentary behaviour

Studies assessed screen time (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017), total SB (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Dewar *et al.*, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and whether participants performed less than 360 minutes of PA per week (Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014). Three interventions found a decrease in screen time between baseline and longest follow-up (Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017). One study found an increase in subjectively measured screen time on weekdays, however a decrease on weekend days (Lubans *et al.*, 2012). In one intervention (Dewar *et al.*, 2014), subjective SB decreased in the intervention group and increased in the control group between baseline and 12 months. However, device-based SB increased for both groups. In two studies (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017), the intervention groups reduced their total SB between baseline and follow-up, whereas the usual care or control group showed an increase in SB. Another intervention found an increase in SB between baseline and eight weeks, three months, six months, and 12 months (Straker *et al.*, 2014). One intervention resulted in an increase in insufficient PA in the intervention group between baseline and nine months although both control groups reduced their level of insufficient PA during the same period (Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014). In another study, SB was lowest when receiving SMS from a parent but was highest when receiving them from a behavioural health specialist, followed by SMS from a peer (Brannon *et al.*, 2018).

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Summary of evidence

The current review found promising evidence regarding the effectiveness of interventions using SMS to improve PA and SBs. Four out of five studies assessing MVPA via self-report found an increase in PA (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) whereas for device based MVPA, two interventions showed an increase (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and one a decrease (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013). Four studies resulted in a decrease for device-based accelerometer counts, LPA, MPA, VPA and step count (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014). One intervention showed an increase in device measured MPA and VPA (Straker *et al.*, 2014). Five studies assessing screen time and total SB using questionnaires demonstrated improvements (Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017) whereas device-based total SB increased in three (Dewar *et al.*, 2014; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and decreased in two studies (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Of 10 interventions involving PA assessment, eight resulted in an improvement of at least one PA outcome and of eight assessing SB outcomes, five showed improvements.

Most interventions included in this review focused on increasing PA, whereas elements targeting SB were scarce. Evidence suggests that distinct assessment and approaches are required to improve PA and SB (Hardy *et al.*, 2013; Pearson *et al.*, 2014). Previous meta-analyses have shown greater SB improvements in interventions solely targeting SB compared to PA interventions or those combining PA and SB (Prince *et al.*, 2014; Martin *et al.*, 2015). To maximise intervention effectiveness, future studies should consider using distinct approaches to improve SB and PA.

The evidence presented in this review noted a variety of different outcome measures, which led to conflicting findings. For both PA and SB, more studies showed improvements when

using subjective measures compared to device-based measures. This is in line with previous findings showing subjective measures demonstrate greater enhancements compared to device-based measures (Stephenson *et al.*, 2017). As self-report measures demonstrate low to moderate validity for the assessment of PA in children and adolescents, it appears that to assess effectiveness, device-based measures such as accelerometers are preferred for both PA and SB (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011). For the assessment of the nature and mode of activity being undertaken, subjective measures should be used (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011; Hardy *et al.*, 2013). Further, a variety of protocols for the assessment and evaluation of participant data has been used. It has been shown that the choice of data reduction protocol when analysing accelerometer data has a significant effect on the classification of SB and PA time in children (Ojiambo *et al.*, 2011). There is a continued need for the standardisation of methods when using device-based measures to assess PA and SB (Hardy *et al.*, 2013) and future studies should consider following current recommendations on the assessment of both PA and SB to enhance the comparability of findings between studies and allow more distinct and unbiased conclusions to be drawn.

Identified studies also used a variety of theoretical frameworks with the more frequent use of the TTM and SCT, consistent with the findings of others (Norman *et al.*, 2007). Interventions informed by SDT, TPB or CCT showed improvements in PA whereas interventions informed by the TTM, SCT and CCT revealed mixed results for PA and SB. Interventions employing SCT showed more positive results for SB than for PA. Nonetheless, the lack of information provided on how theory was applied within the intervention precludes our ability to confirm these assumptions with certainty. These findings are in line with those of a recent meta-analysis (Orr and King, 2015) which stated it was unclear how specific theoretical frameworks are applied or how they are linked to intervention effectiveness. Thus, our findings do not allow for a judgement on whether the ineffectiveness of some interventions included in this review is due to a lack of appropriate theory-derivation and -application. Further, conclusions with regards to how theory relates to intervention effectiveness need to

be drawn with caution and more evidence is needed to warrant the use of specific theories when targeting PA and SB in text-messaging-based interventions for youth.

Evidence has shown increased effectiveness of PA and SB interventions that include the BCTs of goal setting, self-monitoring, and feedback (Michie *et al.*, 2009). In this review, seven studies included goal setting and monitoring with five showing an increase in PA (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Two studies additionally included feedback and achieved improvements in PA (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Four studies including self-monitoring and goal setting found an improvement in SB (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2017; Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). These results are promising and indicate increased intervention effectiveness when including these BCTs in SMS-based interventions targeting PA and SB.

Previous reviews have shown weaknesses in the design of mHealth interventions (Norman *et al.*, 2007; Lau *et al.*, 2011; Wei, Hollin and Kachnowski, 2011; Orr and King, 2015). Our findings are in agreement with those reviews and suggest that SMS-based interventions involving adolescents are weak in design and at high risk of bias. The reasons for high risk of bias were attributed to the use of self-report measures (response bias), a lack of appropriate randomisation method (selection bias) and a lack of blinding (detection bias).

It was also not possible to infer the independent effect of SMS due to the lack of appropriate control groups. Only four studies employed designs that allowed for the effect of text-messaging alone to be assessed (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Lana, Faya-Ornia and López, 2014; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). Two studies showed a positive effect of SMS on PA (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) and two on SB (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). However, most studies included a variety of additional intervention components alongside SMS in the intervention and control groups. Definite conclusions with regards to the effectiveness of individual intervention designs, settings or contents can therefore not be drawn from this review. Future research should employ study designs that allow the examination of the independent effect of SMS on PA

and SB to strengthen the evidence base regarding effectiveness of using SMS alone. Additionally, there is a need for studies exploring which specific text-messaging components such as content or frequency of delivery are most effective.

There is also a continued demand for studies to explore long-term intervention effects on PA and SB (Fjeldsoe, Marshall and Miller, 2009; Lau *et al.*, 2011; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Chaplais *et al.*, 2015; Siopis, Chey and Allman-Farinelli, 2015; Weihrauch-Blueher *et al.*, 2016). Only four interventions lasted for 12 months or longer (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). Two studies assessed PA and SB after 24 months (Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016), with only one showing improvements in PA (Ermetici *et al.*, 2016), but both showing decreases in SB (Dewar *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016). It has been shown that SMS may be an effective tool to enhance participant interest in the long-term as well as to improve adherence (Wei, Hollin and Kachnowski, 2011; Turner *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, more studies should explore the effectiveness of interventions in achieving sustained behaviour change.

The current review shows high heterogeneity of study designs, intervention components, outcomes, and outcome measures. Possible conclusions regarding effective intervention designs and contents are limited and should be drawn with caution. This review provides some, currently limited evidence that the following approaches may result in increased effectiveness of SMS-based interventions for PA and SB in youth:

- Specific focus on desired behaviour
- Include self-monitoring, goal setting and feedback components
- Send three or more SMS per week for PA

Further, future research should incorporate the following methodological elements:

- Use of device-based outcome measures
- Include long-term follow-up
- Designs that allow assessing the independent effect of SMS

4.4.2 Limitations

The authors were unable to conduct a quantitative data synthesis due to high heterogeneity of included studies and a small pool of suitable data consisting of highly heterogeneous interventions and outcome measures. The current review included all studies incorporating SMS as part of their intervention which resulted in a variety of intervention designs and contents. Consequently, it was not possible to draw conclusions with regards to specific intervention elements positively influencing PA and SB. To the best of our knowledge this review provides the first account of interventions using SMS targeting PA and SB in adolescents. It provides researchers and practitioners with a database of potentially effective components crucial for the development of successful behaviour change interventions.

Existing reviews have employed methods to identify and code theory-based elements such as behaviour change techniques of included studies (Lau *et al.*, 2011; Direito, Carraca, *et al.*, 2017; Stephenson *et al.*, 2017). The current review has refrained from following this process for studies not specifying theory base. However, the authors of those studies were contacted, and a lack of theoretical foundation was confirmed. Despite the possibility that these interventions were unintentionally and unknowingly based on theory, there was no overt application of theory to study design. Therefore, it is judged to have limited contribution to intervention effectiveness.

This current review does provide a detailed account of the use of theory in SMS-based interventions involving adolescents which, to the best of our knowledge, is novel and crucial to understanding current trends in intervention design and content. Moreover, a rigorous methodology was used for acquiring suitable studies as well as during the data extraction process. This included hand searching bibliographies, contacting authors of eligible studies, following recognised guidelines during data extraction and pilot testing data extraction items. Existing reviews on technology-based interventions targeting health behaviour change have failed to include one or more of these components (Norman *et al.*, 2007; Fjeldsoe, Marshall and Miller, 2009; Cushing and Steele, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2011; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk,

2012; Head *et al.*, 2013; Hieftje *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2013; Chaplais *et al.*, 2015; Orr and King, 2015; Siopis, Chey and Allman-Farinelli, 2015; Turner *et al.*, 2015; Direito, Carraca, *et al.*, 2017).

4.5 Conclusions

The current review shows a high level of heterogeneity within SMS-based interventions targeting adolescent PA and SB. The evidence base consists of studies using different objective and self-report outcome measures that employ a variety of protocols which impairs the ability to synthesise study content and results. Additionally, assessment of risk of bias showed some limitations in study and intervention design. Results of individual as well as across studies should therefore be analysed with caution. Future research should employ more rigorous research designs, more structured and coherent intervention components as well as more appropriate and valid outcome measures. Overall, the current findings indicate that multi-component interventions incorporating SMS can be effective in improving PA and SB in adolescents, however more evidence is needed to further warrant SMS interventions to improve PA and SB.

Chapter 5

5.1 Study 2

A qualitative study exploring preferences, feasibility, and effectiveness of a text-messaging intervention to enhance physical activity and reduce sedentary behaviour in adolescents

5.1.1 Introduction

Recent evidence suggests that 81% of the global adolescent population is not sufficiently physically active (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). The health benefits of increased PA and reduced SB are well established and include a considerable risk reduction of premature mortality (Warburton *et al.*, 2010; Sallis *et al.*, 2016; Ekelund *et al.*, 2019). Adolescence is a crucial time for delivering healthy lifestyle interventions as behaviours in adolescence are likely to continue into later life and can improve health outcomes in adulthood (Rangul *et al.*, 2012; Telama *et al.*, 2014). Many different interventions are implemented to tackle inactivity (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). For adolescents, interventions tend to be delivered in primary care, communities, at home or in schools (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). School-based programmes in particular are useful since they can reach adolescents from different socio-economic backgrounds and can facilitate the provision of resources suitable for the delivery of behaviour change interventions (Story, 1999). Whilst some reviews have found schools to be an effective setting for improving PA (Kriemler *et al.*, 2011; Dobbins *et al.*, 2013; Rhodes *et al.*, 2017), most show small effects mainly for in-school PA (Kriemler *et al.*, 2011; Dobbins *et al.*, 2013). A more recent study has found no clear positive effects of school-based interventions on device-based MVPA (Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019). Regarding SB, there is limited evidence that school-based interventions are effective during or after school hours (Biddle, O'Connell, & Braithwaite, 2011; Hegarty, Mair, Kirby, Murtagh, & Murphy, 2016) with community-based interventions tending to be more effective for SB (Biddle *et al.*,

2011). Given the limited effectiveness of existing school-based approaches to improve activity levels and SB, alternative approaches are needed to improve PA and SB.

Recently, research has increasingly explored the use of mHealth interventions which draw upon mobile devices, such as phones, to promote healthy lifestyles and support behaviour change (Free *et al.*, 2013; Müller *et al.*, 2018). The use of these devices is supported by evidence showing promising results for PA and SB behaviour change (Free *et al.*, 2013; Müller *et al.*, 2018). In the UK, 83% of children aged 12 to 15 currently own a smartphone (Ofcom, 2019). In comparison, smartphone ownership and access in 13-17-year-olds in the U.S. stands at 95% (Pew Research Center, 2018) with 97% of 12-19 year-olds in Germany having their own smartphone (Statista, 2019). Such high usage suggests that mobile devices and SMS may offer an acceptable means for delivering health behaviour change interventions that can fit within everyday life and have population-wide reach. SMS require no log-in, download or other devices and messages can be transmitted in real-time, making them a low-burden intervention tool (Atun and Sittampalam, 2006). Additionally, more traditional face-to-face interventions tend to come with several barriers for adolescents including cost, lack of opportunities to be active close-by and activities not suitable for or desired by the target group (James *et al.*, 2018). Qualitative research with adolescents has shown that for interventions to be acceptable and effective, they should include PA opportunities that meet their needs and wishes, are suitable to their demographic and provide choice (James *et al.*, 2018). Considering ease of use and adaptability of SMS-based interventions, they offer the opportunity to provide a variety of tailored and population-specific advice and information on health behaviour change, without requiring face-to-face contact. Therefore, the purpose of Study 2 and 3 was to qualitatively and quantitatively evaluate the feasibility, user experiences, preferences, and initial efficacy of a theory-based PA and SB intervention for adolescents involving only SMS.

Despite a sharp rise in research activity around mHealth in recent years (Müller *et al.*, 2018), there is a lack of evidence regarding the effectiveness of mHealth interventions on behaviour

change and health outcomes (Luxton *et al.*, 2011; Källander *et al.*, 2013; Chib, van Velthoven and Car, 2015). Moreover, evidence examining the effects of SMS-only interventions upon PA and SB in youth is scant. Of the evidence currently available, many interventions also involve other components such as apps, group sessions, social media, or activity monitors (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018; Lee *et al.*, 2019). The current evidence base therefore does not allow for conclusions regarding the effectiveness of SMS as a standalone intervention to be drawn. Whilst it has been shown that multi-component interventions can be effective in changing PA in youth, they require more cost and resources compared to single component interventions such as SMS (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). Further, there is some evidence that cost-effective, wide-reach technology-led interventions such as those using SMS can show significant effects on PA (Webb *et al.*, 2010; Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018).

There are a number of studies that have evaluated adolescent preferences for behaviour change interventions, such as underage drinking (Hospital *et al.*, 2016), mental health (Ranney *et al.*, 2014; Aschbrenner *et al.*, 2019) and weight loss (Woolford *et al.*, 2011). Considering adolescent viewpoints is vital as it allows for more tailored and effective interventions to be developed, in a shorter period of time (Larsson *et al.*, 2018). However, there is limited qualitative research focusing on interventions promoting PA and SB change in this group, with even less assessing feasibility and perceived effectiveness. One study that explored feasibility of a SMS-based intervention for PA promotion did not obtain participant views on behaviour change and SMS focused specifically on steps, rather than overall PA (Thompson *et al.*, 2016). Whilst it employed theory to guide SMS, there was no in-depth assessment of it or how it influenced intervention experience and effectiveness (Thompson *et al.*, 2016). Another study focused on participant views of message delivery, such as frequency, and BCTs in SMS promoting PA (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). However, this study lacks an assessment of intervention feasibility or effectiveness (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). Importantly, the current evidence base is highly heterogenous and there is a lack of research

focusing on using SMS in isolation. Therefore, there is a need for developing SMS-only interventions informed through theory and to explore their feasibility, preferences, and acceptability. In addition, pilot testing of SMS interventions is vital and less expensive than full trials. Moreover, pilot studies ensure effective, user-guided interventions are developed without the unnecessary use of resources (El-Kotob and Giangregorio, 2018). Pilot feasibility testing is particularly important when assessing a novel intervention approach, as it allows for the identification of appropriate theory and ensures a more effective and 'implementation-ready' intervention can be developed (Craig *et al.*, 2008; Bowen *et al.*, 2009).

There is a continued debate on the effectiveness of using theory to guide intervention development and on the reporting standards of existing research (Prestwich *et al.*, 2014). Despite evidence that more extensive use of theory and use of more BCTs increases mHealth intervention effectiveness (Webb *et al.*, 2010), there is no clear indication which psychological theories might be effective when implemented within interventions involving SMS (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Study 1 revealed that interventions using TPB or SCT resulted in improvements in PA (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Further, attitudes, past behaviour, perceived behavioural control and self-efficacy are important predictors of PA intentions and in some cases PA behaviour change (Hagger, Chatzisarantis and Biddle, 2002; Rhodes, Macdonald and McKay, 2006; Plotnikoff *et al.*, 2011; Sheeran and Webb, 2016). Therefore, for Study 2 and 3, the intervention was designed to include messages linked to these theoretical components which were deemed appropriate for the use in SMS and relevant to the context of this study. Further, the present study aims to address current issues in the application and reporting of theory in interventions (Prestwich *et al.*, 2014; Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). This study will provide a detailed account of how and why different theoretical frameworks were used, show examples of SMS to facilitate understanding of these procedures and analyse participant preferences of the applied theories.

The primary aim of this study was the qualitative assessment of feasibility and focused on participant recruitment and retention, data collection, delivery of the intervention and SMS response rates (Aim 1). Secondary aims were to assess participant preferences of SMS content and design as well as a variety of theoretical components and BCTs used (Aim 2). A further aim was to establish intervention effectiveness by exploring participants' experiences of behavioural and psychological changes with regards to PA and SB (Aim 3).

5.1.2 Methods

For the reporting of methods, the 32-item COREQ checklist has been used (Tong, Sainsbury and Craig, 2007) (Appendix 12).

5.1.2.1 Study design

This study is a small-scale pilot feasibility trial with a cluster randomised waitlist-controlled design. The design of this study has followed the guidance and framework for the development and evaluation of complex interventions by the MRC (Craig *et al.*, 2008). The intervention was evaluated using a mixed-methods approach, with the quantitative elements presented in Chapter 5.2.

5.1.2.2 Recruitment and sample

The recruitment and randomisation process are described in detail in Chapter 3. All 25 participants randomised to the intervention group were eligible to participate in the focus group discussions conducted as part of this study.

5.1.2.3 Text-messaging intervention

Participants received SMS aiming to increase PA and reduce SB onto their own mobile phone over the course of three weeks. Messages started after baseline measures were taken and continued with post-measures taken during the last week of the intervention. SMS provided information on the benefits of PA, tips, and instructions on how to be more active and sit less, as well as feedback and motivational support. Some messages asked

participants to send a reply, such as what they had done to be more active. In turn, an automated response tailored to the participants' reply was sent. Examples of the intervention messages can be found in Appendix 13.

Language and tone

Overall, SMS were designed to be persuasive but motivational and encouraging in nature (Bandura, 1997; Woolford *et al.*, 2011). Messages were phrased positively, which has been shown to be most effective in changing PA behaviours (Parrott *et al.*, 2008). Also, it has been found that adolescents prefer positive, conversational messages with easy to understand language (Woolford *et al.*, 2011; Ranney *et al.*, 2014).

Theoretical underpinning

Current SMS intervention research does not provide a clear indication with regards to the effectiveness of specific theories for improving PA and SB (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). However, frameworks such as the TPB, SCT and self-efficacy theory have shown positive effects on PA (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). For this intervention, messages were designed based on these theories and their components (Ajzen, 1985; Bandura, 1989, 1997). These frameworks are widely used in PA interventions, have shown to be useful in predicting and supporting successful behaviour change and have been deemed appropriate for SMS-based programmes (Buchan *et al.*, 2012; Rhodes, McEwan and Rebar, 2019). For TPB, SMS were developed around perceived behavioural control, attitudes and intentions with others focusing on judgements of physiological and affective states, past behaviours, and verbal persuasion to increase self-efficacy. These components have shown predictive abilities for PA self-efficacy, intentions, and behaviour change (Bandura, 1977; Hagger, Chatzisarantis and Biddle, 2002; Rhodes, Macdonald and McKay, 2006; Plotnikoff *et al.*, 2011; Sheeran *et al.*, 2016).

Further, several BCTs were chosen to target the above-mentioned theoretical components (Table 8) (Michie *et al.*, 2013; Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015). A recent study has

described which groups of BCTs are commonly used in combination with different theories (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). It has been found that interventions using the TPB, SCT and self-efficacy theory often involve BCTs such as goal setting, feedback, information on how to perform the behaviour and information about health consequences (Bohlen *et al.*, 2020). These BCTs have been recommended for use in PA interventions (Michie *et al.*, 2009; Ashford, Edmunds and French, 2010; Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), so the SMS involved techniques specifically focusing on providing opportunities for goal setting, giving feedback, providing a variety of tips and instructions on how to be more active and sit less as well as information on the benefits of increasing PA and reducing SB.

Frequency and timing

Previous research found no significant differences in effectiveness between groups receiving different doses of SMS (Huberty *et al.*, 2017; Lau *et al.*, 2019). There is evidence supporting higher frequencies (five SMS/week) (Lau *et al.*, 2019) as well as lower frequencies (three SMS/week) for successfully increasing PA among adolescents (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Lau *et al.*, 2019). Further, it has been found that participants prefer a variety of frequencies and timings to ensure different preferences and needs can be met (Ranney *et al.*, 2014). Considering this evidence, daily messages were sent during week one of the intervention, with five messages in week two and three.

As with the frequency of SMS, there is currently no clear indication whether the timing of SMS can positively influence PA behaviour change (Lau *et al.*, 2019). Timing of SMS varied and was determined as follows. Messages were delivered at 10am (N=4), 12pm (N=4), 4pm (N=8) and 6pm (N=1) on weekdays and weekends. This was to ensure messages were sent during and after school hours to target specific behaviours such as school-time SB by sending SMS during lunch hours.

5.1.2.4 Data collection

Of 28 pupils in the intervention group, 25 provided consent to take part. Twenty-four participants (N = 11 female, mean age 16.83 ± 0.48 years) participated in the focus group discussions, with one participant absent on the day of the respective group. Four gender-mixed focus groups with five to seven participants, lasting between 38 and 43 minutes, were conducted shortly after the intervention finished. A multi-purpose classroom in the participants' school was used. KS and SD were present, with KS acting as main interviewer and SD facilitating the discussions and taking notes. A semi-structured interview guide was used to guide the focus group discussions and addressed participation and intervention processes, preferences for message design and delivery as well as perceived effectiveness in improving PA and SB (Appendix 14). As part of the discussions, the researchers printed the delivered messages, displayed them in the classroom and asked participants to use stickers to indicate which of the intervention messages they liked. Reasons for their choices and experiences of receiving these messages were then discussed. Different colours were used for male and female pupils to allow the retrospective exploration of potential gender differences. All discussions were audio recorded on three mobile devices (dictaphone, mobile phone and tablet).

5.1.2.5 Data analysis

Audio files of all focus groups were transcribed verbatim using an external transcription company experienced in working with academic institutions and speakers from the local area. KS checked transcripts for mistakes with SD assisting in resolving any inaudible sections. These steps ensured familiarisation with the data.

For the analysis of focus groups, a thematic analysis was undertaken using a deductive-inductive approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This type of thematic analysis was used as it is not tied to a specific theoretical framework and offered a flexible approach, which was

required for the present data as unexpected themes were likely to be generated due to the combination of deductive and inductive coding (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

This analysis was guided by Braun and Clarke's (2006) six steps outlined in Figure 5.

Transcripts were read, re-read, and imported into NVivo 11 (software, QSR International, Burlington, Massachusetts). KS took initial notes. As five a priori themes (recruitment and opt-in process, intervention process, preferences for SMS content, perceived effectiveness of SMS, suggestions for improvement) were chosen, KS deductively identified initial nodes by labelling individual comments related to those themes. Similar nodes were then grouped together into themes, with similar themes subsequently added to overarching categories, such as 'message design'. Following this, the remaining comments were coded using an inductive approach to allow unexpected themes to be developed. KS read and re-read the remaining quotes and created new nodes, with similar nodes grouped into themes and categories. Some inductive nodes related to themes that did not initially appear related to the chosen a priori themes during the first round of deductive coding.

To ensure high quality and rigour during the data analysis process, KS and a second investigator (RA) performed dependability and credibility checks. First, RA read and re-read all comments within each theme to ensure homogeneity within and heterogeneity across themes and categories (Patton, 1990). RA also worked to identify any un-coded sections, which were subsequently added as nodes and grouped with the appropriate themes and categories. Further, as part of the data analysis process, a 'critical friends' approach was also adopted to encourage reflexivity and enhance dependability and credibility of data (Smith and McGannon, 2018). The 'critical friends' approach enhanced the rigor of analysis as it encouraged KS to reflect upon their coding and provided room for considering alternative interpretations of specific comments (Smith and McGannon, 2018). Thus, all comments provided by RA were discussed with KS and meetings were held to ensure themes were coherent and reflective of what participants said. Further, RA pointed out comments which could be added to different themes and categories. These were then

comprehensively discussed to allow KS and RA to reflect upon the analysis and allow a critical exchange to ensure alternatives to the analysis conducted by KS were considered. RA also checked that negative cases were coded, and data was not analysed selectively.

Figure 5. Six phases of thematic analysis guided by Braun & Clarke (2006)

As a further measure to enhance dependability, a thick description and transparency of processes is provided throughout the manuscript and its appendices (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The COREQ checklist is also used to ensure all relevant methods are reported (Appendix 12) (Shenton, 2004; Tong, Sainsbury and Craig, 2007). Moreover, internal quality checks of data related to dependability and credibility were performed (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). This was conducted by considering any bias' present in sample selection and

processes relating to data collection, analysis and interpretation (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). These were discussed and relevant characteristics of participant selection, setting, data collection and analysis as well as reporting are presented.

5.1.3 Results

5.1.3.1 Aim 1. Feasibility

Recruitment and retention rates are reported in Figure 6. This figure also provides details on the parent consent and opt-in process as well as reasons for participation. As part of the wider evaluation of this SMS intervention, participants were asked to wear wrist-worn ActiGraph GT3X+ devices (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL) and thigh-mounted activPAL4 devices (PAL Technologies, Glasgow, UK) for 24 hours a day over the course of eight days. Although findings describing the effects upon PA and SB are reported in Chapter 6, participants were asked about their experience of wearing the devices as part of the focus groups (Figure 6). To increase adherence to wearing the activity monitors, participants were sent SMS reminders in the mornings of day three, six and eight of wearing the devices. Some felt these were useful, whereas others reported that the reminders were not helpful. It was mentioned that reminders were useful to ensure ActiGraph GT3X+ devices were replaced after taking them off for showering or bathing. There was no consensus as to which frequency of reminders was most useful.

To be eligible for analysis, participants had to wear activPAL devices for at least 10 hours during waking hours on four days, including at least one weekend day. These criteria have been widely used and tested with adolescents (Shi *et al.*, 2019). In the control group, 16 participants provided eligible SB data at baseline and post-intervention data compared to 18 from the intervention group. For PA data to be eligible, ActiGraph devices had to be worn for 16 hours on four days, including at least one weekend day.

Figure 6. Flowchart of recruitment and retention rates including comments on processes derived from focus group data (*)

Eighteen participants in the intervention and 18 from the control group provided eligible data at baseline and post intervention.

5.1.3.2 Aim 2. Participant preferences

Message design

Within the topic of text message design, five a-priori themes were chosen. These related to frequency, language and tone, length, and timing of messages as well as to messages designed for participants to reply to (See Table 6 for all themes, example quotations, and recommendations). There was no consensus which SMS frequency was most useful in supporting successful behaviour change. Some preferred daily messages, with others preferring fewer. Some participants said they disconnected with the intervention when frequency was reduced. Others felt it was too many messages, however they were not perceived to be overwhelming. When asked about their desired frequency over a longer intervention period such as two months, some mentioned they would prefer fewer messages. For some, receiving SMS for longer would mean the intervention would become part of their routine, whereas others felt they would disengage with the programme.

Participants felt that language and tone of the messages were appropriate to their demographic. They preferred positive language, such as the use of 'try' and 'could' rather than 'should' and perceived the messages to be easy to follow. Some mentioned more animated language, such as using exclamation marks and statements like 'well done' or 'woohoo' could be used to increase interest and ensure messages are being read.

Some participants reported to read long and short messages (character count between 160 and 60), with others preferring shorter ones. Some stated they read long SMS later, whereas shorter ones would be read immediately as the message appeared fully on their smartphone's lock screen. Further, participants preferred key points to be mentioned at the

start of each message as they would then go on to read the full message. It was also mentioned longer SMS should be removed.

Regarding preferred timing of SMS, there was no consensus among participants. Some preferred SMS to be delivered before school, whereas others preferred after school or evenings. However, some felt this would not be useful, for example when they were too tired or busy later in the day. Further, participants felt messages were not useful during school lessons or at work. Some reported that messages would be useful on weekends or during holidays. For accelerometer reminder SMS, participants felt these were sent too early in the morning (7am).

Table 6. Summary of participant preferences for message design

Category	Preferences	Participant quote	Recommendations
Frequency	Enough SMS to avoid disconnect	"I kept forgetting what it was, who was texting me because it wasn't that often." (FG3/1)	5-6 messages per week to cater for different preferences
	Daily SMS	"[...] I thought it would have been better to have it every day just to keep reminding you." (FG2/5)	
	Fewer SMS	"[...] If there was one every day it would get annoying." (FG2/1)	
Language, tone	Positive	"[...] There wasn't any 'You should be doing this, you should be doing that', it was 'You could be doing this' [...] so I thought that was better." (FG1/2)	Positive, animated with content relevant to the respective demographic
	Animated	"The messages [could] tell you woohoo or something like that." (FG2/2); "[...] more catchy and sharp [...]." (FG2/6)	
	Age-appropriate	"[...] It was easy to read and relatable [...]. Like being in school [...]. [...] It was relatable when you were reading it." (FG4/6)	
Length	Short messages	"When you open your phone, [...] you can read it to a certain extent, whereas if you got a short message you could see the full message [...]." (FG2/6)	Succinct with key point made at the start of each messages read them fully and at the desired time
	Key statement at start	"It could make the key points at the top of the text rather than make it a big paragraph and then put it at the bottom." (FG3/1)	
Timing	Outside school/work hours	"[...] Some of them were coming [...] during classes, but it's not like we could get up or do anything, [...] we need to sit and don't really get a choice to move." (FG1/3)	Tailor to school or working hours and provide variety to cater for different preferences
	Before school	"[...] In the morning would have been the best time, one to say get up and go, try and do this so that's your target set straight away." (FG3/2)	
	After school	"[...] People go to football [...] and you are like, right, okay, I don't want to go and then you get a message like, right, okay, I kind of need to go." (FG4/6)	Avoid messages during class times
	Weekends and holidays	"[...] It would have been useful if it was at the weekend and I was just sitting about [...]." (FG4/2)	
SMS to reply to	Suitable timing of messages	"Some of the messages kept coming through when we were in class. [...] I was looking at them in class and then by the time it had ended, I couldn't reply or was forgetting to." (FG1/3)	Ensure timing allows participants to respond
	More messages to reply to	"It gets us involved because we have to reply." (FG1/3)	Provide detailed instructions
	Allow free responses	"[...] Maybe if it asked you to give a brief description of what your goal could have been, then it would maybe make you think about it a wee bit more." (FG2/2)	Allow free text responses
	Ask how they feel after being active	"You could ask [...] how has being active made you feel that day?" (FG1/4)	Ask how participants feel after doing PAs
	Provide instructions	"[...] I think I [did] it wrong, so I did [...] the hashtag before the number so I don't know if you were meant to do that or not." (FG2/6)	

FG1/1 stands for focus group 1/participant 1

Table 7. Summary of participant preferences and suggestions for message content

Category	Preferences	Participant quote	Recommendations
Instructions and tips	Relevant tips	"It's really focused on walking, I hate walking. Exercising, I think it was break up your sitting time, maybe go out with your friends or try and do an activity of some sort. I know some of them say that but a lot of them are focused on walking." (FG3/2)	Provide variety of tips relevant to the demographic
	Variety of tips	"The texts were repetitive, saying 'stand up' every time." (FG3/3)	Provide instructions for indoor activities and specific durations
	Instructions for specific durations	"[...] Rather than just saying 'try to be more active' [...] you could maybe say 'go for a walk for 15 minutes' [...]." (FG4/2)	
	Provide indoor activities	"You could maybe encourage more indoor activity. If it was due to the weather, then [...] maybe doing [...] a cardio session or something like that. That would be beneficial because it gives another opportunity if outside isn't available." (FG1/3)	
Personalisation	Tailor to activity levels	"[...] If you got a text saying 'you've only done such and such', 'try a bit more', that would have probably been better" (FG3/3)	Tailor to activity levels and use names to personalise
	Use of names	"Say the name at the start. It gets your attention more, it is talking to you." (FG4/1)	
Other health behaviours	Include diet	"[...] How much fruit have you had? Try to cut out some sugar [...] and focus on fruit and water [...] as well as juggling walking and other activities to help you get more active and healthy." (FG3/6)	Add tips on other health behaviours, such as diet
Rewards	Offer points scheme	"[...] Like a points scheme [...], there could be a little survey, like did you do some exercise today? And if you did then a points scheme. I know younger kids love competition, they love to win [...]." (FG4/3)	Allow users to collect points, add competition and rewards
Other technologies	Use social media	"[...] Someone could not have a phone but they could have a tablet or iPad with Snapchat on it so that you could communicate with them that way." (FG4/4)	Use social media as alternative means for communication
Research participation	Remind of study participation	"I was really interested in what you are going to do with the research [...]. Kind of reminding us what we are doing is going to benefit people [...]. I think that would have really helped." (FG4/5)	Remind participants of research study to help with engagement

Participants also received interactive messages that asked them to reply to specific questions or statements. Some mentioned replying was a straightforward process, and they felt a certain need to reply or replied in order to help with the research. Others felt that the timing of messages was too inconvenient to reply straight away, and they would forget to do so later. Some participants had issues when replying as a specific format needed to be followed for the system to recognise the reply. Participants were asked to reply with a hashtag and number, with some not using the hashtag. The system then sent an error SMS, which participants were unsure how to reply to.

Message content

Participants mentioned that sending a variety of tips and suggestions on how to be active would improve and maintain interest in the intervention (See Table 7 for themes, examples quotations, and recommendations). Some participants felt suggestions for indoor activities would be useful in case of bad weather. It was also mentioned that more relevant tips for being active were preferred and specific instructions for the duration of activities was desired. Further, more SMS requiring participants to reply should be used. It was also suggested that messages could be used to ask participants how they felt after being active and some SMS could focus on other health behaviours, such as diet. One participant felt that on a day where they did not have time to be active but could eat healthily, a message encouraging this behaviour would be useful. Moreover, it was mentioned that participants could be reminded of their study participation.

Participants felt that tailored messages would increase their impact in supporting behaviour change. They suggested that for personalisation, participants' names could be used. Further, some mentioned that allowing them to reply with their own, personal goals would be preferred. Tailoring according to activity levels derived from accelerometer data was also desired. Additionally, some felt SMS could provide information on consequences depending on their individual behaviours, e.g. benefits from having walked to school or consequences of sitting down for long periods.

5.1.3.3 Aim 3. Effectiveness

Behavioural change

Participants mentioned that despite receiving and reading the SMS, school lessons and having to study at home prevented them from reducing SB, despite a desire or intention to change this behaviour. Travelling to and from school and tiredness at the end of a school day also prevented some participants from increasing PA. For others, increasing PA is something they would only do on their own accord without SMS prompts. Other barriers to increasing PA included interest in other activities such as playing video games, lack of desire or need to change, not 'being in the mood', illness, and bad weather.

However, for some, the messages resulted in positive behaviour changes with regards to PA, with one participant even encouraging their friends to be (more) active with them. For others, wearing the accelerometer device alone triggered an increase in PA. It was also mentioned that the messages were motivating, even if they had not resulted in any behaviour change at the time of the focus group discussions.

Psychological change

Some participants reported that the messages triggered intentions for behaviour change or made them feel guilty for not being active. It was also mentioned that some messages increased motivation to change PA and SB.

Behavioural and psychological change following specific messages

Using stickers, participants indicated which specific SMS they preferred. There were no clear trends that participants preferred messages focusing on PA or SB over the other. Also, there were no clear gender differences, with boys and girls selecting both message types by roughly equal measures. This exercise also showed no clear preferences of messages focusing on specific theoretical components, such as self-efficacy or intentions. Participants selected instruction- and benefit-based messages in roughly equal measures. Instruction-

based SMS focused on setting intentions and goals as well as enhancing perceived behavioural control, whereas benefit-based SMS aimed to improve attitudes. Not one theoretical framework was preferred, with no differences apparent between boys and girls. With regards to instruction-based messages, some participants felt they encouraged them to be more active and found them useful in successfully changing their behaviour. However, several participants mentioned the provided tips were not relevant or achievable and added they may be more useful for participants less active than them. To illustrate focus group data related to specific messages, an overview of themes, theory components and SMS examples grouped by BCTs is provided (Table 8).

Table 8. Participant feedback, theory components and example SMS per BCT used

BCT	Theory components	Example SMS	Positive participant feedback	Negative participant feedback
Instruction on how to increase PA [12]	SE, SoSu, I, PBC, GS	<i>You can be more active at any place and any time. Try sitting less at school, go outside in the afternoon, try a new sport or walk to the shops.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraged PA - Focus on small amounts was useful - Improved PBC - Instructions were useful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Did not encourage PA - Tips not relevant - Tips not achievable - More useful for those less active
Instruction on how to reduce SB [15]	SE, SoSu, I, PBC, GS, F	<i>Been sitting down a lot in class today? How about standing up or going for a walk at lunch with your friends. Doing it with someone else can make it easier!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Triggered awareness of sitting time - Encouraged being active 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty of changing SB at school
Information about health consequences [36]	A, I	<i>Mental health is all over the news! Being more active makes you more confident, attentive and energetic. Definitely worth moving more and sitting less!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraged/motivated to do PA - Increased knowledge and awareness - Provides reason to be active - Interesting even if knew facts already - Mental and physical health important 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No behaviour change
Social reward [16]	SE, SoSu, PP, A, I, GS, F	<i>Well done for completing week 1, these small changes you're making have a big effect on your health and wellbeing! Keep it up!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraged PA - Increased motivation - Built self-esteem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No behaviour change - Generic statements not warranted or relevant for each recipient
Goal setting (behaviour) [15]	I, GS	<i>Setting goals can help to be more active. What will you do? Sit less or be more active by walking or exercising? Reply #1 for sitting less #2 for being active > #1/2: Great! Keep this in mind and we will support you to achieve your goal!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraged PA - Served as a reminder for PA - Provision of goal examples useful - Set intention to be active (with others) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No need for goal setting as already active - No desire or unable to sit less
Feedback on behaviour [29]	I, PBC, F	<i>We hope the program is helping you to be more active at school and at home. Have you been active for 1 hour yet today? Reply #1 for yes #2 for no #3 for not sure > #1: Well done! You're doing great and maybe you could be even more active tomorrow! #2: Don't worry! There is still time so maybe go for a walk, do chores or exercise? #3: Any activity counts so just keep moving and try to sit less!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouragement was motivating - Instructions were motivating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generic statements not warranted or relevant for each recipient - No control over correctness of response
Pros and cons, reduce negative emotions, framing/reframing [24]	SE, A, PBC, JPAS	<i>Trying a new activity to be more active can be daunting. Your health is important, you should be confident and proud that you're doing something for yourself!</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraged PA - Increased confidence - Increased optimism - Focus on own intentions and ambitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not motivating

[N] number of stickers placed

5.1.4 Discussion

Our study provides a qualitative exploration of feasibility, participant preferences and effectiveness of an SMS-based intervention aiming to improve PA and SB in adolescents. The main findings of this study revealed that a low burden, SMS-only intervention is feasible with a group of secondary school pupils aged between 16 and 18. Participants liked positively framed messages, however there was no consensus which length or frequency is preferred. Timing transpired to be an important factor and should be tailored to individual schedules and preferences. Our study also shows that age-appropriate activities should be suggested and both behavioural and educational SMS can be useful. Educational messages were deemed interesting as they focused on mental and physical health benefits of PA, with behavioural SMS perceived to be motivating. There was no consensus which theory or BCT is preferred or most useful. These initial findings may be used in the development of future behaviour change interventions involving SMS (Craig *et al.*, 2008; Woolford *et al.*, 2011; Hingle *et al.*, 2013). Overall, this intervention was feasible, some messages were deemed useful for behaviour change and suggestions for improvements were provided.

As in previous pilot studies involving SMS in isolation (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Larsen *et al.*, 2018), attrition rate in this study was low (7.7%). This may be due to the low burden of this intervention as the frequency of messages never exceeded one per day, intervention duration was short and no additional intervention components were involved. The lack of consensus among participants as to which frequency or timing of SMS was most useful is in line with previous research (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). When comparing studies using components in addition to SMS, it is evident that the dose of SMS sent tends to be lower (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Interventions solely using SMS or minimal additional components, such as an activity tracker, have tended to use more frequent SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018). These interventions have been shown to be effective in increasing PA, as have those using multiple additional components with less frequent SMS over a longer period

(Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Considering participant burden and problems associated with adherence in long-term interventions, our findings emphasise the need for focusing on using minimal components, such as only SMS to effectively change activity behaviours. Our study revealed timing of SMS to be important, with some participants reporting not to read messages if they were delivered at an inconvenient time. The current evidence base indicates out-of-school hours (e.g. afternoons, weekends) seem to be preferred (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). For frequency and timing, this study seconds existing recommendations for providing variety to cater for different needs and preferences (Ranney *et al.*, 2014).

As in previous qualitative studies, our findings revealed that participants prefer positive and motivating language in SMS (Woolford *et al.*, 2011; Hingle *et al.*, 2013; Ranney *et al.*, 2014; Yan *et al.*, 2015). Short messages and those mentioning key points at the start of the SMS were also preferred (Hingle *et al.*, 2013; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). Further, future studies should continue to include an interactive component as they have been shown to be important elements for such interventions and participants enjoyed receiving those SMS (Fjeldsoe, Marshall and Miller, 2009; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). It has also been shown that increased adherence to and engagement with technology-based interventions can be linked to behaviour change outcomes (Donkin *et al.*, 2011). It can be speculated therefore that the interactive component in our study may have contributed to participants feeling more engaged with the intervention and facilitated their adherence to the study.

Our results also support existing findings that SMS should provide a variety of tips and instructions for enhancing PA and SB (Thompson *et al.*, 2016). It was mentioned that walking was not an enjoyable activity, so other, more suitable suggestions including cycling or doing specific sports such as football should be made. Participants indicated no clear preference for educational or behavioural messages with the majority finding SMS from both categories useful. A combination of behavioural and educational SMS should therefore be

provided considering interventions providing only educational components are less effective than those targeting goal setting or feedback (Cushing and Steele, 2010). Additionally, qualitative evidence has shown adolescents desire the following elements/BCTs as part of an SMS-based intervention: tailored feedback, instructions on how to be more active, social support, personalised goal setting, and rewards (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). Current evidence therefore indicates that SMS targeting feedback, goal setting, and instructions can be useful for supporting behaviour change in adolescents.

It has previously been shown that tailored interventions are preferred and more effective than those providing generic advice (Fjeldsoe, Marshall and Miller, 2009; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Head *et al.*, 2013; Ranney *et al.*, 2014). Our findings support this evidence; however, individual personalisation was not possible in the present study. The SMS delivery system used for sending and receiving SMS did not allow for the tailoring of SMS content and delivery as this was an automated process, which required sending the same SMS to all participants. Whilst the timing of delivery was tailored to school schedules, there was no option for accounting for individual differences or changes to the pre-determined delivery protocol. More studies are needed to establish how SMS can be personalised effectively and in accordance with automatization processes that require minimal user input and additional time and cost.

Our findings do not provide a clear indication as to which theoretical framework or components were preferred or more useful in enhancing PA and SB. There is a continued call for the evaluation of theory-based interventions to allow linking theoretical frameworks with effectiveness in enhancing PA and SB (Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018).

For behaviour change, some participants reported to have increased PA or reduced SB, whereas others felt unable to reduce their SB specifically during school lessons with fewer mentions of barriers to reducing SB during out of school hours. In Europe, school children spend on average 65% of the school day in SB (van Stralen *et al.*, 2014). It has also been shown that there are gender differences with regards to the patterns of PA and SB, such as

during lunch breaks at school, with girls more sedentary than boys (Bailey *et al.*, 2012). These findings should be considered to allow SMS to be tailored to specific periods and focusing on relevant barriers during those times. Research has shown that SB impacts upon PA during certain times of day, usually after school hours and on weekends (Atkin *et al.*, 2008). This highlights the need to provide participants with support for decreasing SB during adolescents' free time as well as encourage schools to reduce barriers for reducing SB during school hours. It has been found that interventions implemented during lessons, such as sit-stand-desks, can have positive effects on academic achievement and energy expenditure without limiting academic engagement (Koskelo, Vuorikari and Hänninen, 2007; Benden *et al.*, 2014; Dornhecker *et al.*, 2015). Participants also mentioned some SMS increased confidence and motivation to be active which is encouraging since the SMS were designed to facilitate these outcomes by providing feedback and using positive, supporting language (Ashford, Edmunds and French, 2010). Future research should consider assessing outcomes such as self-efficacy and motivation quantitatively to explore behaviour change mechanisms and provide an insight into psychological changes resulting from SMS-based interventions.

Personalisation of SMS was one of the main themes generated from our findings, however in practice, this may lead to issues regarding feasibility. PA is dependent on factors such as age, gender, level of intention, attitudes, motivation and social support (Sallis, Prochaska and Taylor, 2000; Biddle, O'Connell and Braithwaite, 2011). Tailoring SMS individually depending on these factors and elements such as schedules, personal preferences, and existing PA behaviours could be difficult. For SMS interventions to be feasible with large samples, automatic sending of messages is vital and individually tailoring SMS based on device-based activity data or psychological factors assessed via questionnaires entails significant burden in terms of time and resources. Despite this, psychological correlates of PA should be considered when designing interventions and more research with specific populations and participants with differing demographic, anthropometric and psychological

characteristics is needed. Specific needs and preferences, such as of school pupils aged 16, adolescents who are in a working environment outside of school or children who are unable to adhere to normal school hours due to health conditions should be explored. Future research should involve the assessment of mechanisms for behaviour change by measuring psychological outcomes related to PA behaviour change such as attitudes, intentions, and perceived behavioural control and should include SMS more specific and appropriate for adolescent school children (Buchan *et al.*, 2012; Rhodes, McEwan and Rebar, 2019).

5.1.4.1 Strengths

The present study followed a rigorous methodology, including the conduction of in-depth focus groups with credibility and dependability checks during the subsequent analysis. Our focus group discussions involved adolescents aged 16-18 which allowed a detailed exploration of our study aims. This pilot study provides vital evidence for the development of more effective, tailored, theory-based PA and SB interventions for adolescents (Craig *et al.*, 2008; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012). Implementing our findings when developing SMS-based interventions could enhance adherence and support acceptability of such programmes (Thompson *et al.*, 2016). Another strength of our study is the direct involvement of the target audience during the development and implementation of the intervention, which is encouraged with technology-led interventions (Larsson *et al.*, 2018; Partridge and Redfern, 2018).

5.1.4.2 Limitations

Participants in our study reported to already be (very) active and not in need of health behaviour change with regards to PA. Quantitative data collected as part of the wider evaluation of our intervention shows all participants in the intervention group complied with the current UK PA guidelines for cardiovascular activity, achieving a daily average of at least 60 minutes of moderate to vigorous PA/day (UK Chief Medical Officers, 2019) and 87.5% participated in out of school sport on at least one day per week. This does not allow for the

findings of this study to be generalised onto the global adolescent population as our sample does not reflect current activity levels of the general adolescents population (Kalman *et al.*, 2015). More research is needed to explore the needs and preferences of adolescents from different cultural and financial backgrounds as well as those with medical conditions or high SB levels and low PA. Further, using multiple theoretical frameworks within the same intervention and even within individual messages can be problematic (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015). The chosen theories were not applied as a whole, but rather individual components of these frameworks that were deemed suitable for SMS. It has been discussed that the theories' effectiveness may therefore be limited (Rhodes and Nigg, 2011; Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015).

5.1.5 Conclusion

Overall, our study shows that a low burden SMS intervention using pre-determined, automated message delivery is feasible. Motivating, positively framed SMS were appropriate, and participants felt they motivated them to be more active with some changing their activity behaviours as a result of receiving the intervention. Future interventions should involve tailoring of message content (e.g. instructions and information), delivery (e.g. timing), and theory. It is suggested that personalisation occurs according to individual schedules, preferences, needs and activity levels. Our evidence provides crucial insights into participant views and experiences of SMS interventions. Nonetheless, further work is needed to explore long-term adherence to such interventions and effective ways to tailor SMS and behaviour change mechanisms via psychological outcomes associated with PA and SB changes.

Chapter 5

5.2 Study 3

A cluster randomised controlled study exploring feasibility and effectiveness of a text-messaging intervention to improve physical activity and sedentary behaviour in adolescents

5.2.1 Introduction

In addition to the qualitative evidence presented in Chapter 5.1, a quantitative assessment of the feasibility and initial effectiveness of the 3-week SMS intervention was conducted.

Inactivity among children and adolescents remains a global issue with 81% of adolescents being insufficiently active (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). Similar findings are evident from Europe with an estimated 29% of adolescents failing to achieve the recommended 60 minutes of MVPA per day (Steene-Johannessen *et al.*, 2020). The health benefits from achieving sufficient levels of PA are well established and include improved cognition, bone health, mental health and a reduction in all-cause mortality (Hallal *et al.*, 2006; Alves *et al.*, 2016; Biddle *et al.*, 2019; Pascoe *et al.*, 2020). Yet children and adolescents only spend around 5% of their day in MVPA (Chaput *et al.*, 2014). It has recently been shown that increased PA at any intensity, including LPA, and a reduction in SB is associated with a reduced risk for premature mortality (Ekelund *et al.*, 2019). These findings indicate that interventions should target activity behaviours of different intensities, not solely focusing on MVPA, considering their impact on health (Ekelund *et al.*, 2019).

The need for effective interventions targeting insufficient levels of PA has been well established (Global Advocacy Council for Physical Activity and International Society for Physical Activity and Health, 2010). In order to ensure the evidence base of effective interventions is robust and reliable, there is a continued call for high quality research evaluating PA and SB interventions to be conducted (van Sluijs and Kriemler, 2016). This will allow PA intervention research to advance in a way that enables lessons to be learned

from previous (un)successful trials and interventions showing 'true' effective results can be implemented and disseminated (van Sluijs and Kriemler, 2016). Although schools have been cited as an ideal setting to implement health interventions, evidence is conflicting on the potential benefits of the school setting to induce improvements in measures of health and well-being (Owen *et al.*, 2017; Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019). Others also suggest that there does not appear to be any indication that specific settings for PA intervention are more effective than others (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, there is no clear evidence that interventions implemented in the community or at home are more effective than those implemented in schools (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). However, it has been suggested that interventions may be more effective when increased contact and interaction is provided (Rhodes *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, there is a call for research to target interventions implemented in the community without schools as the main delivery setting (Messing *et al.*, 2019).

Technology-based interventions have emerged as a promising tool for behaviour change interventions (Head *et al.*, 2013). Considering technology such as mobile phones or computers are used widely across different populations, interventions have the potential to include those harder to reach and less likely to be involved in health promotion interventions. Moreover, intervention content can be tailored with options to personalise delivery and interact through different formats such as SMS, videos or games (Lau *et al.*, 2011).

Existing evidence has demonstrated non-significant effects of mobile technology-based interventions on adult MVPA but improvements in SB (Direito *et al.*, 2017). As most school-based interventions tend to focus on PA, there has been a call for more research to be conducted focusing on interventions targeting SB (Hynynen *et al.*, 2016). A review of mobile technology-based interventions has shown promising results and they may be an effective tool for improving SB (Stephenson *et al.*, 2017). For PA, the evidence base has shown non-significant small to moderate effects of moderate technology-based interventions (Direito *et al.*, 2017). Whilst the current evidence base of PA interventions is highly heterogenous and

at times of low quality (van Sluijs and Kriemler, 2016), systematic review studies focusing specifically on adolescents, have been undertaken. Although some have found positive effects of technology-based programmes on health behaviours such as PA and SB (Loescher *et al.*, 2018; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), others have not (Böhm *et al.*, 2019). These contrasting findings may, in part, be due to high levels of heterogeneity with regards to study designs and differences in inclusion criteria concerning the mode of delivery (i.e. mobile technology). It must also be mentioned that reviews have found several existing studies to be of low quality, with inconsistent reporting of intervention components and often without a specific focus on PA.

It has been suggested that incorporating messaging, such as via SMS may be an effective tool to use within technology-based interventions (Webb *et al.*, 2010). SMS allow researchers to provide interactivity and personalised feedback (Lau *et al.*, 2011) and messages can be delivered at low cost and in real time tailored to the recipients' schedule (Hall, Cole-Lewis and Bernhardt, 2015). Whether interventions involving SMS have the potential to improve adolescent activity behaviour, however, is unclear. Recent feasibility studies (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Schoenfelder *et al.*, 2017; Larsen *et al.*, 2018) and reviews (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018) highlight the use of additional components such as activity trackers or online-based elements alongside SMS which precludes the inference of intervention effectiveness from SMS alone with their study design. Considering the burden and long-term resources associated with involving multiple components in a single intervention, and the promising effects of interventions using only SMS, there is a need to establish the feasibility and effectiveness of such interventions for improving adolescent PA and SB (Loescher *et al.*, 2018).

Whilst the promotion of increased PA is crucial, adolescents spend around 55% of a 24-hour cycle in SB and LPA, with around 40% in sleep, whereas only around 5% in MVPA (Chaput *et al.*, 2014). Considering SB can contribute to weight gain, reduced fitness and low self-esteem, it is crucial to ensure interventions aiming to improve PA behaviours also target SB

and LPA as vital components of a child's day (Tremblay *et al.*, 2011). Especially given recent findings highlighting the importance of reducing SB (Ekelund *et al.*, 2019), the evidence base of feasibility studies exploring text-messaging intervention effects on PA and SB is scant, with most studies focusing on PA-related outcomes (Schoenfelder *et al.*, 2017; Larsen *et al.*, 2018). Considering the importance of assessing PA and SB as part of current intervention evaluations, it is important to ensure that these activities are accurately captured.

It has been established that accelerometers are the preferred method for assessing PA in youth (Trost, 2020). However, previous text-messaging intervention studies have tended to rely upon self-report measures, such as questionnaires for assessing PA (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lau *et al.*, 2012; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2017). Systematic review evidence has shown that studies evaluating SB tend to employ non-device-based measures (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, recent review evidence has shown that existing questionnaires lack validity and reliability for the measurement of PA and involve issues such as recall bias (Hidding *et al.*, 2018). In contrast, ActiGraph GT3X+ (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometers are widely used to objectively measure PA, whereas activPAL devices have shown sufficient validity for the measurement of SB in adolescents and validated cut points for youth are available (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012; Migueles *et al.*, 2017). Both accelerometers are therefore recommended tools for the device-based measurement of PA and SB. It is important these two devices are deployed in future studies when interventions are aiming to improve both PA and SB so that accurate measures of these behaviours are collected.

Existing studies reporting PA and SB tend to rely upon population- and protocol-specific cut-points which can limit the comparison between studies employing different cut-points or using different accelerometer devices (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). In an attempt to overcome the reliance upon population and device specific activity thresholds, Rowlands (2018) has proposed new activity metrics that can be reported alongside traditional metrics such as LPA and MVPA that are not population specific. By presenting these metrics it is

hoped that future studies may compare or pool findings, regardless of the accelerometer device used to capture activity levels (Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018).

Considering the presented gaps in the evidence base and the use of novel assessment methods, it is crucial to evaluate the proposed intervention in the form of a pilot feasibility trial (Craig *et al.*, 2008). Pilot trials allow researchers to evaluate recruitment and adherence rates as well as intervention and outcome assessment processes (El-Kotob and Giangregorio, 2018).

The primary aim of this quantitative study therefore was to explore the feasibility, including recruitment and retention, data collection and interactivity, of a cluster randomised controlled trial of a text-messaging intervention to improve PA and SB in adolescents. A secondary aim was to assess the efficacy of SMS for increasing PA and reducing SB.

5.2.2 Methods

For the reporting of this study, the 40-item CONSORT checklist with the inclusion of the extension for pilot and feasibility trials was used (Appendix 15; Eldridge *et al.*, 2016).

5.2.2.1 Study design

This study is a small-scale pilot feasibility trial with a cluster randomised waitlist-controlled design. The process of designing this study followed the guidance and framework for the development and evaluation of complex interventions by the MRC (Craig *et al.*, 2008). The intervention was evaluated using a mixed-methods approach, with the qualitative elements presented in Chapter 5.1.

5.2.2.2 Recruitment and sample

The methods for recruitment and randomisation have been described in detail within Chapter 3. Fifty-two participants agreed to take part in this study. A sample size of around 50 participants is common for small-scale pilot intervention studies assessing continuous outcomes and was in line with the available resources related to data collection and analysis

procedures (Billingham, Whitehead and Julious, 2013). Formal power calculations were not conducted as this formative study was conducted to estimate parameters for the full study and not to formally test hypotheses (Thabane *et al.*, 2010).

5.2.2.3 Text-messaging intervention

The SMS intervention is described in detail within Chapter 5.1.

5.2.2.4 Data collection

A detailed description of data collection methods can be found in Chapter 3.

As part of this study, in addition to providing data regarding their age, gender and year group, participants were also asked to indicate their weekly hours of PE at school as well as information on sports participation after school.

To increase wear-time compliance for accelerometer devices worn as part of this study, SMS reminders were sent at 7am on days three, six and eight (McCann *et al.*, 2016).

5.2.2.5 Processing of accelerometer data

During the analysis of activPAL4 data, heatmaps were visually inspected to check for any required corrections to update sleep/non-wear times according to the study schedule. At baseline, no corrections were required, however post intervention, eight data files from the control group and 24 data files from the intervention group had to be updated as devices started recording and showed valid wear time prior to being attached. The respective bouts were corrected as sleep/non-wear.

5.2.2.6 Statistical analysis

Data was analysed to explore differences in PA and SB outcomes between groups. To check for normal distribution of baseline data, Shapiro Wilk's test was used. Outcomes with normal distribution were analysed using independent sample t-tests. As the following variables did not show normal distribution, Mann-Whitney U tests were conducted: number

of sitting bouts lasting 30 to < 60 minutes, average acceleration and MVPA. Further, data was analysed to test for significant differences of accelerometer wear time between baseline and post intervention for each group. As data was normally distributed, paired samples t-tests were used. For the analysis of PA and SB outcomes, data were analysed using univariate analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) as recommended (Vickers and Altman, 2001). Change scores from baseline to post-intervention assessment were used as the dependent variable and group (intervention or waitlist control) as the independent variable (fixed factor). Gender, age, BMI and baseline value of the outcome were used as model covariates. These variables were selected to adjust for differences between groups at baseline considering their predicted impact on intervention effectiveness. Data are presented using mean change scores, standard error (SE) and 95% confidence intervals (CI). All analyses were undertaken in SPSS (SPSS Statistics, Version 25.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.) with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

5.2.3 Results

Baseline participant characteristics can be found in Table 9 with the flow of participants throughout the study provided in Figure 7.

Figure 7. CONSORT pilot and feasibility extension flowchart

Overall, our sample tended to be of normal weight, medium to higher socio-economic status and more than half of participants in both groups took part in after school sports on five or more days. Baseline PA and SB data is presented in Table 10. For all PA outcomes, the intervention group was marginally more active than the waitlist control group and showed lower levels of sitting time (Table 10). The intervention and control groups showed significant baseline differences for the number of sitting bouts lasting between 30 and < 60 minutes as well as standing time ($p \leq .01$). For all other outcomes, no significant baseline differences were found ($p > .05$).

Table 9. Baseline participant characteristics

	Intervention	Control
n	25	27
Mean age (\pm SD)	17 (\pm 0.2)	15 (\pm 0.3)
Female	12	18
Mean BMI (\pm SD)	21.96 (\pm 2.62)	20.90 (\pm 3.53)
Overweight	4	3
Obese	0	1
Participants of most deprived 20%	4	2
P.E. periods/week	6	4
Sport participation after school	21	24
Sport participation after school on 5 or more days	16	14

Table 10. Baseline PA and SB levels presented as daily mean \pm SD

	Intervention	Control
n	21	22
Sitting time (hours/day)	9.9 \pm 0.9	10.4 \pm 0.7
Sitting bouts < 30 minutes (n/day)	49.0 \pm 9.3	53.5 \pm 11.8
Sitting bouts 30<60 minutes (n/day)	4.0 \pm 0.8	4.7 \pm 0.7
Sitting bouts \geq 60 minutes (n/day)	0.8 \pm 0.7	0.6 \pm 0.7
Standing time (hours/day)	2.9 \pm 0.7	2.4 \pm 0.6
Sit to stand transitions (n/day)	54.4 \pm 9.0	59.7 \pm 11.6
<i>N</i>	22	25
Intensity gradient	-2.50 \pm .15	-2.53 \pm .18
Average acceleration (mg)	31.8 \pm 5.3	31.2 \pm 8.5
MVPA (minutes/day)	37.8 \pm 10.0	37.5 \pm 17.7

4.2.3.1 Feasibility

Recruitment and retention

It was attempted to recruit two full secondary school classes to this study. Out of 28 pupils in the year five class, 25 agreed to participate, whereas out of 30 pupils in year four, 27 were

recruited. All 25 participants in the intervention group opted in via SMS and received messages over the course of three weeks, with no opt-outs after the intervention commenced (Table 13). All participants provided baseline data and at follow-up, only one participant in the intervention group failed to provide outcome measures due to absence.

Data collection

At baseline and follow-up, all participants who were present for data collection received both activity monitors (Table 11).

At baseline, four intervention group participants did not provide eligible data. One participant accidentally swapped their device with their sibling, who was part of the control group, at some point during data collection, another device was faulty, and two participants did not meet the wear time criteria. In the control group, five participants did not provide eligible data due to technical faults with their respective devices. At follow-up, three intervention group participants and seven in the waitlist control group did not fulfil the wear-time criteria.

Table 11. Recruitment, retention, and data collection rates

	Intervention, n		Control, n	
Potential	28		30	
Consent forms distributed	28		30	
Consent provided	25		27	
Randomised	25		27	
	Baseline	Follow-up	Baseline	Follow-up
Completed data collection	25	24	27	27
ActiGraph data available	25	24	27	27
ActiGraph data eligible	22	19	25	19
activPAL data available	25	24	27	27
activPAL data eligible	21	21	22	20
ActiGraph complete cases	18		18	
activPAL complete cases	18		16	
Received all text messages	25		N/A	

Regarding PA data at baseline, three participants from the intervention group did not provide eligible data with two not meeting the minimum wear time criteria and one swapping their accelerometer with another participant. In the control group, two participants did not provide eligible data. One was involved in the accidental exchange of accelerometers and the other

did not meet the required wear time criteria. At follow-up, five intervention group participants and eight participants in the control group did not meet the minimum wear-time criteria and were excluded from subsequent analysis.

As part of the assessment of feasibility of data collection methods, wear time of eligible accelerometer data was also evaluated (Table 12). In the intervention and the control group, there was a statistically significant difference between ActiGraph wear time at the two time points with higher wear time post intervention. For activPALs, both groups demonstrated higher waking wear at baseline compared to post intervention, however this difference was only statistically significant in the intervention group.

Table 12. Average daily wear time of accelerometer devices in hours (mean \pm SD)

	Intervention				Control			
	n	Baseline	n	Follow-up	n	Baseline	n	Follow-up
ActiGraph ^a	18	22.5 \pm 0.6	18	23.2 \pm 0.9*	18	22.3 \pm 0.8	18	23.0 \pm 1.1†
activPAL ^{a,b}	18	15.0 \pm 0.7	18	14.5 \pm 0.7†	16	14.4 \pm 0.6	16	14.2 \pm 0.6

*Significantly different from baseline ($p < 0.01$). † Significantly different from baseline ($p < 0.05$).

^a Complete cases only. ^b Waking wear data

SMS responses

The text-messaging intervention included three SMS that participants were asked to reply to, such as which goal they would set themselves or if they had been active yet on a specific day. One reply message was sent on day five, and two on day 13. For feasibility of the SMS delivery system and methods used to allow replies, SMS response rates were analysed. Only four participants replied to all three messages that required a reply. Seven replied to two, eight replied to one and six replied to none of the required messages. Eleven participants responded when asked to do so on day five. On day 13, two messages were sent prompting participants to reply, with 15 participants sending a reply to the first and 14 participants replying to the second SMS. Additionally, SMS replies had to be sent using a pre-determined format, using hashtag and the appropriate number, in order for the text-

messaging system to respond with an automatic, tailored feedback message providing encouragement, information or instructions. Four out of 19 participants who sent at least one reply did not use the pre-determined format (e.g. not using hashtag in their reply), which resulted in the automated feedback not being delivered. None of these participants responded with the correct reply format when prompted to do so by an automated error message.

4.2.3.2 Intervention effectiveness

Sedentary behaviour

Eighteen intervention group participants and 16 from the waitlist control group provided eligible activPAL data at baseline and post intervention and were included in subsequent analysis. After adjustment for pre-intervention values, gender, age, and BMI, there were no significant differences in post-intervention outcomes between the intervention and the waitlist control group (Table 13).

Physical activity

For PA outcomes assessed using ActiGraph GT3X+ devices, 18 intervention and 18 control group participants provided eligible data at baseline and post intervention. After adjustment for pre-intervention values, gender, age, and BMI, there were no significant differences in post-intervention PA outcomes between the intervention and the control group (Table 13).

Table 13. Mean change scores and ANCOVA results for sedentary behaviour and physical activity outcomes adjusted for gender, age, BMI, and baseline values as covariates. Complete cases only

SB	Intervention				Control				p
	Change score	SE	95% CI		Change score	SE	95% CI		
			n = 18				n = 16		
Sitting time (hours/day)	-0.2	0.4	-1.0	0.6	-0.3	0.4	-1.2	0.6	0.945
Sitting bouts < 30 minutes (n/day)	-6.9	3.7	-14.6	0.7	5.7	4.2	-2.8	14.2	0.103
Sitting bouts 30 to < 60 minutes (n/day)	0.1	0.4	-0.7	1.0	-0.7	0.5	-1.6	0.3	0.370
Sitting bouts ≥ 60 minutes (n/day)	0.3	0.4	-0.5	1.0	0.3	0.4	-0.5	1.1	0.998
Standing time (hours/day)	0.2	0.3	-0.5	0.8	-0.1	0.4	-0.8	0.6	0.657
Sit to stand transitions (n/day)	-7.1	3.8	-14.9	0.6	5.6	4.2	3.0	14.2	0.106
PA			n = 18				n = 18		
Intensity gradient	.08	.08	-0.08	.23	-.16	.08	-.31	-.01	.111
Average acceleration (mg)	1.1	3.7	-6.5	8.7	-5.1	3.7	-12.7	2.5	.387
MVPA (minutes/day)	1.2	7.0	-13.1	15.5	-5.4	7.0	-19.6	8.9	.624

SE = standard error; CI = confidence intervals

5.2.4 Discussion

The main aim of this pilot study was to assess the feasibility of a text-messaging intervention targeting PA and SB in adolescents. Our findings indicate that short-term, theory-driven messages providing instructions, information, and feedback on PA and SB are feasible for implementing to adolescents. Recruitment rates were high, with around 90% of pupils in the targeted classes agreeing to take part. Attrition between data collection time points was low and no participants opted out of receiving messages at any point during the study. In terms of data collection procedures, the use of stringent wear-time criteria for ActiGraph GT3X+ and activPAL4 devices is feasible as eligibility rates of PA and SB data were between 70% and 93% for both groups at baseline and post intervention. For analysis of activity data, only complete cases were included. For activPALs, 60% (control) and 75% (intervention) of participants provided eligible data at baseline and post intervention, compared to 76% (control) and 75% (intervention) for ActiGraphs. The use of SMS replies was deemed feasible with 76% of participants replying to at least one message when prompted. For effectiveness, our findings do not show significant differences in change scores between the groups when adjusting for covariates. However, there were slight increases in intensity gradient, average acceleration and MVPA among intervention group participants, with a decrease in all three measures found in the waitlist control group. Sitting time and the number of sit to stand transitions decreased in both groups, with standing time increasing.

The recruitment rate in our study was considered high at around 90% for both groups. This is comparable to other interventions involving SMS showing rates up to 95% (Chen *et al.*, 2017). However, a pilot study that involved recruiting adolescents via a broad community approach showed much lower recruitment rates at 42% (Larsen *et al.*, 2018). This indicates that schools may present a key gateway to successfully recruiting sufficient participants, especially for longer term, more extensive effectiveness trials. In addition to satisfactory recruitment, attrition rates in our study were low, with 0% between baseline and follow-up in the control group and 4% (n=1) in the intervention group. A review of attrition rates in PA-

related interventions for youth using accelerometers has shown rates tend to range between 0 and 30.9% (Howie and Straker, 2016). Indeed, our findings are in line with other pilot studies involving SMS interventions and accelerometers in adolescents that have reported attrition rates between 0 and 10% (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Larsen *et al.*, 2018).

For the analysis of PA and SB data, eligibility criteria in line with current research evidence and recommendations for best practice were applied (Winkler *et al.*, 2016; Rowlands, Edwardson, *et al.*, 2018). For both accelerometer devices, there was a loss of between 7% and 30% of participant data due to non-compliance with our wear time criteria. This is in line with findings that have shown accelerometer non-compliance in studies involving youth to range between 1.7 and 70.1% (Howie and Straker, 2016). More specifically, our data shows that across groups and assessment time points, the inclusion of the weekend day requirement resulted in several data sets (n=10) not being eligible for analysis. This is consistent with the findings of others that found the use of more stringent criteria leads to a reduction of eligible data sets, especially among older adolescent age groups (Toftager *et al.*, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2017). One study showed that including at least one weekend day in the wear-time criteria, eligible data sets are reduced by up to 47% compared to criteria not requiring a weekend day (Smith *et al.*, 2017). In comparison, the compliance in our study of at least 70% of participants is encouraging. Anecdotal evidence received from teachers suggested that participants involved in sporting competitions at the weekend were required to remove their accelerometer devices which may explain the reduced number of valid cases for the weekend. High compliance rates may be due to sending participants frequent SMS reminders in the morning to wear the devices, which has been shown to improve wear-time compliance during school hours (Belton *et al.*, 2013). Future research should explore wear time during and after school hours and on weekends so periods of frequent non-wear can be targeted.

Our results demonstrate that participants achieved higher wear time for wrist worn ActiGraphs post intervention compared to baseline. This was evident in both groups. In

contrast, for activPALs, both groups achieved higher waking wear at baseline. Evidence has shown that wrist-worn devices result in higher wear time and increased compliance with eligibility criteria compared to hip-worn devices (Scott *et al.*, 2017). However, our findings indicate that most participants complied with wear time criteria for both devices at both time points. There is limited data comparing wear time compliance between wrist- and thigh-worn devices or assessing their simultaneous use. Overall, our study shows that most participants complied with wearing both devices simultaneously and provided sufficient data for analysis. Moreover, in our study, financial incentives to increase wear time were not used. These findings indicate that the use of specific, recommended devices for the assessment of PA and SB is feasible and future research should employ this method and further evaluate wear time compliance in youth populations.

An important element of our intervention was the interactive component of prompting participants to reply to certain messages and providing encouragement or feedback tailored to their response. It has been found that for adolescents, social support can be crucial in the successful promotion of PA, with recommendations for its inclusion in behaviour change intervention in place (Mendonca *et al.*, 2014). For our intervention, 75% of participants replied to at least one message, however several others replied to only one or two. This indicates that interactivity may be an important component increasing engagement with the intervention for some, whereas it was less vital for others. The evidence base of effective social support and interactive features in mHealth interventions is scarce, with recommendations for best practice lacking (Tong and Laranjo, 2018). More research is required to establish quantitative effectiveness and perceived utility of a two-way messaging system used as part of a health promotion intervention for adolescents. Nonetheless, some participants replied using an incorrect format which resulted in the system sending an automated error message prompting a reply using the required '# plus reply' format. Before the start of the intervention, information sheets explaining the correct reply format were handed out and participants were advised to keep these at hand and consult when needed.

Considering the first message requiring a reply was sent several days after this information was distributed, it is likely that more timely instructions are needed. These should, for example, be provided once more via SMS. Additionally, when possible, the technology used to deliver and receive SMS should allow for several different reply formats to be used in order to ensure responses are received.

Whilst the formal testing of hypotheses was not the main aim of this pilot study, PA and SB outcome data was nonetheless collected and analysed to estimate intervention effectiveness (Thabane *et al.*, 2010). For PA and SB outcomes, our data does not show statistically significant differences between groups but there was some indication that the intervention may be effective in increasing PA levels. Also, both groups reduced overall sitting. Our findings are in line with those of other short-term studies involving SMS as the sole intervention component, demonstrating no significant effects on PA (Lau *et al.*, 2019). Although others have found significant improvements in PA (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010), it is likely that the disparity in findings is due to the recruitment of inactive individuals in comparison to the PA profiles of our participants. This suggests that participants with lower levels of baseline PA may exhibit greater potential for change when specifically targeted and should be recruited in future studies.

Our study had several limitations. At baseline, high levels of after school sport participation were evident for both groups. The recruited sample may already be considered 'fairly active' and participants may not have felt targeted by the intervention with a perception of not needing to change existing behaviours. In our intervention, messages were designed to be suitable for a variety of participants at different stages in the PA adoption process, however, a more targeted intervention depending on baseline activity and SB levels may be warranted. Technical limitations and restrictions of the text-messaging system used in this study did not allow for higher levels of personalisation within the intervention and its delivery. Messages had to be pre-determined for all participants and programmed far in advance of the start of the intervention. Additionally, the system for sending messages could only be

used by trained staff, who were not part of the research team. Future studies should test the use of open source or readily available, user friendly text-messaging systems allowing for more tailoring and adaptations throughout the intervention to be made. Moreover, interventions should provide specific advice for participants who are not currently engaging in healthy activity behaviours as well as those already achieving the recommended amount of PA.

Finally, whilst SMS allow the transmission of information and instructions in real time, it may not always be evident if or when participants read the messages. The intervention was designed to contain content appropriate for the target age group, however the timing of messages was not consistently in line with individual school timetables. This may have resulted in some messages being sent during class times, with participants potentially receiving or reading the message later. The content of the message may then not be relevant or timely anymore, making the provided instruction or information redundant with no immediate incentive to act upon the advice given. Future research should ensure the delivery of SMS is tailored to individual schedules. Participant preferences should be considered during the development of the intervention timeline and survey data may be used at follow-up to assess when messages were read.

5.2.5 Conclusion

Our study findings indicate that a short-term, theory driven text-messaging intervention is feasible for implementation in adolescents. Additionally, the use of stringent wear-time criteria and two simultaneously worn accelerometer devices for assessing activity and SB levels appears feasible. By tailoring the intervention to baseline activity levels, sending messages over a longer duration, and using an increased sample size with SMS providing instructions, information, and encouragement, increases in PA alongside reductions in SB may be evident.

Chapter 6

Study 4

A mixed methods feasibility study on an 8-week text-messaging intervention targeting adolescent physical activity and sedentary behaviour

6.1 Introduction

In addition to the pilot studies presented in Chapter 5, a mixed methods feasibility study of an 8-week SMS intervention was conducted.

Globally, PA levels among adolescents remain low, with only 19% meeting current recommendations of 60 minutes of MVPA per day (Guthold *et al.*, 2020). Further, studies exploring adolescent SB have found that at age 15, around 70% of waking hours are spent sitting down (Janssen *et al.*, 2016; Arundell *et al.*, 2019), compared to 51% at age seven (Janssen *et al.*, 2016). It has been shown that increased SB and inactivity in youth are associated with poorer health in later life, whilst increased PA reduces the risk of suffering from breast cancer or bone health-related conditions during adulthood (Hallal *et al.*, 2006). Furthermore, increasing PA and reducing SB is positively associated with improved mental health and a reduced risk for all-cause mortality (Alves *et al.*, 2016; Biddle *et al.*, 2019). Since PA tends to decline from adolescence to adulthood, it is clear that behaviours that will improve health need to be promoted and established during this time (Corder *et al.*, 2019). Approaches to promoting PA include interventions that consist of community campaigns or environmental and policy changes (Heath *et al.*, 2012). For youth, schools are often used to implement health promotion interventions given the opportunities to access and educate children from a wide range of backgrounds and the possibilities schools provide to reduce health inequalities (Langford *et al.*, 2014). Nonetheless, recent findings suggest that school-based interventions do not result in significant increases in PA when captured using either device-based measures such as accelerometers (Love, Adams and van Sluijs, 2019) or self-report measures (Owen *et al.*, 2017). Given these findings, it is important to explore other

settings for delivering health promotion interventions, which have the potential for delivering the most benefits.

There has been an exponential increase in research exploring the efficacy of technologies such as mobile devices and smartphones within health promotion interventions (Taj, Klein and van Halteren, 2019). In a recent review and analysis of the literature on digital health behaviour change interventions, almost 1/3 of studies targeted PA, with mobile apps, wearable sensors, and SMS used most frequently to promote PA (Taj, Klein and van Halteren, 2019). SMS are a promising tool for supporting PA and SB change since messages can be delivered at low cost in real time with content developed to be interactive and personalised (Lau *et al.*, 2011; Hall, Cole-Lewis and Bernhardt, 2015). In the UK and United States alone, around 90% of adolescents currently own or use a mobile phone (Ofcom, 2019; Pew Research Center, 2019). Considering SMS have the potential for population-wide reach due to high usage of mobile phones, they may be a promising tool for influencing adolescent health behaviours worldwide.

Although evidence suggests that SMS can be effective in increasing PA and reducing SB in adolescents (Loescher *et al.*, 2018; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), there is a paucity of intervention studies that have used SMS alone (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Interventions often incorporate additional components within their study design such as websites, activity trackers and face to face content, which does not allow for the independent effect of SMS to be established (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). In addition, interventions that involve more complex components such as school-based programmes (Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Dewar *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Ermetici *et al.*, 2016) or face to face contact as part of group sessions (Patrick *et al.*, 2013; Straker *et al.*, 2014) tend to be of longer durations between 12 and 24 months. In contrast, interventions using minimal additional components appear to be shorter, with those using SMS in isolation lasting only two to three weeks (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Study 2 & 3).

Furthermore, previous intervention studies supporting participants to be more active, tend to focus on increasing PA, and whilst SB is measured as an outcome, they do not appear to

include specific content that facilitates reducing SB (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017). Considering increased SB has been shown to be independently associated with poor physical and mental health (Carson *et al.*, 2016), there is a need for studies to target and measure PA and SB as separate constructs. Moreover, previous evidence suggests that adolescents are interested in changing additional health behaviours, such as healthy eating (Study 2). Multiple health behaviours, such as unhealthy eating and high levels of SB can often occur concurrently (de la Haye *et al.*, 2014) and tend to track from adolescence into adulthood (Telama *et al.*, 2014; Hayes *et al.*, 2019). Further, it has been shown that support PA behaviour change can elicit higher levels of self-efficacy for enhancing other health behaviours, such as SB (Prochaska, Spring and Nigg, 2008).

Evidence suggests that from seven to 15 years of age, SB increases by almost 23% to just under 75% of waking hours per day with the biggest increases in SB occurring during the transition from primary to secondary school (Janssen *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, adolescents spend a greater proportion of their time sitting down during class compared to after school (Arundell *et al.*, 2019), with evidence showing SB to be associated with adverse health outcomes such as obesity, hypertension, and depression as well as reduced academic achievement and self-esteem (de Rezende *et al.*, 2014; Hoare *et al.*, 2016). It is vital therefore that interventions are developed to target SB across the whole day, rather than during specific periods such as during school/work or after school/work.

In previous studies, authors tend to rely upon self-report measures to capture PA and SB-related outcomes (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Whilst such measures can provide more comprehensive information regarding the context and type of these activities, accelerometers have been established as the preferred device-based measure for assessing frequency, volume and intensity of PA and SB (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011). Furthermore, there has been a call for more studies to be conducted using device-based measures of SB in youth to explore additional, novel outcomes such as sitting bouts and sit to stand transitions in order to capture breaks in SB and explore periods of prolonged sitting

(Saunders, Chaput and Tremblay, 2014). This is particularly important with adolescents since the duration of sitting bouts tends to increase compared to younger children (Saunders, Chaput and Tremblay, 2014; Janssen *et al.*, 2016).

The current understanding of the effective use of theory within health behaviour change interventions, and those using SMS for PA and SB in particular, is limited (Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). It has been recommended that interventions should be developed in an evidence-based, theory-led manner to increase feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness (Craig *et al.*, 2008). Using theory to guide digital behaviour change interventions and incorporating BCTs is associated with increased effectiveness (Webb *et al.*, 2010). However, it has recently been shown that the use of specific theoretical frameworks and BCTs cannot yet be directly linked to intervention effectiveness for some delivery modes, including apps (Milne-Ives *et al.*, 2020). It is often unclear how and where theory is applied within interventions, with detailed descriptions lacking (Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018; Milne-Ives *et al.*, 2020). To assess the impact of theory on the effectiveness of behaviour change interventions, it is vital for studies evaluating such interventions to provide appropriate detail of how theory and BCTs are applied. The present study builds on evidence from the literature and recommendations for the most effective and appropriate theoretical frameworks and BCTs for use in PA behaviour change interventions involving adolescents (Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). To explore mechanisms for behaviour change and assess how theory may impact effectiveness, psychological factors associated with theoretical frameworks applied within interventions were measured (Orr and King, 2015). Study 1 demonstrated that SMS interventions guided by the TPB, SCT, or the TTM can be effective in improving PA and SB (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Psychological factors associated with these theories, including attitudes, intentions, perceived behavioural control, subjective norm, and self-efficacy have been shown to be linked with successful PA and SB change in adolescents (Nigg and Courneya, 1998; Plotnikoff *et al.*, 2011; Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014; Prapavessis, Gaston and DeJesus,

2015; Rice and Klein, 2019). The analysis of those psychological factors is crucial for exploring whether the applied theories are able to elicit improvements in PA and SB. The measurement of these individual components will allow for a deeper understanding of which theories and psychological outcomes should be targeted to achieve successful behaviour change (Orr and King, 2015).

Previous SMS intervention research has explored the level of responsivity regarding SMS replies to provide evidence on intervention fidelity (Bech- Larsen and Grønhøj, 2013; Psihogios *et al.*, 2019). Intervention fidelity is a crucial factor within evaluations as it allows assessing the level of interactivity as well as adherence to reading messages throughout the intervention duration. As remote SMS interventions do not allow for face-to-face contact, it is important to quantitatively and qualitatively explore if, how, and why participants interact with intervention content (Yardley *et al.*, 2016). Existing SMS interventions show promise, but they do not consistently elicit significant improvements in PA and SB (Study 1, 2, and 3). Further, research is needed to focus on exploring participant preferences and experiences. Enhancing the acceptability of SMS interventions is vital for eliciting more successful behaviour change, with qualitative and quantitative data needed to demonstrate the most effective intervention delivery protocols and content.

The primary aim of this study was to examine the feasibility, fidelity, and acceptability of implementing an SMS intervention among secondary school pupils. The secondary aim was to explore the initial efficacy of the intervention upon measures of PA, SB, healthy eating, and psychological outcomes related to the theoretical frameworks applied within the intervention.

6.2 Methods

For the reporting of this study, the CONSORT checklist with the extension for pilot and feasibility trials was used (Appendix 16; Eldridge *et al.*, 2016).

6.2.1 Study design

The present study is a small-scale, parallel mixed-methods pilot study with a one group, longitudinal design. Whilst a randomised controlled trial design was originally planned, low recruitment rates did not allow for a control group to be added. For the evaluation of the intervention, several quantitative measures as well as a focus group discussion were used. As advised by the MRC, this intervention was evaluated using a pilot study design as part of the process of developing a complex behaviour change intervention (Craig *et al.*, 2008).

6.2.2 Recruitment and sample

A convenience sample of secondary school pupils was recruited from a local school in South Lanarkshire, Scotland. To be eligible, participants had to be aged between 13 and 15 years, be able to take part in general PA, proficient in the English language and willing to receive messages to their personal mobile phone or, if not available, via email. Our target was to recruit two classes, each with 25 pupils providing an overall sample size of 50. This sample size was perceived appropriate to establish feasibility and is comparable to or exceeds sample sizes in existing feasibility studies and common recommendations (Julious, 2005; Larsen *et al.*, 2018; Wurz and Brunet, 2019; Schwartz *et al.*, 2020). The school identified two classes of potential participants, resulting in 70 individuals being provided with information sheets and informed consent forms.

6.2.3 SMS intervention

The 8-week SMS intervention was designed to target adolescents without the involvement of their parents. Messages were sent to their own mobile phones using the online delivery system 'Esendex'. Following a comprehensive review of SMS delivery services, Esendex was chosen as it allowed participants to send SMS replies free of charge and researchers could manually input SMS content and delivery protocols. One participant did not own a mobile phone, so messages were delivered via email following the same delivery protocol.

SMS provided information on the benefits of increased PA and reduced SB, tips on how to be more active, sit less and eat healthy as well as feedback and encouragement (Appendix 17). The intervention also encouraged interaction by asking participants to reply to receive automated, pre-determined responses from the research team. All messages were motivational in nature and positively framed to support behaviour change. Over the course of eight weeks, 38 messages were sent. Twenty-eight targeted PA and SB, seven focused on healthy eating and three explored engagement by asking participants about reading SMS and if they acted upon the advice that was given. Seven intervention messages included an option for participants to reply. SMS focusing on PA were guided by the current UK government guidelines for adolescent PA and SB, which included increasing activity to achieve 60 minutes of MVPA per day, encouraging participants to try a variety of activities at different intensities and reducing SB whenever possible (UK Chief Medical Officers, 2019). Evidence from a pilot study conducted to inform the current intervention showed that participants prefer receiving healthy eating advice in addition to messages focusing on activity behaviours (Chapter 5). To ensure message content was consistent with current practice within the UK's NHS, a team of dieticians from NHS Lanarkshire identified key topics provided during consultations with parents and their adolescent children. These included eating out, snacks, portion size, school lunches, balanced meals, drinking sufficient water, and achieving five portions of fruit and vegetables per day. These topics were subsequently included in the intervention and relevant messages obtained approval from an NHS Lanarkshire community paediatric dietician.

The SMS intervention design was based on evidence from systematic reviews exploring the use and effectiveness of theory within current interventions (Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), findings from a pilot study conducted to guide intervention development (see Chapter 5) and guidance from health professionals, including Telehealth staff and youth PA and nutrition experts. Thus, PA and SB-related SMS were based on components from within the TPB, SCT and the TTM (Bandura, 1997; Nigg and Courneya, 1998) as well as findings

from existing studies of SMS targeting adolescent activity behaviours (see Chapter 5; Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Lubans *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2017).

A review of SMS interventions demonstrated that those guided by TPB can be effective in improving PA (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). In adolescents, attitudes have shown to predict PA intentions, whereas perceived behavioural control is the strongest correlate of behaviour within the TPB (Plotnikoff *et al.*, 2011). There is promising evidence that these TPB components are also applicable as predictors for SB (Prapavessis, Gaston and DeJesus, 2015). Messages within the intervention therefore targeted the promotion of positive attitudes towards being active and sitting less and presented content enhancing the participants' perceived ease of improving PA and SB. Similarly, perceived peer and parental norms can enhance adolescent health behaviours and were therefore also targeted within the intervention (Rice and Klein, 2019).

SCT outlines how self-efficacy and social support determine health behaviours and research has found both to be associated with adolescent PA (Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014). SMS therefore provided links to finding and using social support to help change behaviours by encouraging the involvement of parents and peers. Considering higher levels of PA self-efficacy are associated with lower SB as well as increased activity, the current messages aimed to enhance the participants' perceived level of competence to increase PA and reduce SB (Sterdt, Liersch and Walter, 2014; Rollo, Gaston and Prapavessis, 2016). In addition, messages focused on targeting sources of self-efficacy, including the judgement of physiological and affective states, past achievements, and vicarious experiences (Bandura, 1977). Persuasive, but encouraging language was used to further enhance the participants' perception of being able to change the target behaviours (Bandura, 1977).

The TTM consists of multiple constructs aiming to describe how and when individuals change behaviours (Prochaska and DiClemente, 1983). One element within the TTM relates to stages of change that consist of the precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance stage, which individuals move through as part of a behaviour change

process (Prochaska and DiClemente, 1983). It has been shown that individuals in the precontemplation stage show lower levels of self-efficacy compared to all other stages (Nigg and Courneya, 1998). Considering the intervention targets sources of self-efficacy and SMS are designed to enhance self-efficacy, stages of change was assessed as an outcome in this study. This may establish whether targeting self-efficacy is important for supporting individuals to move successfully through the stages of behaviour change.

BCTs were also incorporated throughout the intervention. It has been shown that BCTs such as goal setting and feedback can have positive effects on PA and SB change in adolescents (Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Further, a recent expert consensus identified links between frequently used BCTs and mechanisms of action within behaviour change interventions (Connell *et al.*, 2018). Additional BCTs that therein have been linked to mechanisms of action related to the theoretical frameworks applied within our intervention were also used (Connell *et al.*, 2018). An overview of all BCTs applied within intervention SMS is provided in Table 14.

Table 14. Overview of BCTs linked to mechanisms for action and theories within the intervention

Theory	Mechanism of action	BCT title
SCT, TTM	Knowledge	Instruction on how to perform behaviour Information about health consequences
TPB, SCT	Beliefs about capabilities	Instruction on how to perform behaviour Verbal persuasion about capability Focus on past success
TPB, TTM	Intentions	Goal setting (behaviour) Information about health consequences
TPB, SCT, TTM	Subjective norms	Information about others' approval
TPB, SCT, TTM	Attitude towards the behaviour	Information about health consequences Credible source Pros and cons
SCT	Feedback processes	Discrepancy between current behaviour and goal Feedback on behaviour

SMS were developed to provide an interactive element by prompting participants to reply to certain messages. This allowed for the integration of interactivity but also enabled the assessment of intervention fidelity using response rates. Further, participants were asked to reply using a pre-determined format, which ensured messages were free of charge and a pre-determined response based on the participants' reply could be sent by the research team. The interactive messages and replies from the research team were framed by the theoretical frameworks applied within the intervention and targeted the following psychological factors: past achievements (week one, two, four and six), judgement of physiological and affective states (week three), perceived behavioural control (week five), and intentions (week seven). Targeting past achievements allowed the research team to provide feedback and encouragement based on the participants' perception of whether they had made any changes yet and how active they were. Asking about their perceived

judgement of physiological and affective states, such as how they felt when being active, enabled the response to focus on reinforcing positive feelings towards increasing PA as well as provide support in case participants experienced negative associations. One message asked about the participants' perceived behavioural control to allow for additional advice and suggestions for implementing small changes to increasing PA and reducing SB. Finally, intentions were targeted in another message, which allowed participants to set goals and receive encouragement for achieving these.

As the evidence base for the most effective timings and frequencies of messages is equivocal (Study 1 & 2), SMS were sent at varying times of day and at different frequencies throughout the intervention period (Huberty *et al.*, 2017; Lau *et al.*, 2019). Messages were tailored to the participants' school timetable and were sent either before school (between 8 and 8:30am), during mid-morning break (between 10:30am and 11am), at lunch time (between 12:30pm and 1:30pm), after school (between 3:15pm and 4pm) and in the evenings (between 5pm and 7pm). On weekends, messages were sent at 10am, 5pm or 6pm. SMS continued through one week of school holidays during week two of the intervention. The intervention was designed to ensure messages were sent at different times and on different days each week and the topic and theoretical orientation of SMS varied throughout. This was to ensure that different participant preferences and needs would be met throughout the intervention duration and engagement could be maintained. The frequency of messages reduced over the course of the intervention, with daily messages in week one and two, five messages each in week three, four and five, and three messages each in week six, seven and eight, to cater for different participant preferences (Ranney *et al.*, 2014).

6.2.4 Data collection

A combination of quantitative and qualitative measures was used to assess feasibility, fidelity, acceptability, and effectiveness of the intervention.

Focus group discussion

A sub-group of eight participants (five girls, three boys) who completed the intervention took part in an informal focus group discussion (29:25 minutes) to explore participant experiences of the intervention and wearing accelerometers, preferences for the delivery and content of messages and perceived effectiveness for changing PA and SB. Whilst the discussion was guided by a semi-structured interview schedule (Appendix 18), it was conducted in an informal setting, with scope for the conversation to be led by the participants' interactions with each other and the interviewer. To aid the discussion, a selection of intervention messages was printed and available for participants to refer to, which was expected to further allow participants to guide the conversation and refer to specific messages they felt were important for their intervention experience. Moreover, the PE teacher facilitating this study selected pupils who completed the intervention to take part in the focus group, with some selection focus on pupils who would be particularly willing to share their experiences, however generally not based on any other formal selection criteria. A school meeting room was used and only the main investigator (KS) and the chosen participants were present. The discussion was audio recorded using a dictaphone and mobile phone.

Feasibility and fidelity

To assess feasibility of implementing the present intervention, recruitment and retention rates were evaluated throughout the study duration. Participant attrition was analysed for both data collection time points and each week of the intervention. To explore fidelity, SMS delivery and participant response rates were used. This involved messages in week three and eight, asking participants to reply with how many SMS they have read. Participants were prompted to reply with a number corresponding to either having read '*all or most*' (1) or '*some or none*' (2) of the messages. Week five included a message asking if participants felt they were reading messages and were trying to follow the advice, using the answer options '*Yes*' (1) or '*No*' (2). As a further measure of fidelity, the use of interactive messages, with

each one incorporated during weeks one through seven of the intervention, was assessed by recording response rates.

Acceptability

To assess acceptability of the present intervention a short paper survey and focus group discussion were used. The 4-item paper-based survey was completed by all participants still enrolled at the end of the intervention to assess their preferences for receiving SMS.

Participants were asked to provide information on which day(s) of the week, time(s) of day and frequency was preferred. They were also able to leave any comments or feedback. This survey was conducted as not all participants were able to take part in the focus group discussion to convey their preferences.

Demographic and anthropometric data

In addition to the other demographic and anthropometric data described in Chapter 3, participants were asked to note any existing medical conditions as well as how often they participate in PE classes at school and in sport and exercise after school.

PA and SB data collection

A detailed description of methods for PA and SB data collection can be found in Chapter 3.

To increase accelerometer wear time, SMS reminders were sent at 8am on days two, four and five as well as at 4pm on day six (McCann *et al.*, 2016).

Using Processing PAL, a random selection of heatmaps of available activPAL4 data were visually inspected to check for irregularities in sleep/non-wear times. No corrections were required.

Healthy eating behaviours

To assess healthy eating behaviours, the Adolescent Food Habits Checklist was used (Johnson, Wardle and Griffith, 2002). This 23-item questionnaire has shown good

convergent validity and high internal and test-retest reliability in previous studies involving adolescents (Johnson, Wardle and Griffith, 2002). Additionally, the items had a strong link to the healthy eating-related intervention messages, covering similar topics and behaviours, making it suitable for assessing any dietary changes as a result of the intervention.

Psychological outcomes

Participants were asked to complete several self-report questionnaires assessing psychological outcomes related to the theoretical frameworks applied within intervention messages (See Table 15 for questionnaires, answer scales, and example items). All measures of psychological constructs were selected based on their suitability for use with adolescent populations (Motl *et al.*, 2000; Hagger *et al.*, 2001; Welk, 2002; Norman *et al.*, 2004; Parker *et al.*, 2010) appropriateness for the respective theory construct (Hagger *et al.*, 2001; Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010) and previous demonstrations of factorial variance and invariance as well as factorial, construct and content validity (Motl *et al.*, 2000; Welk, 2002; Norman *et al.*, 2004). Several items (PA attitudes n=8 items; SB attitudes n=6; PA intentions n=1; SB intentions n=1; PA subjective norm n=1; SB subjective norm n=1; PA self-efficacy n=7; PA stage of change n=4; SB stage of change n=4) were adapted to refer specifically to current UK guidelines for adolescent PA and SB (UK Chief Medical Officers, 2019) and where questions were not deemed to be relevant to the current context, they were removed (SB attitudes n=2). For more details, all questionnaires used can be found in Appendix 19.

Table 15. Overview of characteristics of psychological outcome questionnaires.

Outcome (source)	Items	Response scale	Example item
Attitudes			
PA (Motl <i>et al.</i> , 2000)	8	Disagree a lot (1) to Agree a lot (5)	<i>If I were to be physically active every day of the week it would help me cope with stress.</i>
SB (Motl <i>et al.</i> , 2000)	6	Disagree a lot (1) to Agree a lot (5)	<i>If I were to sit less every day of the week it would give me more energy.</i>
Intentions			
PA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010)	1	Unlikely (1) to Likely (7)	<i>I intend to do physical activities every day next week.</i>
SB (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010)	1	Unlikely (1) to Likely (7)	<i>I intend to sit less every day next week.</i>
PBC			
PA (Motl <i>et al.</i> , 2000)	4	Very difficult/Disagree a lot (1) to Very easy/Agree a lot (5)	<i>If I want to, I can be physically active for at least 1 hour every day.</i>
SB (Motl <i>et al.</i> , 2000)	4	Very difficult/Disagree a lot (1) to Very easy/Agree a lot (5)	<i>If I want to, I can reduce my daily sitting time.</i>
Subjective norm			
PA (Hagger <i>et al.</i> , 2001)	1	Unlikely (1) to Likely (7)	<i>Most people important to me think I should do physical activities at least for 1 hour every day.</i>
SB (Hagger <i>et al.</i> , 2001)	1	Unlikely (1) to Likely (7)	<i>Most people important to me think I should sit less.</i>
Self-efficacy			
PA (Motl <i>et al.</i> , 2000)	8	Disagree a lot (1) to Agree a lot (5)	<i>I can be physically active every day of the week no matter how busy my day is.</i>
SB (Norman <i>et al.</i> , 2004)	7	I'm sure I can't (1) to I'm sure I can (5)	<i>Turn off the TV even when there is a program on you enjoy?</i>
Stage of change			
PA (Welk, 2002)	4	Yes/No	<i>Do you currently engage in regular physical activity?</i>
SB (Welk, 2002)	4	Yes/No	<i>Do you currently limit your sitting time?</i>

PBC = perceived behavioural control

6.2.5 Data analysis

Quantitative and qualitative data were analysed separately, and the findings converged for the presentation of results.

Qualitative analysis

The focus group discussion was transcribed verbatim (KS) and analysed using the reflexive thematic analysis approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006, 2019). For this study, coding was conducted at a semantic level using a dynamic approach of inductive and deductive coding considering the presence of some a priori themes related to specific participant preferences. The five a priori themes included reasons for participation, preferences for SMS content, preferences for SMS design, perceived effectiveness, and suggestions for improvement. Familiarisation of data was achieved by transcribing, reading, and re-reading the transcript. This was followed by inductive coding for comments related to the participants' experiences of the intervention and a more deductive focus for the coding of comments related to a priori themes. Themes were generated by combining codes with shared meaning. Individual themes were then grouped into larger categories. To encourage reflexivity and enhance dependability and credibility of the analysis, the 'critical friends' approach was used (Smith and McGannon, 2018). A second researcher (RA) read and re-read the transcript and looked for homogeneity within themes and heterogeneity across themes (Patton, 1990). RA also looked for any un-coded sections and ensured negative cases were also coded. KS and RA discussed codes, themes, and categories to ensure these were coherent and reflective of the data.

Statistical analysis

Considering the present study aimed to assess feasibility and consisted of a small sample size, using inferential statistics to determine intervention effects is not recommended (Abbott, 2014). Instead, descriptive statistics such as proportions to present recruitment and retention rates, interactivity, and engagement as well as within-group mean changes were calculated (Abbott, 2014). Furthermore, only participants that provided both baseline and post intervention data were included within subsequent analysis. Complete case analysis has been recommended in case of high levels of missingness and if outcome data was

aimed to generate hypotheses for a larger scale randomised controlled trial rather than to assess full effectiveness of an intervention (Thabane *et al.*, 2010; Jakobsen *et al.*, 2017).

For healthy eating scores, psychological outcomes, except stage of change, and accelerometer data, means \pm standard deviations as well as mean change and 95% confidence interval were calculated for baseline and post intervention using SPSS statistical software for Windows version 25 (IBM, Armonk, NY). For stage of change, SPSS was used to calculate frequencies at both time points.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Feasibility and fidelity

A CONSORT diagram demonstrating the flow of participants through the study can be found in Figure 8. Sixty consent forms and information sheets were distributed to two classes, with an additional 10 to individual pupils from the same year group who expressed interest in taking part. Of the 70 consent forms distributed, 36 pupils provided consent and agreed to take part in the study. One participant was excluded as they received the intervention via email, with another absent at baseline, leaving 34 participants (26 females, mean age 13.62 \pm 0.49) completing data collection. Participant characteristics at baseline can be found in Table 16.

Table 16. Participant characteristics at baseline

	n = 34
Female, n	26
Mean age (years) (SD)	13.62 (0.49)
Mean BMI (kg/m ²) (SD)	21.46 (4.89)
Health status, n	
(Severe) Thinness	1
Normal weight	23
Overweight	9
Obese	1
Asthma	6
Coeliac disease	1
Type 1 Diabetes	1
Deprivation (SIMD), n	
1 (most deprived)	0
2	4
3	8
4	11
5 (least deprived)	11
Participation in every P.E. lesson, n	32
Sport participation after school, n	30
Sport participation after school on 3 or more days, n	24
Sport participation after school on 5 or more days, n	14

n = frequency, Mean (SD) = mean (standard deviation)

Thirty-four participants were sent an SMS asking them to opt-in to the intervention, with four opting out and seven not replying despite two follow-up prompts. Twenty-three participants opted into the intervention, with 14 still enrolled at the end of week eight. One participant opted out in week two, two in week four and six in week eight of the intervention.

Thirteen participants completed follow-up data collection, with one participant absent.

Overall, attrition between baseline and follow-up data collection was 62%, with an attrition of 39% between the start of the intervention and the end of week eight among participants who

opted in to receiving SMS. Following the 8-week intervention, 14 participants completed post data collection. As one participant received the intervention messages via email, their data was excluded from data analysis.

All 34 participants completed psychological outcome questionnaires and anthropometric data collection at baseline. At follow-up, all 13 remaining participants completed these measures.

At baseline, 34 participants were given both accelerometers. Following the return of ActiGraphs and activPALs, 29 participants provided sufficient valid wear time. Five did not meet the pre-determined wear time criteria for each device. At post, 13 participants took part in data collection and received both devices. For ActiGraphs, eight met the wear time criteria, compared to 11 for activPALs. Only complete cases were eligible for inclusion in the analysis of activity data, leaving eight participants for PA and nine for SB outcomes.

During the focus group discussion, some participants mentioned the accelerometers were “massive”, “really annoying” and “people [were] looking”. Others found the devices uncomfortable to wear as they developed a skin rash. However, it was mentioned that the issues with accelerometers did not have an impact on the participants’ perception of the intervention and SMS reminders to wear the accelerometers were “helpful”.

Figure 8. CONSORT pilot and feasibility extension flowchart

Twenty-two participants who were still enrolled in the study responded to the first message assessing engagement in week three. Twelve reported they read most or all messages, with two reading some or none. When asked again in week eight, 43% of 14 participants still enrolled in the study replied. One participant reported to have changed their number and did

not receive the final engagement message. All participants who replied, reported to have read most or all messages. In week five, participants were asked if they felt they were reading the messages and/or were trying to follow the advice given. Eleven participants of those still enrolled (n=20) replied. Ten replied saying they did, with one reporting they did not.

In the focus group, some participants mentioned to have read SMS throughout the intervention, whereas others read them "*sometimes*". It was also reported that participants didn't always see the messages at time of delivery but saw and read them at a later time.

Response rates were also assessed for interactive messages that provided automated feedback, advice or information depending on the participants' reply. In week one, 16 participants replied, with responses decreasing in weeks two through seven, with 12, 11, six, nine, eight and six replying respectively. Table 17 presents an overview of response rates for the respective pre-determined reply options within interactive messages.

Table 17. Response rates for interactive messages, per pre-determined reply option

Week	Question	Reply option 1	n	Reply option 2	n
1	What have you done this week to be active?	<i>You were active</i>	15	<i>You did nothing</i>	1
2	Since we started sending you SMS, what have you tried?	<i>You tried being active</i>	10	<i>You tried sitting less</i>	2
3	How does being active make you feel?	<i>Amazing or good</i>	9	<i>Not any way in particular or worse</i>	2
4	What did you do this week so far? Were you more active?	<i>More active than usual</i>	4	<i>Less active than usual</i>	2
5	What do you think: Can you change how active you are?	<i>You can</i>	9	<i>You can't</i>	0
6	Have you been active every day last week?	<i>Yes</i>	5	<i>No</i>	3
7	What will you do for 1 hour today?	<i>Run, walk, exercise, or play sports</i>	6	<i>Stand watching TV, walk to school, or stand between lessons</i>	0

6.3.2 Acceptability

The focus group discussion revealed that participants took part in the intervention to experience “*something different*” that they hadn’t seen before and to have fun. Some reported to participate because their peers were, whereas others mentioned to have agreed on their own accord. Participants felt “*fine*” about receiving SMS, with some reporting that continuously receiving messages was “*encouraging*” and in line with their expectations, whereas others stated the intervention was “*annoying*”. Participants also felt that the intervention duration of 8 weeks was not too long and should not be any shorter as participants “*wouldn’t have enough time to change*” their behaviours. In addition, participants preferred receiving messages to their mobile phone compared to via email.

The post-intervention survey showed most participants (n=8) preferred to receive messages only on weekdays, with three preferring weekdays and weekend days. For time of delivery, evenings were preferred by most (n=7), followed by afternoons (n=4) and mornings (n=2). For frequency, just under half (n=6) preferred to receive three messages per week, with four wanting five per week and three preferring daily SMS. This variety of preferences for message delivery with no clear indication of which day, timing or frequency is most useful was also confirmed in the focus group discussion. Some participants preferred receiving SMS in the morning, whereas others wanted more messages after school and in the evenings as they felt they had more time then to react to the advice and change their behaviours. For frequency, findings were also equivocal, with some reporting they did not read SMS when they were delivered too often as it was “*annoying*” and “*there were so many to go through*”. Participants also mentioned that they preferred receiving three to five messages per week as this meant they “*could actually take in what it was saying*”.

In terms of the content of messages, the focus group discussion revealed that participant preferences and experiences varied. An overview of preferences with regards to specific message categories is shown in Table 18.

Table 18. Overview of participant preferences for message content per message category with themes generated from focus group data

Message category	Themes
Advice and tips for healthy eating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice helpful for eating healthily • Advice provided new, useful information • Advice a useful reminder of information
Advice and tips for increasing PA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice to walk more was better than other tips • Advice to go to the park was helpful • Advice was useful to keep in mind for later
Advice and tips for reducing SB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice to reduce SB at school not achievable • Advice to stand more at home not useful • Advice to watch less TV was useful
Advice to include family/friends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice not useful as already doing other things with them • Advice not helpful as is doing PA on their own • Advice not useful as wants to spend time doing other things • Advice useful as would do PAs with friends or family
Information of health benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information was useful • Knew some information already • Preferred information over advice and tips
Setting goals for PA and SB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Felt no need to set goals • Did not have a specific goal • Set goals but unsure about achieving them • Setting goals was helpful and motivating for increasing PA
Interactive SMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful to receive feedback • Better feedback needed • Need for more answer options

6.3.3 PA- and SB-related outcomes, healthy eating behaviours and psychological outcomes

An overview of results for healthy eating scores and psychological outcomes can be found in Table 19, with the results for PA- and SB-related outcomes at baseline and post intervention, including mean change, shown in Table 20.

Table 19. Psychological outcomes and healthy eating score at baseline and post intervention for complete cases only

	Baseline n=13	Post n=13	
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean change (95% CI)
Healthy eating score	15.42 \pm 4.83	16.29 \pm 2.97	0.87 (-1.24 to 2.97)
<i>Psychological outcomes</i>			
PA Attitude	4.27 \pm 0.54	4.24 \pm 0.51	-0.03 (-0.35 to 0.29)
SB Attitude	3.17 \pm 0.89	3.10 \pm 0.87	-0.14 (-0.75 to 0.47)
PA Self-efficacy	4.17 \pm 0.60	3.98 \pm 0.55	-0.19 (-0.49 to 0.11)
SB Self-efficacy	3.69 \pm 0.68	3.71 \pm 0.50	0.02 (-0.29 to 0.33)
PA Intention	6.15 \pm 0.99	6.23 \pm 1.09	0.08 (-0.72 to 0.88)
SB Intention	5.46 \pm 1.05	4.85 \pm 1.07	-0.62 (-1.14 to -0.09)
PA Subjective norm	5.62 \pm 2.06	6.38 \pm 0.87	0.77 (-0.59 to 2.12)
SB Subjective norm	5.08 \pm 1.85	3.85 \pm 2.04	-1.23 (-2.37 to -0.10)
PA Perceived behavioural control	4.58 \pm 0.52	4.48 \pm 0.56	-0.10 (-0.34 to 0.15)
SB Perceived behavioural control	3.92 \pm 0.56	3.67 \pm 0.98	-0.25 (-0.68 to 0.18)
	n	n	
<i>PA Stage of change</i>			
Preparation	1	0	
Maintenance	12	13	
<i>SB Stage of change</i>			
Precontemplation	2	5	
Preparation	8	6	
Maintenance	3	2	

At post intervention, healthy eating scores had increased slightly, with self-efficacy for decreasing SB as well as PA-related intentions and subjective norm also showing higher scores (Table 19). All other psychological outcome factors decreased after the intervention compared to baseline. For PA stage of change, one participant moved from preparation at baseline to maintenance after the intervention. For SB stage of change, an increase of participants in the precontemplation stage was evident, with more participants in the preparation and maintenance stages at baseline.

With regards to the participants' perceived impact of SMS on their eating behaviours, some mentioned not to have changed, whereas others felt they did achieve small changes.

Table 20. PA and SB outcomes at baseline and post intervention for eligible complete cases only

	Baseline	Post	Mean change (95% CI)
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	
<i>PA outcomes</i>	n=8	n=8	
MVPA (minutes/day)	33.0 \pm 15.0	34.8 \pm 17.3	1.8 (-13.2 to 16.8)
Intensity gradient	-1.3 \pm 0.2	-1.3 \pm 0.2	0.0 (-0.1 to 0.2)
Average acceleration (mg)	30.0 \pm 7.5	31.1 \pm 9.0	1.1 (-5.8 to 7.9)
<i>SB outcomes</i>	n=9	n=9	
Sitting time (hours/day)	8.9 \pm 0.9	9.6 \pm 1.1	0.6 (-0.4 to 1.7)
Standing time (hours/day)	2.5 \pm 0.6	2.7 \pm 0.5	0.2 (-0.1 to 0.5)
Sit to stand transitions (n/day)	53.1 \pm 10.0	53.2 \pm 12.3	0.1 (-6.5 to 6.7)
Sitting bouts < 30 minutes (n/day)	48.8 \pm 10.1	47.7 \pm 12.7	-1.1 (-8.4 to 6.2)
Sitting bouts 30<60 minutes (n/day)	3.1 \pm 0.9	4.2 \pm 1.0	1.1 (0.3 to 1.9)
Sitting bouts \geq 60 minutes (n/day)	0.4 \pm 0.5	0.4 \pm 0.5	0.0 (-0.7 to 0.7)

The analysis of PA data shows a mean increase of 1.8 minutes (95% CI -13.2 to 16.8) of daily MVPA between baseline and post intervention. Average acceleration also increased slightly by 1.1 mg (95% CI -5.8 to 7.9), with intensity gradient remaining at -1.3 (95% CI -0.1 to 0.2). For SB, activPAL data revealed an increase in mean daily time spent sitting and standing of 0.6 hours (36 minutes; 95% CI -0.4 to 1.7) and 0.2 hours (12 minutes; 95% CI -0.1 to 0.5), respectively. For sit to stand transitions, a mean increase of 0.1 (95% CI -6.5 to 6.7) per day was evident. In terms of sitting bouts, post intervention data showed a mean decrease of 1.1 bouts (95% CI -8.4 to 6.2) lasting under 30 minutes, with an increase of 1.1 bouts (95% CI 0.3 to 1.9) for those between 30 and under 60 minutes. There was no change in the number of bouts lasting 60 minutes or longer (95% CI -0.7 to 0.7).

During the focus group discussion, some participants reported to have sometimes changed their PA behaviours by walking instead of driving or taking the bus and walking the dog or going for a run. Others were unsure if they made any changes because of the messages, with some mentioning they continued with their usual activities and felt *“what I’m doing is already good enough”*. For SB, some reported to have watched less TV and broken up prolonged sitting.

Barriers to changing these behaviours were also discussed in the focus group. Participants reported to be busy with homework or clubs and sometimes felt unable to immediately react to the advice. This was due to being busy with schoolwork or feeling unable to change their behaviours during class. SMS prompting participants to stand more during school hours were perceived not to support behaviour change as they *“sit in school for [...] six hours a day”* and *“can’t really [...] stand in class”*. It was reported that, when unable to immediately react to an SMS, the desired activities were *“done [...] later because I have more free time then”*. Further, some participants felt it took them a few days or a couple of weeks before they changed their PA and SB.

6.4 Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the feasibility, fidelity, and acceptability of an SMS intervention targeting PA and SB in adolescents. Our findings show that an 8-week intervention using SMS providing advice, information, and feedback for improving PA and SB has promise. Nonetheless, revisions to the recruitment and opt in process, accelerometer wear time compliance strategy as well as content and timing of delivery of intervention SMS are necessary prior to a further trial.

51% of 70 pupils in the two chosen classes agreed to take part, with 64% of 36 who provided consent also opting in via SMS to receive the intervention. The present recruitment rates are in line with those of another intervention study exploring the effects of SMS alone on PA in adolescents where 52% of 247 pupils who were invited to take part, provided consent (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010). In contrast, a 2-week intervention study

exploring health behaviour change SMS related to healthy eating that also involved secondary school pupils achieved a much higher recruitment rate of 86% of 1,225 pupils providing consent (Carfora, Caso and Conner, 2016). The lower recruitment rate in our study may be due to the double opt in process, which required participants to provide consent during initial recruitment and again via SMS. This approach mirrored the consent and opt in processes used within NHS Lanarkshire. Whilst the instructions for opting in via SMS were provided verbally and in paper form, some participants reported to have replied but did not receive the opt-in confirmation. To ensure participants who want to take part can be allocated to the intervention, a single opt-in process, common in current SMS intervention research, should be considered in future trials where possible.

It is acknowledged that in a previous intervention study using a 3-week SMS protocol, recruitment rates were much higher, with 90% of 58 pupils approached for participation agreeing to receive the SMS intervention (see Chapter 5). Moreover, all participants who provided consent also opted in via SMS and completed the intervention (see Chapter 5). The contrast in recruitment and retention rates between the two studies may, in part, be due to the longer intervention duration which may have resulted in some participants losing interest. Our findings also suggest that participants were already active and had been for a prolonged period. This may have contributed to the SMS losing impact as they may not have been perceived to be applicable for all.

From the participants who complied with both opt in processes, 61% completed the 8-week intervention. An attrition of 39% is moderate to high compared to other interventions involving adolescents who are required to wear accelerometers (Howie and Straker, 2016). Six out of nine participants (67%) who discontinued the intervention by opting out via SMS did so in week eight. Accelerometers were to be worn during the last week of the intervention and participants were informed of this procedure by their teacher and via SMS. Whilst speculative, it is thought that the drop-out may be linked to having to wear the accelerometers. Findings from the focus group discussion show that some participants had

issues with the ActiGraph devices and found them uncomfortable to wear. Also, some reported to have developed skin rashes when wearing activPAL devices, which may have also contributed to some participants opting out. These experiences are in line with existing studies that have found acceptability and adherence for wearing accelerometers could be improved by using less obstructive and more comfortable to wear devices (Audrey *et al.*, 2013). Participants also mentioned preferring Fitbits or similar activity trackers and suggested this would increase wear time. Accelerometers have historically been worn on the hip but recently, wrist-worn devices have been used in large scale studies with adolescents showing high wear time compliance of up to 83% for stringent criteria requiring seven valid days and ≥ 16 hours of wear per day (Rowlands, Harrington, *et al.*, 2018). To increase recruitment rates and avoid high drop-out for data collection, future studies should consider using devices such as the GENEActiv (Activinsights, Huntingdon, UK), Axivity (Axivity, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK) or ActiGraph GT9 Link (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, US) due to their watch like, less obstructive appearance. Therefore, whilst ActiGraph and activPAL devices have been validated and recommended for measuring adolescent PA and SB (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012; Migueles *et al.*, 2017) and wear time compliance of participants eligible for complete case analysis was high (62% and 69% respectively), other assessment tools may be needed for use in this population.

No incentives were used in this study to encourage accelerometer wear. A study assessing the effectiveness of different strategies to increase accelerometer wear time in young people has found that monetary rewards for wearing and returning devices may be effective for increasing compliance, with phone calls less effective (Sirard and Slater, 2009). However, another study exploring adolescents' views on protocols to increase compliance found that peer support, mobile phone reminders and monetary rewards were preferred (McCann *et al.*, 2016). Whilst participants in our study felt SMS reminders were useful to increase accelerometer wear time, some also reported that one of the reasons for taking part in our study was their peers' participation. Future research should explore the effect of peer

support on accelerometer wear time compliance in adolescents considering this appears to be a contributing factor within this age group.

Intervention fidelity in our study was considered satisfactory, with most participants reporting to have read all or most SMS. However, response rates for interactive messages reduced from 70% (16 participants) in week one to 30% (six participants) in week seven. The evidence regarding responsiveness for SMS replies within interventions involving adolescents is scarce. However, a 16-week SMS intervention for adolescent and young adult cancer survivors targeting health behaviour change found response rates to reduce from just under 80% in week one, to just under 60% in week eight and around 45% at the end of the intervention (Psihogios *et al.*, 2019). Further, a study promoting healthy eating via SMS, reported a reduction in response rates from 91% in week one to 71% in week four (Bech-Larsen and Grønhøj, 2013). Whilst it appears that a drop-off in engagement and interactivity is evident towards the end of this type of intervention, our study showed a reduction of 40%, compared to 20% for similar interventions (Bech-Larsen and Grønhøj, 2013; Psihogios *et al.*, 2019). It has been recommended that social support elements, such as an interaction between researchers and participants, should be included within behaviour change interventions (Mendonca *et al.*, 2014). However, there is a growing body of evidence calling for more effective strategies to enhance engagement with digital behaviour change interventions and mixed methods research to explore participant views and experiences (Yardley *et al.*, 2016). There is a need for future studies to involve target populations to explore what type of interactive features should be included and how these can contribute to enhancing effective engagement with the intervention (Yardley *et al.*, 2016).

The intervention was designed to use a variety of timings and frequencies for delivering SMS. The focus group discussion revealed that participants had different preferences for when and how many SMS should be sent. However, it appears that between three and five messages per week and SMS on weekdays only are preferred by most. These findings are in line with others who suggest that three to five messages per week is needed to support

PA behaviour change (Lau *et al.*, 2019). For timing of delivery, available evidence does not suggest a preference by participants (Lau *et al.*, 2019), so SMS were sent depending on when the targeted behaviours were likely to be carried out. Our findings demonstrate that participants have different preferences, however SMS during school were not perceived useful as participants felt unable to change PA and SB during class. A systematic review exploring the prevalence of SB outside of school hours (Arundell *et al.*, 2016) supports our recommendation for future interventions to consider focusing on after school hours to enhance behaviours such as active travel, after school sport participation and targeting prolonged sitting in the evenings. Participants also revealed that they read some messages later in the day, which may have limited the impact of the SMS. This further supports focusing the delivery of SMS on times of day during which SMS are accessible to adolescents and behaviour change is more likely to occur immediately. Moreover, it is warranted for future interventions to focus on reducing SB specifically during evenings, when the biggest amounts of prolonged sitting occur (Arundell *et al.*, 2019) and participants may perceive to be more in control of change.

The present intervention was based on behaviour change theory and aimed to enhance attitudes, self-efficacy, intentions, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control. Our focus group discussion showed that for the content of SMS, there was no clear indication what type of information or advice is preferred, and which theoretical framework is most useful for supporting successful behaviour change. Questionnaire data revealed that following the SMS, only self-efficacy for changing SB, PA intentions, and subjective norm appeared to have increased slightly. It has been shown that using theory and multiple behaviour change techniques within technology-based interventions can increase effectiveness (Webb *et al.*, 2010). In this study, SMS incorporated several theoretical frameworks and behaviour change techniques working in line with each other, however, there was a limited number of SMS focusing on each of these constructs which may have lessened their impact. Future research should consider implementing whole theoretical

frameworks into an intervention when the aim is to establish the effectiveness of individual theory components (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015).

Assessing intervention effectiveness was a secondary aim of this study and there were minimal changes in PA and SB. Stage of change data found that 92% of participants were regularly physically active for the past six months. Whilst most considered reducing SB before the intervention, they did not advance to the action or maintenance stage. This may be an indication that the participants recruited to this study were already taking part in PA and therefore less likely to change their behaviours. The focus group discussion supports this by showing that some participants did not feel a need to change their behaviours and continued with their usual PA. As the primary aim of this study was to explore feasibility and acceptability of the intervention, it is hoped that clinical populations who may benefit from SMS interventions can be recruited for future trials. Finally, it has been shown that tailoring SMS according to individual PA and SB levels using the TTM's stages of change may be effective in supporting behaviour change (Lau *et al.*, 2012). Notwithstanding the potential technical and resource challenges, future trials may wish to explore the efficacy of personalized SMS intervention content.

6.4.1 Limitations

There were several limitations associated with our study. Low recruitment rates did not allow for a control group to be added within this study. Despite no comparator being available, the present evidence still provides vital insights contributing to enhancing the feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of future SMS interventions. Moreover, the use of a double opt-in process that involved signed informed consent forms and an additional opt-in via SMS is acknowledged. Some participants reported not to have received this opt-in message, whereas others mentioned they replied, however their response was not received. In future, it is recommended that free answer formats are used, and teachers are prompted to follow up with participants in case of technical errors. In addition, our study sample consisted of participants who were already active, which may have affected their interest and perceived

need to change PA and SB. This may have also contributed to the minimal changes in PA, SB, and healthy eating scores.

6.4.2 Strengths

Strengths of this study include providing vital evidence for the development and implementation of future SMS interventions in applied settings. The present study evaluated an 8-week SMS intervention, with previous research focusing predominantly on shorter term interventions between two and three weeks (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Study 2 & 3). Moreover, Study 4 provided crucial insights into participant fidelity and acceptability and followed rigorous procedures throughout the intervention development and evaluation process. The application of theoretical frameworks and BCTs within intervention messages is a key strength of this study. The choice of theories and BCTs was guided by evidence from existing interventions as well as the wider literature, which supported the use of the TPB, SCT, and the TTM. Moreover, BCTs were used based on the applied frameworks, which was expected to further strengthen the effectiveness of the chosen theories. Crucially, each intervention SMS was based on theory and employed BCTs to support behaviour change. In addition, device-based measures for assessing changes in PA and SB were used, which rarely occurs simultaneously. Moreover, validated questionnaires were used for assessing healthy eating as well as psychological factors related to the applied theories. There is a lack of research assessing psychological outcomes for exploring behaviour change mechanisms, with the present qualitative and quantitative data making an important contribution to the evidence regarding effective theories and BCTs within SMS interventions.

6.5 Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate that an 8-week SMS intervention for adolescents implemented within a secondary school context can be feasible and acceptable. Nonetheless, several revisions to the intervention are needed prior to a future trial. These include the use of a single opt-in process to encourage recruitment, the use of tailored SMS based on

participants' activity levels, using accelerometers that are watch like in appearance and the use of SMS that target SB during after school hours rather than during school hours. Finally, feasibility of offering monetary incentives and peer support for increasing accelerometer wear time compliance will be explored.

Chapter 7

General discussion

This chapter contains a summary of aims and brief discussion of findings from Study 1, 2, 3, and 4. In addition, strengths and limitations of the research are presented, followed by implications for future research and recommendations for practice.

The data presented in this thesis aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the feasibility of an SMS intervention implemented among secondary school pupils, as well as an overview of participant preferences for, and experience of, such interventions. The individual studies explored the effectiveness, SMS content, and use of theory within existing interventions (Study 1), using mixed methods approaches to assess the feasibility and acceptability of SMS interventions involving secondary school pupils (Study 2-4). In the following, the main findings of each study chapter will be discussed.

7.1 Summary of findings

7.1.1 Study 1

The aims of the systematic review presented in Chapter 4 were to identify and review current interventions using SMS to target adolescent PA and SB as well as assess use of theory and BCTs. This study followed MRC guidance, which outlines that exploring the evidence base and previous use of theory are vital within the early stages of intervention development (Craig *et al.*, 2008).

Study 1 revealed that most SMS intervention studies targeted PA, with few providing specific content on SB. The majority used theory to guide the intervention, with some also incorporating BCTs. For SMS delivery, most studies chose timings outside of school hours and frequency of delivery varied between daily and once a month. For assessing intervention efficacy, the use of self-report measures remained popular. Some studies found improvements in PA and SB, whereas others did not. It was evident that those using self-

report measures were more likely to report improvements in PA and SB compared to those using device-based measures.

The evidence presented as part of Study 1 underlined the importance for future studies to involve content targeting both PA and SB (Hardy *et al.*, 2013; Pearson *et al.*, 2014) as well as comprehensively applying theory and reporting its use in-depth. This is expected to enhance intervention efficacy and will allow to explore the most effective theoretical frameworks and BCTs for specific intervention delivery methods, behaviours, and populations (Biddle, Mutrie and Gorely, 2015; Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015). Thus, Study 2, 3, and 4 followed this call and involved SMS content focusing on both PA and SB whilst establishing and testing theories and BCTs to guide intervention development. In addition, the evidence indicated that it is crucial for future studies to use device-based measures for assessing PA and SB (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011) to achieve higher methodological quality (Sallis and Saelens, 2000; Monyeki *et al.*, 2018).

For SMS delivery, there was no clear indication for the most effective timing and frequency, however it appeared a variety of times and doses is frequently used, with more research needed to explore successful delivery protocols. Moreover, the review provided vital evidence on intervention efficacy. A specific focus on populations with low PA and high SB levels was scarce, which is speculated to potentially result in a lack of effectiveness. This is in line with findings from Study 2, 3, and 4, which did not specifically target insufficiently active or inactive adolescents and also demonstrated limited PA and SB efficacy. Findings also revealed a lack of interventions using SMS in isolation, which did not allow for conclusions to be drawn with regards to the specific effectiveness of SMS. The interventions in Study 2, 3, and 4 therefore involved only SMS. Overall, the review provided a much-needed overview of the evidence on SMS interventions targeting adolescent PA and SB and underlined the importance of future intervention studies exploring strategies for enhancing efficacy, engagement, and user experiences (Yardley *et al.*, 2016).

7.1.2 Study 2

The aims of the qualitative pilot study presented in Chapter 5 were to assess the feasibility, participant preferences, and perceived effectiveness of a 3-week, theory-based SMS intervention targeting adolescent PA and SB.

The four focus group discussions revealed that the SMS intervention and accelerometer protocol used for assessing PA and SB was feasible for use amongst secondary school pupils. In line with previous research, there was no consensus as to which SMS frequency and timing was preferred (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). However, most participants wanted to receive SMS outside of school hours and timing was mentioned to be important for behaviour change and interaction with two-way messaging. For SMS content, participants echoed existing findings (Thompson *et al.*, 2016) and felt a variety of tips and advice on how to improve PA and SB was needed, with generic content not deemed as useful. Study 2 also showed that there was no consensus as to which theoretical framework or BCT was most useful. Some participants felt the SMS motivated them to be more active, whereas others mentioned the advice or information provided was not encouraging, relevant, or achievable. Moreover, it was evident that some participants did not have a perceived desire or need to change their behaviours.

The qualitative evidence from Study 2 provided crucial guidance for the development of future interventions (e.g. Study 4) and revealed important factors potentially influencing intervention effectiveness. Overall, the lack of consensus among participants revealed that there is a need to explore the most appropriate and efficient options for tailored SMS timing and frequency to enhance engagement and effectiveness (Thompson *et al.*, 2016; Van Dyck *et al.*, 2019). This also includes enhancing the use and timing of interactive SMS as they are expected to be important contributors for intervention engagement and successful behaviour change (Donkin *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, findings revealed that SMS content should focus on a variety of information and advice for changing PA and SB, with research needed to explore options for tailoring content effectively. This guidance echoes previous calls (Fjeldsoe,

Marshall and Miller, 2009; Militello, Kelly and Melnyk, 2012; Head *et al.*, 2013; Ranney *et al.*, 2014) as to the importance of personalising intervention content depending on the respective target audience. Whilst the present findings did not allow specific conclusions for user preferences regarding theory, evidence indicated that using BCTs such as feedback, instructions and goal setting can be effective. Thus, future mHealth interventions are encouraged to include such techniques as well as theoretical frameworks in line with these, to explore effective intervention frameworks (Orr and King, 2015; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Importantly, future studies should also involve quantitative assessments of psychological factors, such as self-efficacy and attitudes, that were targeted, to explore potential changes as a result of the intervention and better understand behaviour change mechanisms (Buchan *et al.*, 2012; Rhodes, McEwan and Rebar, 2019). These recommendations were also addressed as part of Study 4.

7.1.3 Study 3

The aim of Study 3 was to quantitatively evaluate a 3-week pilot intervention. This cluster randomised waitlist-controlled trial provided an assessment of the feasibility as well as initial effectiveness of the intervention.

The recruitment and retention rates in this study revealed that a low-burden, short-term intervention involving only SMS is feasible for implementation among secondary school pupils. Retention in this study was high, with all participants completing the intervention and all but one providing baseline and follow-up PA and SB data. Wear-time for both accelerometer devices was high and a protocol involving simultaneous wear of two devices was deemed feasible among this population. For intervention efficacy, findings revealed no significant differences in post-intervention PA and SB between the intervention and waitlist-controlled group.

Study 3 provided important evidence on feasible SMS interventions, demonstrating that a PA and SB intervention using SMS as the sole intervention component are appropriate for use

among adolescents. It revealed that using two accelerometer devices simultaneously allows for moderate to high wear-time compliance, which is encouraging for future research. Considering devices such as the ActiGraph GT3X+ and activPAL4 have been validated specifically for adolescent PA and SB (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012; Migueles *et al.*, 2017), this study underlines the importance of future research using this protocol. Moreover, Study 3 reiterates that SMS reminders (Belton *et al.*, 2013) or other strategies to increase wear-time, particularly on weekends, should continue to be explored. In addition, the slight increases in PA-related outcomes among the intervention group, compared to decreases in the waitlist-control group, are promising. These findings indicate that exploring more effective strategies for delivery and content seems warranted.

Several participants in Study 2 had indicated that they did not feel a need to change behaviours, which may have influenced intervention effectiveness. Therefore, future research should focus on participant groups in need of PA and SB change due to low activity levels and high sitting times. Lastly, Study 3 contributes to the scarce evidence base on effective strategies for interactivity within mHealth interventions (Tong and Laranjo, 2018) and demonstrates free answer formats and other social support tools may be needed to enhance intervention engagement and efficacy.

7.1.4 Study 4

The primary aims of this one-group, mixed methods study were to assess the feasibility, fidelity, and acceptability of an 8-week SMS intervention among secondary school pupils. The secondary aim was to assess initial efficacy of the intervention in terms of PA, SB, healthy eating, and psychological outcomes targeted by the intervention. Study 4 aimed to address the recommendations made by Study 1, 2, and 3, by designing an SMS intervention based on theory and appropriate BCTs, using validated measures for PA and SB, incorporating two-way messaging, tailoring SMS content more successfully to the target population, providing a variety of frequencies and timings as well as incorporating advice on healthy eating.

Recruitment rates for this intervention were lower compared to the shorter intervention in Study 2 and 3. Moreover, only 68% of recruited participants completed the opt-in process via SMS. Study attrition was moderate to high (62%) between baseline and follow-up. Most participants who opted-out during the intervention did so during the last week. These late drop-outs have been speculated to be partly due to the participants' unwillingness to wear accelerometers for a second time, as suggested by anecdotal evidence. Fidelity was moderate, with 86-100% of participants reading most or all messages and between 30-70% using interactive, two-way messaging. There was no consensus as to which SMS content, theory, or BCT was preferred. Most participants found SMS during after school hours to be useful, with three SMS per week being most popular. Accelerometer data showed small increases in MVPA and AA, with slight increases in sitting time. Participants perceived schoolwork and after school activities to be barriers for behaviour change. Others mentioned not feeling a need to change. Healthy eating scores slightly increased post-intervention, with mixed results for psychological outcomes targeted by the SMS.

This study contributed vital findings to the evidence base of PA and SB interventions using SMS in isolation. The present evidence demonstrated that such interventions can be feasible for use among adolescents, with more research needed to explore reasons for low opt-in rates, particularly when using SMS-based replies. Study 4 provides evidence that single opt-in processes or free-text replies should be used where possible as this is expected to enhance compliance with opt-in processes. The present findings reiterate the call for exploring strategies for effective engagement (Yardley *et al.*, 2016), such as by enhancing interactivity within two-way messaging protocols as this is expected to enhance behaviour change (Donkin *et al.*, 2011). More research is needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of effective, population-specific strategies for interactivity within SMS interventions.

To increase compliance with accelerometer wear-time criteria in future studies, Study 4 underlines the importance of considering smaller, watch-like devices (e.g. GENEActiv) as

participants perceived ActiGraph GT3X+ devices to be uncomfortable to wear. Using more comfortable devices and exploring strategies for increasing wear-time compliance, such as peer support (McCann *et al.*, 2016) or monetary incentives (Sirard and Slater, 2009; McCann *et al.*, 2016) may be needed to achieve higher compliance, particularly among youth.

Varying participant preferences, baseline activity levels as well as limited initial efficacy indicate that despite age-appropriate and timetable-based adaptations to the intervention, more research is needed to explore most effective SMS content and delivery. Considering the lack of clear conclusions as to which theories or BCTs are most effective within SMS interventions, Study 4 contributed vital insights. It was evident that psychological factors targeted by theory-based SMS did not consistently improve following the intervention, which calls for future interventions to apply theory more comprehensively (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015) and increase the number of SMS focusing on individual outcomes. For SMS delivery, Study 4 provided indications for focusing on out of school hours and targeting prolonged periods of sitting, such as during evenings (Arundell *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, it is recommended that a variety of times is used, or timing is tailored individually according to schedules and preferences. Evidence from Study 4 also warrants future research focusing on long-term interventions with the aim for long-term, maintained behaviour change. Further, it will be important to provide a bigger focus on insufficiently active participants or those with a perceived need or desire to change activity behaviours.

7.2 Strengths

The research presented in this thesis had several strengths. Firstly, the studies presented in Chapter 5 and 6 followed recommendations outlined within the MRC framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions (Craig *et al.*, 2008). This entailed conducting a systematic review before pilot and feasibility research based on theory and findings from previous research, to inform the development of larger scale efficacy trials.

Secondly, the research also comprehensively focused on using theory to guide the development of intervention messages. The systematic review presented in Chapter 4 (Study 1) provided an overview of frequently used theories, which informed the frameworks subsequent intervention studies (see Chapter 5 & 6) included. In addition to using TPB, TTM, and SCT to inform intervention messages, several BCTs were applied. These were selected due to their association with the theoretical frameworks as well as their evidence-based effectiveness for supporting PA and SB change among adolescents. Despite no comprehensive application of a single theory, combining these frameworks and incorporating related BCTs was expected to elicit positive effects on behaviour change and participant experiences. The evidence presented in Study 2, 3, and 4 provides guidance as to preferred BCTs for adolescents, which will be of use within future research.

Another strength is the continuous mixed methods approach as recommended by the MRC (Craig *et al.*, 2008). Collecting qualitative data through focus group discussions aimed to enhance and compliment quantitative feasibility and efficacy data. Considering Study 2, 3, and 4 were designed as pilot studies, not large scale RCTs, qualitative data was particularly important. It allowed for a more comprehensive, in-depth understanding of participant preferences and experiences prior to larger scale research. Participant views are particularly important during the intervention development stage (Larsson *et al.*, 2018), meaning the evidence presented in this thesis is crucial for informing future research and enabling more effective interventions.

Finally, whilst the use of qualitative data was essential for the purposes of Study 2 and 4, the research also focused on the use of validated measures for collecting quantitative efficacy data. For assessing PA and SB, previous research often employed self-report tools despite a continued call for using device-based measures when assessing effectiveness in terms of frequency, intensity, and volume of these behaviours. The present research involved the simultaneous use of ActiGraph GT3X+ and activPAL4 devices, which is rare in the literature. Findings from Study 2 and 3 indicated it can be feasible for use among secondary school

pupils although findings from Study 4 suggest that alternative devices or additional strategies may be needed to improve compliance for repeat deployments. Given these findings, it seems prudent that future work explores the acceptability of wearing both ActiGraph GT3X+ and activPAL4 devices before both devices are used in future studies.

7.3 Limitations

There were some limitations to the research presented in this thesis. Overall, sample sizes within Study 3 and 4 were small. Whilst the testing of feasibility allows for smaller sample sizes compared to efficacy trials, larger samples would have allowed for a more comprehensive view of participant preferences as well as additional efficacy data. Moreover, poor recruitment rates in Study 4 did not allow for a control group to be added. Whilst the data presented in Chapter 6 nonetheless informs future intervention development and provides insights into feasibility, fidelity, acceptability, and initial effectiveness of the intervention, a control group would have enhanced methodological rigour. It is expected that the use of more user-friendly, acceptable accelerometer devices and a modification of the opt-in process, that is, using single opt-ins, will increase recruitment rates within a future trial.

Secondly, throughout Study 2 to 4, recruitment focused on secondary school pupils with no specific targeting of those currently inactive or insufficiently active. It is evident that many participants did not perceive a desire or need to change behaviours, which may have influenced intervention effectiveness. Prior to recruitment for Study 4, there was an attempt to involve clinical populations. The aim was to involve overweight and obese adolescents within the NHS community dietetics pathway, however low numbers of eligible patients over several months did not allow for this population to be included in the present research. Moreover, the present research did not specifically involve participants from lower socio-economic backgrounds, despite evidence that health inequalities have been increasing over recent years (Shackleton, Hale and Viner 2016). Research has shown that young adolescents with lower socio-economic status are at higher risk of negative health outcomes,

including overweight (Shackleton, Hale and Viner 2016; Vallejo-Torres *et al.*, 2014) and those of lower socio-economic status show less engagement with paediatric primary healthcare provisions (Cox *et al.*, 2012). Thus, it is important to remain cautious with conclusions encouraging the use of SMS for enhancing PA and SB among adolescents, considering a lack of research focusing on those in most need. Despite the lack of focus on those potentially more in need or more susceptible to PA and SB change within the present research, the findings from Study 1 to 4 are vital for informing future interventions that involve clinical populations. Providing comprehensive detail in terms of the context for recruitment and data collection throughout this thesis was expected to enhance the transferability of findings to other populations and intervention settings. However, it will be important for future studies to consider recruiting participants with an increased need for behaviour change intervention as well as those unable to effectively engage with current health behaviour change interventions. In order to allow those in need of additional support or interaction with service providers to benefit from healthcare provisions, remote interventions should be offered alongside more comprehensive and resource-intensive, face-to-face interventions. Specifically, it has been found that mHealth interventions should be accompanied by other approaches to provide multi-component support (Mannocci *et al.*, 2020). It is proposed that remote, mHealth and face-to-face interventions should not be mutually exclusive in a wider healthcare setting, such as the NHS community support provision.

Lastly, the present interventions involved SMS over the course of three (Study 2 & 3) and eight weeks (Study 4). Whilst this is comparable to similar interventions, participants mentioned that a period of at least eight weeks was needed to allow sufficient time for behaviour change to occur. It is expected that a lower frequency of messages (around three per week) over a longer duration (12 weeks or more) may enhance intervention efficacy by allowing time for participants to digest information and advice provided and subtle prompts to embed within daily habits.

7.4 Recommendations for practice

The research presented in this thesis aimed to inform the development and implementation of SMS interventions within current NHS practice. The following will outline an overview of recommendations derived from the findings of Study 1 to 4, which are expected to enhance the feasibility and effectiveness of using SMS within clinical and health care pathways.

The following provides an overview of recommendations for the delivery of SMS:

- Use a variety of timings and frequencies
- Encourage behaviours during times when changes are achievable
- Send at least three SMS per week for information, support, and advice
- Send daily messages for compliance with medication or assessment protocols
- Where possible, tailor the timing and dose of SMS to individual recipients

The following provides an overview of recommendations for the content of SMS:

- Use short messages, with the main point at the start
- Formulate messages to be positive and motivational
- Tailor SMS based on current PA and SB levels
- Provide information on health benefits and instructions on how to change
- Use a variety of tips and advice, including involving family and friends
- Add SMS that prompt goal setting, self-monitoring, and provide feedback
- Use two-way messaging with free text answers to allow interactivity

In addition to the recommendations above, it may be appropriate to incorporate multiple health behaviours within interventions. Research presented in this thesis indicates that adolescents are interested in additional advice, such as healthy eating, when targeting PA and SB (Chapter 5). Incorporating multiple health behaviours may allow for a more comprehensive approach for encouraging healthy lifestyles and could interrupt the perceived monotony of focusing on individual behaviours. Research suggests that changing one

behaviour may elicit higher self-efficacy for improving other behaviours (Prochaska, Spring and Nigg, 2008). As health behaviours such as unhealthy eating and higher SB can occur simultaneously (de la Haye *et al.*, 2014) and tend to track from youth into adulthood (Telama *et al.*, 2014; Hayes *et al.*, 2019), it may be beneficial to enhance healthy lifestyle behaviours comprehensively. Considering health and clinical care pathways may work with patients requiring comprehensive health-related advice, targeting behaviours such as sleep and diet in addition to PA and SB could enhance intervention effectiveness.

Moreover, it is vital to test SMS for use within clinical pathways, to explore the interventions' ability to support successful behaviour change among patient populations. This will allow patients in need of behaviour change to benefit from such efforts and enhance the evidence base of effective strategies for implementing research into practice. It is expected that those in need of behaviour change may be able to elicit greater health benefits from such interventions, as has been shown for PA (Minton *et al.*, 2013).

Lastly, considering the low-burden, low-cost, flexible nature of remote SMS interventions, they represent a promising tool for providing behaviour change support during the current Coronavirus pandemic. Whilst mHealth and other digital tools, such as video-based health promotion consultations have been put in place (Park *et al.*, 2020), there is a perceived lack of staff knowledge and training for using such systems (Charles and Ewbank, 2020).

However, SMS interventions such as those described within this thesis are designed to be used at minimal burden to patients and clinicians and may be able to compensate for a lack of face-to-face contact. In addition, many staff are trained in existing NHS systems such as Florence and they offer a unique opportunity for clinicians and care staff to remain in contact with patients who are unable to receive advice or information face to face (Park *et al.*, 2020). It is expected that mHealth tools will increasingly be used, so implementation within clinical pathways and scientific research are crucial for developing effective interventions now and eliciting health behaviour change in the future.

7.5 Implications for future research

The individual study chapters and the content under 7.3 outline some of the limitations within the studies presented in this thesis. In the following, these will be considered to provide recommendations for future SMS intervention research.

7.5.1 Study and intervention design

The evidence regarding interventions using SMS in isolation for supporting PA and SB is scarce (Study 1). However, they present a unique opportunity to support successful behaviour change through minimal burden on participants, even when adding features such as two-way messaging. Interactivity, such as via two-way messaging, was a crucial element of the interventions presented in this thesis. There is no clear guidance on how to enhance interactivity within mHealth interventions (Tong and Laranjo, 2018) and findings from Study 2, 3, and 4 indicate that more research is needed to identify successful strategies that elicit effective engagement and support behaviour change (Yardley *et al.*, 2016). It is also evident that SMS interventions tend to use a variety of SMS timings and frequency, with no clear link how these impact efficacy (Study 1). Study 4 revealed that a variety of SMS frequencies and timings may be appropriate, however more research is warranted exploring most effective SMS delivery protocols that support behaviour change. As timing of delivery appeared to be vital for whether behaviour change was attempted or not (Study 2 to 4), it is particularly important to explore efficient strategies for personalisation. In addition to SMS delivery, content of messages may also need to be tailored depending on individual preferences, abilities, and needs. It is recognised that SMS targeting young cancer survivors (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017), adolescents with type 1 diabetes (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009) or those insufficiently active (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) may require content specific to the respective needs of these populations.

Moreover, present PA and SB interventions for adolescents that use only SMS (Sirriyeh, Lawton and Ward, 2010; Study 2 to 4) or minimal additional components such as

pedometers (Newton, Wiltshire and Elley, 2009) or apps (Mendoza *et al.*, 2017; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) tend to be of short durations. Generally, there is a lack of research assessing the long-term impact of behaviour change interventions on PA and SB (Murray *et al.*, 2017), with evidence showing SMS interventions between six and 12 months may be most effective (Armanasco *et al.*, 2017). Importantly, Study 4 provided vital evidence suggesting at least eight weeks are needed (Chapter 6), with other evidence showing 12 weeks to be acceptable (Thompson *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, considering SMS interventions appear promising for supporting successful behaviour change (Study 1 to 4), larger-scale, longer-term, high-quality studies are warranted to enhance this evidence base.

7.5.2 Recruitment and retention

As recruitment and retention rates varied considerably between Study 2, 3, and 4, it is important for future research to explore reasons for failed opt-ins or dropouts. In Study 4, it was speculated that late dropouts may be due to participants being unwilling to wear accelerometers for a second time. This is supported by anecdotal evidence from non-completers. Future interventions are encouraged to use single opt-in processes (i.e. using only consent forms) where possible to reduce no-opt-in rates. Further, when using opt-in or consent via SMS, free-text responses should be allowed to avoid technical difficulties or failed responses due to non-compliance with pre-determined answer formats.

7.5.3 Population target groups

More research focusing on insufficiently active or sedentary populations is warranted. This is particularly important as models have shown that slight increases in PA among those previously least active yield bigger effects on mortality compared to larger increases among those already active (Minton *et al.*, 2013). Throughout this thesis, intervention efficacy was limited, which is speculated to be due to the recruitment of participants already participating in PA and not perceiving a need to change. It is expected that as participants were not from highly inactive groups, even small increases in PA (Study 3 & 4) and slight decreases in

sitting time (Study 3) would not have yielded relevant health benefits. Some studies specifically targeted insufficiently active populations (Lau *et al.*, 2012; Brannon *et al.*, 2018) or those not participating in PE at school or organised sports (Lubans *et al.*, 2012), however, there is scope for research to elicit the most effective intervention components for enhancing PA levels among those currently inactive as well as those already sufficiently active. Considering higher intensity activities yield enhanced health outcomes (Poitras *et al.*, 2016; Strain *et al.*, 2020), there is benefit in promoting increased PA population-wide.

7.5.4 Use of theory and BCTs

Findings from Study 1 indicated that most SMS interventions targeting adolescent PA and SB are guided by theory (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). The current evidence base however does not allow assessing which theories or BCTs are most effective, with qualitative and quantitative research needed (McIntosh *et al.*, 2017). This has been suggested to be partly due to the frequent lack of reporting of how theory was applied within the intervention as well as theories not being applied comprehensively (Prestwich, Webb and Conner, 2015).

The research presented in Study 2, 3, and 4 involved an in-depth application and reporting of theory, with the addition of using BCTs linked to the applied theoretical frameworks. Whilst popular theories, such as the TPB, TTM, and SCT are frequently used (Ludwig *et al.*, 2018) and were employed within the present research, there is a need more studies exploring the effectiveness of these theories within mHealth interventions. It has been suggested that novel SMS interventions may require different frameworks and BCTs compared to more traditional intervention approaches (Lewis *et al.*, 2017). Popular theories such as those used within this thesis may not be appropriate for remote interventions using SMS (Riley *et al.*, 2011). However, Study 2, 3, and 4 show that popular BCTs, such as goal setting and feedback, are perceived useful, with SMS based on the TPB, self-efficacy, and the TTM able to elicit positive changes in SB self-efficacy, PA intention, PA subjective norm and PA stage of change (Study 4). These initial findings are promising, and this evidence followed the previous call for research to assess psychological factors targeted by theories applied within

the intervention (Orr and King, 2015). The evidence presented in this thesis indicates that applying psychological theories more comprehensively with an increased number of SMS targeting specific components, improvements in psychological factors such as attitude and perceived behavioural control would be strengthened. Moreover, this will allow for a better understanding of behaviour change mechanisms and which theoretical components are most effective (Orr and King, 2015; Rhodes, McEwan and Rebar, 2019).

Moreover, there is a gap in the evidence base using qualitative methods to explore adolescent preferences for different theories and BCTs. Whilst the research in this thesis supports existing evidence recommending the use of BCTs related to information on how to change, information on health benefits as well as goal setting and feedback (see Chapter 5 and 6; Michie *et al.*, 2009; Ashford, Edmunds and French, 2010; Hynynen *et al.*, 2016; Ludwig *et al.*, 2018), more research is warranted to explore best practice strategies for implementing such techniques.

7.5.5 PA and SB measurement

In terms of the measurement of PA and SB, future research should employ validated methods to enhance the quality of the evidence base on SMS interventions. The research presented in this thesis demonstrated that the simultaneous use of validated devices for PA and SB is feasible among adolescents (see Chapter 5 & 6). However, Study 4 indicated that research is needed to explore additional strategies, such as using incentives, to increase adherence to and compliance with repeated accelerometer deployments. Considering the incidental nature of PA and SB among youth (Fairclough and Noonan, 2020), device-based measures may reflect such behaviours more accurately compared to self-report tools. Therefore, if volume, intensity, and frequency of behaviours are of interest, device-based measures should be used for PA and SB (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011; Lynch *et al.*, 2019). However, when activity context and domain are in question, self-report measures, such as questionnaires, should be employed (Loprinzi and Cardinal, 2011) whilst continuing to explore the development of more valid and reliable self-report tools (Hidding *et al.*, 2018).

As indicated within Study 4, participants may find certain accelerometers uncomfortable to wear. Future research should, despite their validity and wide-spread use for measuring adolescent PA and SB (Dowd, Harrington and Donnelly, 2012; Migueles *et al.*, 2017), consider using alternative, watch like devices to enhance compliance and aid initial study recruitment. Research has shown that participants are willing to wear smaller devices such as the GENEActiv repeatedly (Scott *et al.*, 2017). This is crucial considering in the present research, compliance for wrist worn ActiGraph GT3X+ devices was lower at follow-up compared to baseline, with participants mentioning not being willing to wear the device a second time (Study 4) or finding it too big or uncomfortable (Study 2). The smaller design of GENEActiv accelerometers may be particularly appealing for adolescents, who have shown to be susceptible to non-compliance if appearance is deemed unsuitable (Kirby *et al.*, 2012; Study 4). In addition, more qualitative research with different population groups is needed to explore effective strategies for increasing compliance, such as by using peer support, monetary incentives, or SMS reminders (Sirard and Slater, 2009; McCann *et al.*, 2016). It has been shown that SMS reminders can increase compliance also in medical and health care environments (Belton *et al.*, 2013), underlining the importance of continuing to build the evidence base of using SMS interventions and reminders for enhancing clinical care.

In conclusion, the evidence presented in this thesis indicates that SMS interventions represent a promising, feasible tool for promoting behaviour change among adolescents. Whilst there is a lack of evidence confirming the use of SMS alone as an effective way to increase PA and reduce SB, the present findings indicate that longer-term, large scale studies are warranted. It is recommended that research focuses on exploring effective strategies for tailoring content, uses validated, acceptable device-based measures for PA and SB, explores the effectiveness of theories and BCTs within interventions and targets adolescents in need of behaviour change, such as those insufficiently active. It is expected that low burden mHealth interventions will continue to be used within health care systems across the globe. To ensure effective use within clinical or health care practice, SMS

interventions should ensure content is tailored to individual preferences and abilities, there is a focus on multiple health behaviours where appropriate, options for free text responses within two-way messaging are provided, and there is an increased involvement of and testing with clinical populations such as obese adolescents at risk of diabetes or those with other conditions typically entailing limited PA.

Chapter 8

Reflective commentary

The challenges and lessons learnt from conducting intervention research in secondary schools

As for many PhD students working on applied research in real-world settings, some elements of my work did not go according to plan. Reflecting upon my experiences, there are many lessons I have learned which I will take forward in my development as a researcher. I hope through this reflective commentary readers are able to find some context for the previous content presented in this thesis and the valuable lessons learnt.

Reflections on developing and implementing an intervention in collaboration with the NHS and within a local council context

The PhD studentship funding my research was set up in collaboration with NHS Lanarkshire (NHSL). The aim of the PhD was to design and conduct a series of studies to explore the feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of using the NHS's text-messaging delivery system, Florence, to promote PA among adolescents. Using Florence for this purpose was novel and my research findings were to influence the development of an SMS intervention used within NHS community dietetics pathways for adolescents treated for overweight and obesity or those at risk of Type 2 Diabetes. This PhD programme of work particularly suited my goals to work on research informing practice.

From the beginning, I set out a clear strategy to determine which elements of my research would involve members of staff from the NHS Child Healthy Weight and Telehealth units. It was expected that their involvement would increase intervention effectiveness and feasibility within the desired context. Using stakeholder expertise from NHS staff was a key element during intervention development and implementation (O'Cathain *et al.*, 2019; Turner *et al.*, 2019). The NHSL Child Healthy Weight unit offered to support the recruitment of schools and the Telehealth team was to facilitate the use of Florence. As Florence is a closed-loop

software, only Telehealth staff would be able to input SMS, however I was able to access a portal allowing me to add participant information and start and stop SMS protocols.

Study 2 and 3: Evaluation of a 3-week text-messaging intervention targeting adolescent physical activity and sedentary behaviour

The collaboration with Telehealth staff throughout Study 2 and 3 involved consistent communication between myself and NHSL as well as a clear strategy for the required timeline and support. I was able to design my studies in line with NHS Lanarkshire's Florence guidelines and data protection regulations. I successfully completed this research and enjoyed its applied nature as the aim was to use my findings to inform NHS practice.

Reflecting upon working with the NHS Telehealth team, this was an interesting, eye-opening experience, which developed my skills and expertise in working with public sector partners in a research context. Conducting my work within NHS regulations was complex but I was able to complete the required paperwork and training for using Florence. I feel it is a significant achievement for myself as an early career researcher to have built an effective working relationship with NHSL and completed complex studies within the required timeframe.

To successfully complete this research, it was vital for me to understand NHS priorities and work streams as well as appreciating their internal processes for obtaining approvals. An awareness of my collaborators' needs and expectations as well as excellent communication and interpersonal skills allowed me to build a positive rapport and enabled me to receive the support that was needed. These studies also enhanced my skills in resource and project management and built the foundations for future collaborations with NHSL.

Study 4: A mixed methods feasibility study of an 8-week text-messaging intervention targeting adolescent physical activity and sedentary behaviour

Study 4 was also designed and conducted in collaboration with NHSL and Telehealth staff agreed to facilitate Florence once again. As Study 2 showed participants were interested in receiving healthy eating advice, NHSL community dietitians were approached. Working with

NHS dieticians during intervention development was straight-forward, enjoyable, and ensured SMS content was in line with current NHS practice. I was pleased with my ability to work efficiently within a new partnership and believe these skills will be vital for future collaborations in my professional career.

It was agreed with the NHSL Telehealth team that Florence would be available for my research in April. However, a shift in the Telehealth team's workload occurred and the team was now unable to support my use of Florence. One member of staff negotiated to remain on the project, however this still impacted on my ability to provide schools with accurate information regarding the timeline of our work and NHS involvement. Throughout my work, I strive to have fixed schedules as this enables me to work in an efficient manner, which I felt unable to do during this time. As a researcher, I found it difficult to align my workload and schedule with the priorities of NHSL and potentially collaborating schools. Looking back on this experience, I believe I could have outlined a comprehensive plan for alternative timelines from the start and discussions with NHSL could have been held on a more definite basis with less room for changes. I also learned that conducting interdisciplinary research in real world settings requires being flexible with regards to study designs. It has become evident that this is a crucial skill for successfully conducting such work without becoming overwhelmed and frustrated with any changes.

The intervention designed as part of Study 4 involved a longer time frame, with 38 intervention SMS delivered over eight weeks. However, when the SMS protocol was sent to the Telehealth team, a cost issue with regards to the number of SMS was raised. Whilst this cost issue could be resolved due to the availability of additional funds within NHSL, it caused significant uncertainty and stress for myself. I was unable to work to the predetermined timeline and I felt this challenge was raised long after the intervention had been designed and a longer duration had been communicated to NHSL. As a researcher, I feel I could have considered and discussed key elements such as cost earlier in the process. Doing so could

have prevented uncertainty and frustration and would have enabled me to design my intervention in a way that complied with available NHSL funds.

Following a second round of recruitment, Study 4 was ready to commence. However, shortly after, NHSL team member who negotiated to support my work was now unable to input the SMS protocol into Florence due to competing workstreams. This had a significant impact on my communication with schools and the continuous delays and workload shifts resulted in uncertainty of how and when I would be able to complete my work. During this time, clear, direct communication was important for maintaining a positive rapport with the recruited schools and NHSL staff. Despite consistent interactions between schools, NHSL and I, the challenge of being unable to use Florence had a significant impact on my confidence as a researcher and my outlook on completing this study. I felt unable to influence the issues that arose and found it difficult to accept that my project could not be completed as planned. I have learned from this experience that whilst it is possible to have contingency plans for certain issues, it is impossible to predict everything that could change along the way. In the future, it will be important for me to accept any issues quickly and focus on finding solutions. Moreover, I have learned that changes to the plan do not make my work less meaningful.

To ensure I was able to complete my work within the desired time frame, we aimed to identify an alternative SMS delivery service, which mimicked Florence's functions. The process of identifying Esendex as an alternative system was complex and time consuming, particularly as ethics approval had to be sought once again. It was important that participant replies were free of charge and there had to be a specific type of answer format for two-way messaging. Moreover, the involvement of NHSL appeared to be a key element of schools' interests in taking part in my work. Despite this, and thanks to my positive rapport with teachers, we were able to continue working with the schools that were initially recruited. This period was challenging, however I gained a deeper understanding of ethical guidelines and General Data Protection Regulations to ensure Esendex complied with such standards.

At the end of August, South Lanarkshire Council informed us that approval from their ethics team had to be sought prior to conducting our research. At this stage, we also contacted North Lanarkshire council to ensure we were following their procedures for conducting research in schools. Approval by South Lanarkshire council was granted within 10 days, however following 11 weeks of communication with North Lanarkshire Council, they decided not to grant approval for conducting our work. This was due to concerns around data collection and intervention delivery, which could not be resolved. Whilst I reassured the Council we were following data protection procedures and the university ethics committee had approved my work, the Council remained firm on its disapproval. Whilst council approvals were never requested in previous research projects conducted within my institute, I could have been more intuitive during planning to ensure all relevant approvals were sought in good time. As a researcher, it is vital for me to appreciate which guidelines need to be followed, and considering the university granted approval, I was disappointed to not receive approval from North Lanarkshire Council. I feel that for my future work, it will be important for me to have a greater appreciation for different levels of awareness and understanding of my area of research when working with non-academic partners. Overall, this period was incredibly demanding on me as the main point of contact for councils and schools and it was my duty to ensure guidelines of external organisations were followed. These unexpected obstacles challenged my communication and organisational skills as multiple timelines and workflows occurred simultaneously.

The difficulties experienced with obtaining approval from North Lanarkshire council resulted in acute time pressure. As a result, I aimed to involve two classes from the first school we recruited, each of which would represent an intervention and a control group. However, due to low recruitment rates from this school (see Chapter 6), I was unable to recruit a control group for this study. Moreover, the rising prevalence of Coronavirus during the first few months of 2020 further diminished any options for recruiting an additional school or collecting more data. Due to the lockdown measures and the foreseeable challenges for any

intervention research to continue, it became apparent that my work was to continue with no available control group. The challenges I encountered during my work reiterate the importance of conducting research in an efficient manner and accounting for circumstances outwith the researcher's control.

Reflections on conducting intervention research in local secondary schools

Recruitment

For Study 2 and 3, an existing contact to the PE department within a local secondary school was used as a gateway for recruitment. Due to a very positive rapport, the recruitment process in this school was straightforward and completed in a timely manner. The buy-in from the whole PE department was crucial for ensuring pupils and their parents were willing to take part in the research and allowed us to achieve the required sample size.

For Study 4, new links to local schools had to be built. The flowchart in Figure 9 provides an overview of the recruitment process for this study. Due to the lack of response during step 1, step 2 involved contacting the respective PE department heads and Active Schools coordinators in addition to head teachers. Active Schools is a Scotland-wide initiative to promote after school sports participation among school pupils and I identified its local coordinators to be potentially effective gateways to receive a buy-in that would enhance the schools' interest in my work. Further, I included the heads of PE in as I saw an opportunity to use their own focus on providing opportunities for sport participation to facilitate the schools' interest in taking part in my study. Throughout, I included information about how the research would benefit the respective schools' strategy for supporting healthy lifestyles, by potentially contributing to increased numbers in PE and helping to close attainment gaps between those from more deprived and more affluent areas. It appears this may have also contributed to enhancing the schools' perception of the importance of my work and could have influenced their interest for taking part. Overall, I was pleased that a revision to my recruitment strategy resulted in much higher response rates.

Figure 9. Flowchart of the recruitment process for Study 4

Reflecting upon my interactions with schools during this phase, it is evident that members of staff I met with were keen to get involved. Whilst most of these links then resulted in recruitment, others did not, with some schools ceasing contact. Considering I was unable to use any financial incentives to encourage interest and participation, my work was heavily reliant on school staff seeing value in and endorsing our work. Consistent communication was crucial to ensure schools were kept up to date with my research process and positive relationships could be maintained even when changes to the proposed timeline occurred.

Communication and co-operation

One of the main reflections taken from my PhD is that consistent and clear communication with schools is key for successful co-operations. Whilst schools were disappointed not to be able to participate in my study due to timetabling or approval issues, there was a general understanding that this was due to issues outwith my control. It is encouraging that schools I was unable to include in my research were willing to remain on my department's records for future research projects.

Lessons learned

There have been several lessons I have learned from my experience of working with the NHS, local councils, and schools. I believe the following elements are vital for the successful completion of a PhD programme of work involving members of staff from such organisations.

1. COMMUNICATION

Consistent and clear communication is key to building and maintaining positive working relationships with collaborators.

2. UNDERSTANDING

A comprehensive understanding of collaborating partners' work streams, priorities, and timelines is crucial for building a rapport and ensuring their duties align with the needs and aims of the research.

3. AWARENESS

Awareness and knowledge of procedures and rules that need to be followed to complete research within the guidelines of partnering organisations is vital.

4. CLARITY

Research aims need to be clear to stakeholders as well as how the research will benefit their organisation.

5. FLEXIBILITY

Some flexibility needs to be kept throughout the study process to allow for changes in priorities, timelines and research aims because of shifts in availability of staff and resources.

To conclude, conducting intervention research in secondary schools in collaboration with the NHS is complex and requires excellent interpersonal and communication skills. It is evident that multiple, overlapping timelines and workstreams are likely to occur, with efficient organisation important for successfully completing research within the required time frame. Further, researchers ought to be flexible and adaptable with regards to study designs and timelines to ensure projects can be completed successfully whilst mitigating any frustrations as a result of changing schedules and goalposts. During recruitment, positive buy in from teachers, pupils, and parents can be achieved by providing a clear link to the schools' health and wellbeing strategy, particularly if financial incentives are unavailable. Conducting research within the complex network of schools, the NHS, and local councils poses many challenges. Yet, the findings from such research are vital for the successful implementation and evaluation of current public health efforts within applied settings.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Participant information sheet for Study 2 & 3

Participant information sheet Research project

Text-messaging intervention to improve physical activity and sedentary behaviour in adolescents:
A pilot study exploring feasibility and effectiveness

We are looking for adolescents to take part in a research project around text messages and being active. Maybe you would like to take part?

Please read the following information and contact me, Kim Ludwig if you have any questions!

What is this project about?

We are currently undertaking research around how text messages can be used to encourage adolescents in Scotland to be more active and to sit less. With this project, we want to find out what adolescents think of our text-messaging program. We also want to know if it helps and motivates you to do more physical activity and spend less time sitting down. By participating in this project, you can be part of a group of adolescents whom we will ask for their opinion of the text-messaging program. Your opinion will influence how we create a text-messaging program that will be used in future studies.

What will you be doing if you decide to take part?

I will give you a small device called an accelerometer, which you will wear on your wrist and measures your activity levels. Another monitor will be attached to your thigh. We will do this at school and other participants will be given this at the same time.

After 1 week, I will come back and collect the devices. You will also answer some questions about your age, gender and taking part in P.E. and sports.

During the 3 weeks after this, we will send you text messages about physical activity and sitting time.

After 3 weeks, I will meet you again at your school and you will once again be given an accelerometer and monitor for your thigh. You and other participants will also take part in a focus group discussion. This means we will sit around a table and I will ask you some questions about the text messages you got sent.

After one week, I will come back and collect the devices.
This will be the end of your participation in this project!

Do you have to take part?

No, this is completely voluntary! If you decide to take part but change your mind, you can drop out at any point. You also don't need to tell anyone why and there will be no negative consequences.

What are the benefits of taking part?

You will have the chance to take part in a program that could help you to be more active and sit less. This can have benefits for your health and help you feel better, concentrate better at school and have more energy.

What are the risks of taking part?

We believe there are no risks of taking part in this project.

What to do next?

If you wish to take part in this study, you and your parent/guardian will be asked to sign an informed consent form. If you do not want to take part, then there is nothing else you need to do. Thank you for your time!

Thank you very much for reading about our project and maybe even taking part!

Personal details withheld.

Kim Ludwig

Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 2. Florence information sheet for Study 2 & 3

Information sheet

Florence text messaging system

Our research project involves using the text-messaging system Florence, which is widely used by the NHS. This requires you to provide the following personal details:

- Your name
- Your mobile phone number
- Your CHI number (Community Health Index; made up of date of birth and gender)

Given the recent issues in the news regarding personal data, we thought you would like to know what happens with your personal data. Please find below the key information related to the legal framework of Florence. Should you wish to find out more, please visit their website or get in touch with me, Kim Ludwig [REDACTED] if you have any questions!

<https://www.getflorence.co.uk/legals/>

Who has access to my personal data?

Participant data is collected and stored by the computer servers that run Florence. This information can be accessed by clinicians, such as your GP, who are attached to your data. NHS administration teams and Mediaburst (the company behind Florence) can also access your data in case there are any technical issues with Florence.

It is part of NHS Lanarkshire's policy to share data with other health authorities if requested. Don't worry however as appropriate measures are in place to prevent unauthorised access and processing of your data, or accidental loss or damage to your data. Florence is an opt-in and opt-out system so you won't receive any messages if you don't specifically sign up and you can stop receiving messages at any point.

How will my data be stored?

Data and records are stored securely to avoid misuse or loss. Any data file or record that contains personal data is considered as confidential. All databases are password protected and no personal data is kept on any laptop or other removable drive. Your data will be stored securely for a maximum of 5 years on Florence. After 5 years, your data is disposed of to ensure the data does not fall into the hands of unauthorised personnel.

Rest assured, your personal data will not be passed onto companies for marketing purposes.

Thank you for taking part in our research!

Appendix 3. Informed consent form for parents, caregivers/guardians for Study 2 & 3

School of Science & Sport

Informed consent form
Research participation

Text-messaging intervention to improve physical activity and sedentary behaviour in adolescents: A pilot study exploring feasibility and effectiveness

I, _____ (Name) agree to my child participating in this study. I have understood the following:

The participation in this study is voluntary and my child is able to stop taking part at any stage without any consequences and informing anyone of reasons.

I have been informed that all information and data that they give will be kept safe and their identity will be made anonymous.

I agree to the focus group discussions being audio recorded.

The data my child gives will be retained for a possible publication or presentation of this project.

I can contact the researcher should my child or I have any concerns or questions.

I have read the information sheet and understand all given information.

Signature (Parent/guardian): _____ Date: _____

Signature (Researcher): _____ Date: _____

Appendix 4. Informed consent form for pupils for Study 2 & 3

School of Science & Sport

Informed consent form
Research participation

Text-messaging intervention to improve physical activity and sedentary behaviour in adolescents: A pilot study exploring feasibility and effectiveness

I, _____ (Name) agree to participate in this study. I have understood the following:

(Please tick)

My participation in this study is voluntary and I am able to stop taking part at any stage without any consequences and informing anyone of reasons.

I have been informed that all information and data that I give will be kept safe and my identity will be made anonymous.

I agree to the focus group discussions being audio recorded.

The data I gave will be retained for a possible publication or presentation of this project.

I can contact the researcher should I have any concerns or questions.

I have read the information sheet and understand all given information.

Signature (Participant): _____ Date: _____

Signature (Researcher): _____ Date: _____

Appendix 5. Use of Florence information sheet for Study 2 & 3

Using Flo as part of the UWS Research Project

You have agreed to use Florence as part of your involvement in this Research Project. You will be sent a text invite to opt in to the Flo text messaging service – just reply “yes” to confirm you wish to participate.

Please remember that this is an automated service and no-one will be looking at your readings every day. If you feel unwell, you should seek medical advice as normal; you may contact NHS24, your local pharmacy or your GP.

Florence will send you a variety of messages over the course of the research project. These messages are free to you and have been prepaid by NHS Lanarkshire***

Some messages from Flo are hints or tips or reminders and require no response from you at all.

e.g. Please remember to wear your wrist and thigh monitor every day, all day! Only take the wrist monitor off in the shower or bath or for swimming. Thank you! Flo.

Some messages from Flo will require you to text a response:

e.g. We hope the programme is helping you to be more active at school and at home. Have you been active for 1 hour yet today? Reply #1 for yes #2 for no #3 for not sure

To reply: Text # followed by the number e.g. #2 (please don't put in anything else) Flo will only understand the message if you put the # before the number.

If you want to stop all messages, text STOP to Flo, but if you want a short break from receiving messages, text 'AWAY' and then 'HOME' when you want to start again.

Florence communicates by text messages to and from your mobile phone. It will work with any mobile phone or network able to send and receive text messages. All texts to and from Florence are free to you (even if your mobile phone says that you will be charged). Florence runs on a free to text short code, 64711. There is a web site to check this out independently:
www.phonepayplus.org.uk

*****If you are a PlusNet customer you may not be able to reply to 64711. Instead you can reply to 07860033066. The texts to you from Florence will still be sent from 64711 but you will need to send your replies to 07860033066. These replies will come out of your text bundle. You will only be asked to reply to two texts.**

Appendix 6. Participant information sheet for Study 4

Participant information sheet Research project

We are looking for adolescents to take part in a research project around text messages and healthy lifestyles. Maybe you would like to take part?

Please read the following information and contact me, Kim Ludwig, if you have any questions!

What is this project about?

We are currently undertaking research around how text messages can be used to encourage adolescents in Scotland to be more active, to sit less and be healthier. With this project, we want to find out what adolescents think of our text-messaging program. We also want to know if it helps and motivates you to do more physical activity and spend less time sitting down. By participating in this project, you can be part of a group of adolescents whom we will ask for their opinion of the text-messaging program. Your opinion will influence how we create a text-messaging program that could be used by the NHS in Lanarkshire.

What will you be doing if you decide to take part?

I will give you a small device called an accelerometer, which you will wear on your wrist and measures your activity levels. Another monitor will be attached to your thigh. We will do this at school and other participants will be given this at the same time.

After 8 days, I will come back and collect the devices. You will also fill in some questionnaires asking about things like your age, how often you take part in sport or what you think about being active and healthy.

Then, for 8 weeks, we will send you text messages via Esendex® onto your mobile phone about being active and healthy. Some messages ask you to reply.

After these 8 weeks, you will once again wear the two monitors on your wrist and thigh for 8 days and complete some questionnaires.

Do you have to take part?

No, this is completely voluntary! If you decide to take part but change your mind, you can drop out at any point. You also don't need to tell anyone why and there will be no negative consequences.

If you no longer want to take part, you can tell me, Kim Ludwig, at any stage or simply text STOP as a reply to any text messages. This will make sure you are no longer receiving our messages and you no longer need to provide any measurements.

At any stage of this program, please talk to your parent/guardian or your teacher if you have any issues or concerns. You can also get in touch with your GP if you feel you need additional support.

What are the benefits of taking part?

You will have the chance to take part in a program that could help you to be more active and sit less. This can have benefits for your health and help you feel better, concentrate better at school and have more energy.

What are the risks of taking part?

When you change the tape for the thigh monitors, you may feel slight discomfort. This is similar to removing a plaster and is not painful.

What to do next?

If you wish to take part in this study, you and your parent/guardian will be asked to sign an informed consent form. If you do not want to take part, then there is nothing else you need to do. Thank you for your time!

Thank you very much for reading about our project and maybe even taking part!

Kim Ludwig

Email:

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 7. Parent/guardian information sheet for Study 4

Parent/Guardian information sheet Research project

We are looking for adolescents to take part in a research project around text messages and healthy lifestyles. Maybe your child would like to take part?

Please read the following information and contact me, Kim Ludwig, if you have any questions!

What is this project about?

We are currently undertaking research around how text messages can be used to encourage adolescents in Scotland to be more active, to sit less and be healthier. With this project, we want to find out what adolescents think of our text-messaging program. We also want to know if it helps and motivates you to do more physical activity and spend less time sitting down. By participating in this project, your child can be part of a group of adolescents whom we will ask for their opinion of the text-messaging program. Their opinion will influence how we create a text-messaging program that could be used by the NHS in Lanarkshire.

What will your child be doing if they decide to take part?

I will give your child a small device called an accelerometer, which they will wear on their wrist and measures activity levels. Another monitor will be attached to the thigh. We will do this at school and other participants will be given this at the same time.

After 8 days, I will come back and collect the devices. Your child will also fill in some questionnaires asking about things like age, sport/P.E. participation or what your child thinks about being active and healthy.

Then, for 8 weeks, we will send your child text messages via Esendex® onto their mobile phone about being active and healthy. Some messages ask your child to reply. These replies are free of charge.

After these 8 weeks, your child will once again wear the two monitors on their wrist and thigh for 8 days and complete some questionnaires.

Does your child have to take part?

No, this is completely voluntary! If your child decides to take part but changes their mind, they can drop out at any point. They also don't need to tell anyone why and there will be no negative consequences.

If your child no longer wants to take part, they can tell me, Kim Ludwig, at any stage or simply text STOP as a reply to any text message. This will make sure they are no longer receiving our messages and they no longer need to provide any measurements.

At any stage of this program, your child is advised to talk to you or their teacher if they have any issues or concerns. They can also get in touch with their GP if they feel they need additional support.

What are the benefits of taking part?

Your child will have the chance to take part in a program that could help them to be more active and sit less. This can have benefits for their health and help them feel better, concentrate better at school and have more energy.

What are the risks of taking part?

When your child changes the tape for the thigh monitors, they may feel slight discomfort. This is similar to removing a plaster and is not painful.

What to do next?

If your child wishes to take part in this study, you and your child will be asked to sign an informed consent form. If your child does not want to take part, then there is nothing else you need to do. Thank you for your time!

Thank you very much for reading about our project and maybe even taking part!

Personal details withheld.

Kim Ludwig

Email

Appendix 8. Esendex information sheet for Study 4

Information Sheet Esendex® Text-Messaging System

Our research project involves using the text-messaging system Esendex®, which is a UK-based company developing online platforms for sending and receiving text messages. It is widely used by organisations across the UK. In order for you/your child to receive text messages from us via Esendex®, we require your child to provide us with their mobile phone number.

Given the recent issues in the news regarding personal data as well as developments in data protection regulations in May 2018, we thought you would like to know what happens with your child's personal data. Please find below the key information related to the legal framework of Esendex®. Should you wish to find out more, please visit their website (<https://www.esendex.co.uk/terms-and-conditions>) or get in touch with me, Kim Ludwig, if you have any questions.

Who has access to my personal data?

Participant data is collected and stored by the computer servers that run Esendex® as well as by Microsoft Azure in the UK. Esendex® has access to your child's mobile phone number and the replies your child sends only as part of the current project to send messages, store message replies and troubleshooting. Your child's mobile number will not be used for any other purposes and won't be transmitted to any other third party. Your child's name will not be linked to their mobile phone number on Esendex®. Only the research team will know which number belongs to which participant. The UWS ethics committee has approved the guidelines we use for the use of your child's personal data and we and Esendex® are following current General Data Protection Regulation standards. Further, your child will be asked to opt-in to receiving messages from Esendex® and is able to opt-out via text message at any point during the study.

How will my data be stored?

Data and records are stored securely to avoid misuse or loss. Any data file or record that contains personal data is considered as confidential. All databases are password protected and no personal data is kept on any laptop or other removable drive. Your child's data will be stored securely for a maximum of 2 years on Esendex®. After 2 years, data is disposed of to ensure the data does not fall into the hands of unauthorised personnel.

Rest assured, your child's personal data will not be passed onto any other companies for marketing purposes.

Please get in touch if you have any questions or concerns ([REDACTED])

Thank you for taking part in our research!

Appendix 9. Informed consent form for pupils and parents/guardians for Study 4

Informed consent form
Research participation

A study to explore the effectiveness of a text-messaging intervention in promoting healthy lifestyles and health behaviour change (physical activity and sitting time)

I, _____ (Name) agree to participate in this study. I have understood the following:

(Please tick)

My participation in this study is voluntary and I am able to stop taking part at any stage without any consequences and informing anyone of reasons.

I have been informed that all information and data that I give will be kept safe and my identity will be made anonymous.

I agree to my (child's) mobile phone number being shared with Esendex® for the purpose of receiving text messages as part of the programme.

I agree to taking part in a focus group discussion and consent to this being audio recorded.

The data I gave will be retained for a possible publication or presentation of this project.

I can contact the researcher should I have any concerns or questions.

I have read the information sheet and understand all given information.

I have no underlying health conditions, which may preclude me from participating.

I have been informed that I can talk to my parent/guardian, teacher or GP if I have any issues or concerns related to the program

Signature (Participant): _____ Date: _____

Signature (Parent/guardian): _____ Date: _____

Signature (Researcher): _____ Date: _____

Please make sure you return the completed form to us. You can get in touch with the research team by sending an email to _____ if you have any questions.

Appendix 10. Use of Esendex information sheet distributed for Study 4

Using Esendex®
as part of the UWS research project

You have agreed to use Esendex® as part of your involvement in our study. Here are a few instructions to ensure you receive our messages and are able to reply when asked to. Please ask me, Kim Ludwig, if you have any questions or concerns [REDACTED].

1

We will text you from the following number: **80800**. If this number pops up on your phone, you know it is us.

2

The first message from us will ask you to opt-in to the programme. Please do so if you still want to be part of the study by replying with **KIM Yes** or **Kim Yes**. It is important that you reply using the following format to ensure your text is free, isn't taken out of your allowance and reaches us.

KIM or **Kim** + *Your reply*, for example: **KIM Yes** or **Kim Yes**

3

We will also send you other messages we want you to reply to such as:

*Hey, it's Flo! Have you been active for 1 hour every day this week? Please reply with **KIM Yes** or **KIM No**.*

Please reply with either: **KIM Yes** or **KIM No** (or **Kim Yes** or **Kim No**)

4

If you want to stop all messages and not take part in the study anymore, please reply with

KIM Stop or **Kim Stop**

to any of our messages and we will make sure you don't receive any more. You will also not take part in any other data collection.

All texts to and from Esendex® are free if you use the required format we have explained above (**KIM/Kim** plus your reply). Esendex® runs on a free to text short code, 80800. There is a website to check this out independently if you wish: <https://psauthority.org.uk/>.

Thank you very much for taking part in our study!

Appendix 11. Participant information sheet for wearing accelerometers

Device instructions

Please read these instructions on how to wear the monitors carefully and contact me, Kim Ludwig ([REDACTED]), if you have any questions!

Wrist monitor

- Wear every day
- Wear all day and night (24 hours)
- Take it off when you have a shower, a bath or are going swimming
- NOT WATERPROOF

Thigh monitor

- Wear every day
- Wear all day and night (24 hours)
- WATERPROOF
- Change the adhesive tape every 2-4 days or when it comes loose

To change the adhesive tape:

1. Remove the monitor from your thigh
2. Peel the tape off the monitor
3. DON'T REMOVE THE WHITE WATERPROOFING SLEEVE
4. Sit down on a chair
5. Position the monitor on your thigh with the figure standing up (head facing upwards)
6. Peel the backing off a new adhesive patch and place it over the monitor (Photos below)
7. Smooth out air bubbles and wrinkles to firmly secure the device

Appendix 12. COREQ checklist

No	Item	Description	Page
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity			
Personal characteristics			
1.	Interviewer/facilitator	KS interviewer, SD facilitator	101
2.	Credentials	KS MSc, SD MRes, RA PhD, DB PhD; experienced in the use of qualitative methods and PA interventions	Not reported
3.	Occupation	KS, SD PhD students in PA; RA, DB sport and exercise lecturers and PA researchers	Not reported
4.	Gender	KS, SD, RA female; DB male	Not reported
5.	Experience and training	KS, SD, RA, DB trained and experienced in using qualitative and quantitative methods for PA research with youth	Not reported
Relationship with participants			
6.	Relationship established	Multiple meetings with P.E. teacher responsible for chosen class; participants met KS & SD on day 1 of data collection	Not reported
7.	Participant knowledge of the interviewer	Participants were made aware of research being conducted as part of KS's PhD and were informed of SD's role in the focus groups	Not reported
8.	Interviewer characteristics	Participants were made aware of KS and SD's work on health promotion, the involvement of the NHS in this study and the interviewers' interest in obtaining feedback to improve the piloted intervention	Not reported
Domain 2: Study design			
Theoretical framework			
9.	Methodological orientation and theory	Thematic analysis using Braun & Clarke (2006)	101-104
Participant selection			
10.	Sampling	School selected convenience sample	52
11.	Method of approach	School approached class of potential participants face-to-face, subsequent contact with researchers also exclusively face-to-face	52
12.	Sample size	N = 24	101
13.	Non-participation	N = 1 absent at data collection due to illness	101
Setting			
14.	Setting of data collection	Multi-purpose classroom in the participants' local secondary school	101
15.	Presence of non-participants	Only researchers and participants present	101
16.	Description of sample	11 female and 13 male secondary school pupils aged between 16 and 18 (mean age 16.83 ± 0.48 years)	101
Data collection			
17.	Interview guide	Focus group guide was pilot tested on university students; KS and SD provided	101, 263-264

		prompts to obtain clarifications or encourage more elaborate answers	
18.	Repeat interviews	No repeat interviews carried out	Not reported
19.	Audio/visual recording	Audio recording of discussions on 3 devices	101
20.	Field notes	SD took field notes; Gestures or facial expressions were not recorded	101
21.	Duration	Group 1 = 41 minutes, Group 2 = 38 minutes, Group 3 = 39 minutes, Group 4 = 43 minutes	101
22.	Data saturation	Data saturation was not considered as sample size was limited by the intervention	Not reported
23.	Transcripts returned	Transcripts were not returned	Not reported
Domain 3: analysis and findings			
Data analysis			
24.	Number of data coders	N = 1 (KS), SD assisted with resolving inaudible transcript sections, RA performed quality checks	101-104
25.	Description of coding tree	No coding tree provided, however main categories, themes and example quotes shown	104-113
26.	Derivation of themes	A priori themes chosen with related data coded deductively, nodes grouped into themes and subsequent grouping into categories. Remaining comments inductively coded and grouped into new and existing themes and categories	101-104
27.	Software	NVivo 11 was used to manage transcripts and analyse data	102
28.	Participant checking	Participants were not asked to provide feedback on the findings	Not reported
Reporting			
29.	Quotations presented	Example quotes are presented in Table 6 & 7 with focus group and participant numbers provided	108-109
30.	Data and findings consistent	Researchers have attempted to be consistent with the data presented and findings with major and minor themes being presented and discussed clearly and in line with the data collected.	Not reported
31.	Clarity of major themes		
32.	Clarity of minor themes		

Appendix 13. Example intervention messages

Theme	Timing	Example message	Automated response
Instructions for increasing activity	Weekday, lunchtime	<i>You can be more active at any place and any time. Try sitting less at school, go outside in the afternoon, try a new sport or walk to the shops.</i>	
Information on health benefits	Weekday, afternoon	<i>Mental health is all over the news! Being more active makes you more confident, attentive and energetic. Definitely worth moving more and sitting less!</i>	
Encouragement	Weekend, morning	<i>Well done for completing week 1, these small changes you're making have a big effect on your health and wellbeing! Keep it up!</i>	
Interactive message with automated response – Goal setting	Weekday, morning	<i>Setting goals can help to be more active. What will you do? Sit less or be more active by walking or exercising? Reply #1 for sitting less #2 for being active</i>	<i>#1/#2: Great! Keep this in mind and we will support you to achieve your goal!</i>
Interactive message with automated response – Feedback	Weekend, afternoon	<i>We hope the program is helping you to be more active at school and at home. Have you been active for 1 hour yet today? Reply #1 for yes #2 for no #3 for not sure</i>	<i>#1: Well done! You're doing great and maybe you could be even more active tomorrow #2: Don't worry! There is still time so maybe go for a walk, do chores or exercise? #3: Any activity counts so just keep moving and try to sit less!</i>

Appendix 14. Focus group interview guide (Study 2)

Question	Example prompt
Participation in project	
Why did you decide to take part?	What were your expectations?
Your parents needed to give you permission to take part. How was that?	Was it easy or difficult? Were they happy for you to do it or did they have any questions or concerns?
Intervention process	
Over the last 3 weeks, you have been receiving text messages onto your phone. How did you find it when you got the first message asking you to opt-in? What about the other messages that asked you to send a reply?	Did you feel like you knew what to do? Why did you reply? There are a few of you that didn't reply to those messages. Why? In one message you were asked to set a goal. Those who replied mostly said their goal would be to move more rather than sit less. Why? What specifically did you think you could change?
We also sent you some SMS reminders to keep wearing the monitoring devices. What did you think of these messages?	Did you read them? Did they help you to remember to wear the devices or did you not need them?
What did you think about the length of the SMS?	Were they easy to read?
What do you think about how often you received the messages?	Do you feel like you got too many or not enough?
Preference of SMS content	
Now let's look at the messages with stickers on them. What did you think about the content of these messages? Why did you like them? Have these messages changed the way you think about physical activity?	What are your thoughts on the tips for being active and sitting less? What did you think about being given information on how being more active can improve your health and wellbeing? Were the benefits for your mental and physical health important to you? Do you feel one of them is more important than the other? Were the messages relevant to you?
How did you feel when you got these messages?	What was your immediate reaction/thoughts?
Now what about the messages you didn't like. What did you think of these messages?	Why didn't you put your sticker here? If we did the program again, are there any you would ask us to not send again?
Preference of SMS language and tone	
What do you think about the language and tone of the messages you got sent?	Was it appropriate for your age? Did you feel like we spoke to you personally?
Effectiveness	
Have these messages changed the way you behaved? What happened directly after you received those messages? Did you do anything else differently during the last 3 weeks? Has your behaviour changed in other ways?	What effect, if any, did these messages have on how active you were or how much you were sitting? Did you try to be active straight away? What about sitting less? Did you think about that? What did you think? How did you find it when you tried to follow the advice given? Did you find it easy or hard to move more and sit less? Was there anything that made it difficult to follow the advice?
Suggestions and feedback	
What suggestions do you have for improving the text messages you got sent?	If you would take part again, what would you like to see/read? What would help you (more)? Imagine you would get these messages for a few months. What type of message or information do you think would

	be most useful in helping you to be more active and sit less?
If you could come up with your own messages, what would it say?	What do you feel you would need to read in a message that would make you more active?
Is there anything else someone wants to add?	Is there anything that's important but we haven't discussed?

Appendix 15. CONSORT checklist (Study 3)

Section/Topic	No	Checklist item	Page
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a pilot or feasibility randomised trial in the title	120
	1b	Structured summary of pilot trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT abstract extension for pilot trials)	N/A
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale for future definitive trial, and reasons for randomised pilot trial	120-124
	2b	Specific objectives or research questions for pilot trial	124
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of pilot trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	124
	3b	Important changes to methods after pilot trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	N/A
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	52
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	Not reported
	4c	How participants were identified and consented	52-54
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	98-100
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined prespecified assessments or measurements to address each pilot trial objective specified in 2b, including how and when they were assessed	59-62, 125
	6b	Any changes to pilot trial assessments or measurements after the pilot trial commenced, with reasons	N/A
	6c	If applicable, prespecified criteria used to judge whether, or how, to proceed with future definitive trial	N/A
Sample size	7a	Rationale for numbers in the pilot trial	124-125
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	N/A
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	52
	8b	Type of randomisation(s); details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	52
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	N/A
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	52
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	N/A
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	N/A

Statistical methods	12	Methods used to address each pilot trial objective whether qualitative or quantitative	124-126
Results			
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were approached and/or assessed for eligibility, randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were assessed for each objective	127
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	127
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	Not reported
	14b	Why the pilot trial ended or was stopped	Not reported
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	128
Numbers analysed	16	For each objective, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis. If relevant, these numbers should be by randomised group	127-132
Outcomes and estimation	17	For each objective, results including expressions of uncertainty (such as 95% confidence interval) for any estimates. If relevant, these results should be by randomised group.	128-132
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed that could be used to inform the future definitive trial	N/A
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	N/A
	19a	If relevant, other important unintended consequences	N/A
Discussion			
Limitations	20	Pilot trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias and remaining uncertainty about feasibility	136-137
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (applicability) of pilot trial methods and findings to future definitive trial and other studies	133-137
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with pilot trial objectives and findings, balancing potential benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	133-137
	22a	Implications for progression from pilot to future definitive trial, including any proposed amendments	133-137
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number for pilot trial and name of trial registry	N/A
Protocol	24	Where the pilot trial protocol can be accessed, if available	N/A
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	N/A
	26	Ethical approval or approval by research review committee, confirmed with reference number	52

Appendix 16. CONSORT checklist (Study 4)

Section/Topic	No	Checklist item	Page
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a pilot or feasibility randomised trial in the title	138
	1b	Structured summary of pilot trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT abstract extension for pilot trials)	N/A
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale for future definitive trial, and reasons for randomised pilot trial	138-142
	2b	Specific objectives or research questions for pilot trial	142
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of pilot trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	143
	3b	Important changes to methods after pilot trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	N/A
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	143
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	Not reported
	4c	How participants were identified and consented	53
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	143-148
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined prespecified assessments or measurements to address each pilot trial objective specified in 2b, including how and when they were assessed	59-62, 148-152
	6b	Any changes to pilot trial assessments or measurements after the pilot trial commenced, with reasons	N/A
	6c	If applicable, prespecified criteria used to judge whether, or how, to proceed with future definitive trial	N/A
Sample size	7a	Rationale for numbers in the pilot trial	143
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	N/A
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	N/A
	8b	Type of randomisation(s); details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	N/A
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	N/A
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	N/A
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	N/A
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	N/A

Statistical methods	12	Methods used to address each pilot trial objective whether qualitative or quantitative	148-152
Results			
Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were approached and/or assessed for eligibility, randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were assessed for each objective	157
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	157
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	Not reported
	14b	Why the pilot trial ended or was stopped	Not reported
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	155
Numbers analysed	16	For each objective, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis. If relevant, these numbers should be by randomised group	157, 162, 163
Outcomes and estimation	17	For each objective, results including expressions of uncertainty (such as 95% confidence interval) for any estimates. If relevant, these results should be by randomised group.	154-164
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed that could be used to inform the future definitive trial	N/A
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	N/A
	19a	If relevant, other important unintended consequences	N/A
Discussion			
Limitations	20	Pilot trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias and remaining uncertainty about feasibility	169-170
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (applicability) of pilot trial methods and findings to future definitive trial and other studies	164-169
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with pilot trial objectives and findings, balancing potential benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	164-169
	22a	Implications for progression from pilot to future definitive trial, including any proposed amendments	164-169
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number for pilot trial and name of trial registry	N/A
Protocol	24	Where the pilot trial protocol can be accessed, if available	N/A
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	N/A
	26	Ethical approval or approval by research review committee, confirmed with reference number	52

Appendix 17. SMS by topics and theoretical framework

Topic: Increasing PA and reducing SB
Theoretical framework: Theory of Planned Behaviour
Attitude
Being active increases muscle strength and endurance. It also improves your academic abilities and overall health and wellbeing! Try to move more and sit less!
Being active can be really enjoyable - walking, exercising, cycling! It improves your health and wellbeing and can be fun! Especially after a long day.
If you think you will sit a lot this weekend, try being active instead! All activities count, and the more, the better.
Activity is great for your mental health! You could feel focused and energetic. We want you to feel these benefits. You could try to stand/walk at lunch today!
Perceived behavioural control
Exercise doesn't have to take long! A short fast walk, a quick workout, playing sports or simply standing up when on the phone or watching TV could really help!
Adding activity to your day can be easy, just give it a go: 15 minutes running, 45 mins walking, standing up when on the phone or watching TV. You can do it!
What do you think: Can you change how active you are? KIM 1 I can, KIM 2 I can't
*KIM 1: Yes you can! We know you have the tools to be more active and achieve your goals. It's up to you and you are doing great. Well done!
*KIM 2: Confidence comes over time. You might not feel like it now but you can do it. Think about a day that was hard and you managed to be active! You are doing great!
Bad weather can make activities difficult. Try indoors! Walk around when on the phone, go to the gym or pool, do a workout at home. Try something today.
Intention
Changing habits is easier with a plan. Try walking or another activity for 1 hour this afternoon. You could cycle, run, do sports... Give it a go today! Kim.
It's important to be active for 1 hour every day and try to sit less. An easy 1-hour bike ride or standing up when on the phone - You could try it this weekend.
Physical activity is fun! You could ask your family/friends to be active with you this weekend. Make a plan and seeing them do it too might make it easier for you!
Goals are great! What will you do for 1 hour today? KIM 1 run, walk or exercise or play sports, KIM 2 stand watching TV, walk to school, stand between lessons
*KIM 1: These are great ways to improve your health and wellbeing. 1 hour will fly by if you're having fun! We know you can achieve your goal for today!
*KIM 2: These are great ways to improve your health and wellbeing. Sitting less is important and little changes can make a big difference. Kim.
Subjective norm
Messages in the media agree that physical activity is good for you. We think being more active is important and small changes can make a difference.
Whatever activity you like to do - you are not the only one! Try to start an activity this week and work up to 1 hour every day.
We are doing this program to help you be healthier. Thank you for taking part and using this opportunity! We all care about being active and know you might too.
On weekends, parks can be full of people being active. You could put on your trainers and go too. Walking around a shopping centre racks up steps too!
Theoretical framework: Self-efficacy, Social Cognitive Theory
Social support
Being active can be easier when you do it with others. Ask your family or friends - whatever you enjoy doing, doing it together can make it even more fun.

Many people in your class are getting the same SMS. Try to buddy up and do activities together. It helps keep you motivated and can be so much fun!
It can be hard to find time to be active. Ask your friends to stand/walk with you at lunch today. Together you could all achieve more.
Quick tip: planning activities with others can make it easier to stick to goals. Tomorrow, you could stand/walk between lessons or walk part of the way home.
Attainments
Question: What have you done this week to be active? Please reply KIM 1 if you were active, KIM 2 if you did nothing.
*KIM 1: Well done, be proud of what you have achieved and keep trying to reach your goals! Flo.
*KIM 2: That's okay. We are here to motivate you. Try something small every day. Maybe a 15-minute walk? You can do it!
You have completed week 2! Since we started sending you SMS, what have you tried? Reply KIM 1 for being active, KIM 2 for sitting less
*KIM 1: A big well done to you! It can be hard, but you are trying and that's what counts. Maybe set a new goal and keep going for it!
*KIM 2: Sitting less is important and you are doing so well! Little changes make a big difference. Set some goals and you will keep reaching them, we know it!
Please reply. What did you do this week so far? Were you more active? KIM 1 More active than usual, KIM 2 Less active than usual
*KIM 1: That's fantastic! You should feel really good about yourself. Maybe our tips have helped you a little but ultimately you did it! Well done.
*KIM 2: That's okay, being active can be a struggle but just try doing what you can. Try some activities this weekend, every little helps!
Quick question! Have you been active every day last week? KIM 1 Yes, KIM 2 No
*KIM 1: Well done! You have achieved a lot already. Try to keep doing it. The more you do it the easier it will get! 1 hour per day is great!
*KIM 2: Don't worry! Why not try it next week? 1 hour per day is the goal and you can do it by walking, exercising, playing football, dancing, cycling...
Judgement of physiological and affective states
Trying a new activity can be daunting. You might even feel stressed. Try not to put too much pressure on yourself. Start small. You'll get more confident!
Some worry about not being good enough to exercise or do sports. Everyone starts small. You don't have to be an elite athlete to be active and happy!
Question! How does being active make you feel? KIM 1 Amazing or good, KIM 2 Not any way in particular or worse
*KIM 1: Isn't it great how a little change like that can make you feel good? Feeling happier and healthier is great, well done!
*KIM 2: That's okay. Try something new or change your routine! Walk to school, cycle with friends, play sports - start small and you will enjoy it soon.
You don't have to be an elite athlete to go run or exercise. Feeling anxious about an activity is okay. Focus on your own progress and you might enjoy it!
Topic: Supporting healthy eating
Eating out
Top tips for eating out healthy: Share big portions, choose options without fried foods, go for lots of veg and lean red meat! Try it next time you eat out.
5 portions of fruit and vegetables per day
Hi, it's Kim. Try to have your 5 a day. Try different fruit and veg throughout the day. 2 portions are a good start, 3 better, 5 the best!
Snacks
It's Kim! Occasionally, treats are fine. If you have more, swap them for something low-sugar, low-fat or low-salt then healthy diet here we come!
Portion size
It can be tempting to choose a bucket of popcorn or big portion of nachos. We know! Just try a smaller portion next time you have a treat. Just as tasty!

School lunches

Having packed lunches? Maybe try wholegrain sandwiches or wraps with cold meat, houmous, cheese or egg, and add some veg like sweetcorn or cucumber! Delicious!

Balanced meals

Try this week: eat fruit or veg and low fat or wholegrain options. Even pasta, meat and pies can be healthy. Try to swap for a healthy option this week!

Drinking water

Did you know drinking lots of water makes you healthier? And it helps you concentrate! Try having 6-8 glasses every day.

* pre-determined, automated response sent by the research team

Appendix 18. Focus group interview guide (Study 4)

Experience of receiving text messages		
Reasons for participation	Why did you decide to take part in our study? What were your thoughts on receiving text messages to help you be more active and sit less?	How did you feel/think about changing your health behaviours?
Preference of SMS content	What did you think about the messages we sent you? What did you think about the information, tips and advice we sent you? Which messages were most/least relevant/useful to you?	How did you feel when you got our messages? What about the messages did you find most useful or interesting?
	Were there any messages you didn't find useful?	What about these messages made them not useful for you?
Participant preferences		
Preferences of SMS design	What do you think about the language and tone of the messages you got sent? How do you feel about the frequency of messages? How did you feel about the timing of messages? How did you find the length of messages?	Did the language we used have an impact on how useful the message was for helping you to be more active? How did you find the number of messages you got each week? Was it useful and appropriate? How did you find the time of day we sent you messages at? Was it useful? Was it appropriate?
Perceived intervention effectiveness		
Behaviour change	What, if anything, did you change as a result of receiving our messages? What was your reaction after receiving one of our messages?	What effects did the messages have on you? What impact did the messages have on your physical activity? What impact did the messages have on how much you sit? What impact did the messages have on your diet?
Barriers to behaviour change	What made it hard for you to follow our advice? What were the reasons you didn't or couldn't change your behaviours?	Was there anything about the messages that made you not change your behaviours?
Facilitators for behaviour change	What made it easy for you to follow our advice?	Was there anything about the messages that helped you to change your behaviours?
Suggestions and feedback		
What suggestions do you have for improving the text messages you got sent? What could we change to make sure the messages help you be more active and healthier?		If you would take part again, what would you like to see/read? What would help you (more)?

Appendix 19. Psychological and healthy eating outcome questionnaires

First name: _____

Last name: _____

Please answer the following questions by ticking the boxes.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

The questions ask you about whether you do or plan to do regular physical activity.

Regular physical activity means you are active for at least 1 hour every day of the week.

For example, in a day you could walk to school and back for 30 minutes and go to the gym or ride your bike for 30 minutes. It could also mean walking your dog for 20 minutes and have netball for 40 minutes.

Activities can be anything like walking, cycling, playground activities, doing gardening, running, gym exercise and sports like hockey, football, dancing, or rugby.

Please answer all questions with either YES or NO

1. Do you currently engage in regular physical activity? YES NO

2. Do you intend to engage in regular physical activity in the next 6 months? YES NO

3. Do you intend to engage in regular physical activity in the next 30 days? YES NO

4. Have you been regularly physically active for the past 6 months? YES NO

Please answer the following questions by ticking the boxes.

SITTING TIME

The questions ask you about whether you currently try to or plan to **reduce your sitting time**.

Sitting time means any activities you do sitting down. This can be watching TV, playing video games, studying, sitting at school, sitting down speaking to your friends on the phone or listening to music or watching videos or shows online.

We want to know if you currently do or plan to either sit less by not doing these activities or by getting up or walking every now and again whilst you do these things.

Please answer the following questions with either YES or NO

1. Do you currently limit your sitting time? YES NO
2. Do you intend to limit your sitting time in the next 6 months? YES NO
3. Do you intend to limit your sitting time in the next 30 days? YES NO
4. Have you been limiting your sitting time for the past 6 months? YES NO

Please answer by filling in the circle in the correct column.

If I were to be PHYSICALLY ACTIVE every day of the week...

	Disagree a lot	Disagree a little	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree a little	Agree a lot
1. It would help me cope with stress	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. It would be fun	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. It would help me make new friends	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. It would get or keep me in shape	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. It would make me more attractive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. It would give me more energy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. It would make me hot and sweaty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. It would make me better in sports, dance or other activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If I were to SIT LESS every day of the week...

	Disagree a lot	Disagree a little	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree a little	Agree a lot
1. It would help me cope with stress	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. It would be fun	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. It would help me make new friends	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. It would get or keep me in shape	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. It would make me more attractive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. It would give me more energy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Please answer by filling in the circle in the correct column.

	Disagree a lot	Disagree a little	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree a little	Agree a lot
1. I can be physically active for at least 1 hour every day of the week.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. I can ask my parent or other adult to do physically active things with me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. I can be physically active every day of the week even if I could watch TV or play video games instead.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I can be physically active every day of the week even if it is very hot or cold outside.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. I can ask my best friend to be physically active with me every day of the week.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. I can be physically active every day of the week even if I have to stay at home.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. I have the coordination I need to be physically active every day of the week.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. I can be physically active every day of the week no matter how busy my day is.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

SITTING TIME

Please answer by filling in the circle in the correct column.

	I'm sure I can't	I probably can't	Neutral	I probably can	I'm sure I can
1. Turn off the TV even when there is a program on you enjoy?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. Limit your computer or smartphone game playing time to 1 hour a day?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. Leave the room where the TV is on even if others are watching TV?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Plan ahead of time what TV or online shows you will watch during the week?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Instead of just listening to music, listen while you are being active (e.g. walking or dancing)?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Set limits on how long you plan to talk on the phone or online with friends?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. Limit watching shows on TV or online, video and computer games to only 2 hours per day?	<input type="radio"/>				

Please fill this circle if you never have access to electronic devices such as TV, mobile or smartphone, tablet, video game console, computer or lap top.

Please answer by ticking 1 grey box for each question.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

I intend to do physical activities for at least 1 hour every day next week.

Likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unlikely						
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SITTING TIME

I intend to sit less every day next week.

Likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unlikely						
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PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Most people important to me think I should do physical activities for at least 1 hour every day.

Likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unlikely						
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SITTING TIME

Most people important to me think I should sit less.

Likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unlikely						
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Please answer by filling in the circle in the correct column.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

	Very easy	Somewhat easy	Neither easy nor difficult	Somewhat difficult	Very difficult
For me to be physically active for at least 1 hour every day would be	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Disagree a lot	Disagree a little	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree a little	Agree a lot
I have control over my being physically active for at least 1 hour every day.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe I have all the things I need to be physically active for at least 1 hour every day.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I want to be, I can be physically active for at least 1 hour every day.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

SITTING TIME

	Very easy	Somewhat easy	Neither easy nor difficult	Somewhat difficult	Very difficult
For me to reduce my daily sitting time would be	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Disagree a lot	Disagree a little	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree a little	Agree a lot
I have control over reducing my daily sitting time .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe I have all the things I need to reduce my daily sitting time .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I want to be, I can reduce my daily sitting time .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please tick the box that is right for you most of the time

<p>1) If I am having lunch away from home, I often chose a low-fat option.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never have lunch away from home.</p>	<p>2) I usually avoid eating fried foods.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>3) I usually eat a desert or pudding if one is available.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	<p>4) I make sure I eat at least one serving of fruit a day.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>5) I keep my overall fat intake down.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	<p>6) If I am buying crisps, I often chose a low-fat brand.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False <input type="checkbox"/> I never buy crisps.</p>
<p>7) I avoid eating lots of sausages and burgers.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never eat sausages or burgers</p>	<p>8) I often buy pastries or cakes.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>9) I try to keep my overall sugar intake down.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	<p>10) I make sure I eat at least 1 serving of vegetables or salad a day.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>11) If I am having dessert at home, I try to have something low in fat.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False <input type="checkbox"/> I don't eat desserts.</p>	<p>12) I rarely eat takeaway meals.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>13) I try to ensure that I eat plenty of fruit and vegetables.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	<p>14) I often eat sweet snacks between meals.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>15) I usually eat at least one serving of vegetables (excluding potatoes) or salad with my evening meal.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	<p>16) When I am buying a soft drink, I usually choose a diet drink.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>17) When I put butter or margarine on bread, I usually spread it on thinly.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never have butter/margarine on bread.</p>	<p>18) If I have a packed lunch, I usually include some chocolate and/or biscuits.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never have a packed lunch.</p>
<p>19) When I chose to have a snack between meals, I often choose fruit.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never eat snacks between meals.</p>	<p>20) If I am having a dessert or pudding in a restaurant, I usually choose the healthiest one.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I never have desserts in restaurants.</p>
<p>21) I often have cream on desserts.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False <input type="checkbox"/> I don't eat desserts.</p>	<p>22) I eat at least 3 servings of fruit most days.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>
<p>23) I generally try to have a healthy diet. <input type="checkbox"/> True <input type="checkbox"/> False</p>	

THANK YOU FOR COMPLETING THESE QUESTIONNAIRES!

